

Patterned Single Letter Representations of Natural Numbers

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Abstract

*This work brings patterned representations of natural numbers from 1 to 1000 in terms of single letter a . For any value of letter a from 1 to 9, the results are always same. To bring these results, only basic operations, such as **addition**, **subtraction**, **multiplication** and **division** are used. This work is extension of author's [11] work in patterned form. Patterns representations are some what similar to symmetrical extensions. For similar kind of work in different way refer Taneja [12].*

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1 Introduction

1.1 Single Letter Representations

Let us consider

$$f^n(10) = 10^n + 10^{n-1} + \dots + 10^2 + 10 + 10^0,$$

For $a \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9\}$, we can write

$$af^n(10) = \underbrace{aaa\dots a}_{(n+1)\text{-times}},$$

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In particular,

$$\begin{aligned}
 aa &:= f^1(10) = a10 + a \\
 aaa &:= f^2(10) = a10^2 + a10 + a \\
 aaaa &:= f^3(10) = a10^3 + a10^2 + a10 + a \\
 aaaaa &:= f^4(10) = a10^4 + a10^3 + a10^2 + a10 + a \\
 &\dots
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

For example, one can write

$$\begin{aligned}
 5 &:= \frac{aa - a}{a + a} = \frac{11 - 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{22 - 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{33 - 3}{3 + 3} = \frac{44 - 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{55 - 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{66 - 6}{6 + 6} = \frac{77 - 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{88 - 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{99 - 9}{9 + 9} \\
 56 &:= \frac{aaa + a}{a + a} = \frac{111 + 1}{1 + 1} = \frac{222 + 2}{2 + 2} = \frac{333 + 3}{3 + 3} = \frac{444 + 4}{4 + 4} = \frac{555 + 5}{5 + 5} = \frac{666 + 6}{6 + 6} = \frac{777 + 7}{7 + 7} = \frac{888 + 8}{8 + 8} = \frac{999 + 9}{9 + 9} \\
 111 &:= \frac{aaa}{a} = \frac{111}{1} = \frac{222}{2} = \frac{333}{3} = \frac{444}{4} = \frac{555}{5} = \frac{666}{6} = \frac{777}{7} = \frac{888}{8} = \frac{999}{9} \\
 &\dots
 \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

Detailed study on **single digit** representations can be seen in Taneja [4, 6, 7, 8]. Here below are more examples:

$$\begin{aligned}
 717 &:= (1 + 1)^{11} - 11^{(1+1+1)} &= 22^2 + 222 + 22/2 &= 3^{(3+3)} - 3 - 3 \times 3 \\
 &= 4 \times (4 \times 44 + 4) - 4 + 4/4 &= (55 \times (55 + 5 + 5) + 5 + 5)/5 &= (6 \times 6 / (6 + 6))^6 - 6 - 6 \\
 &= 777 - 7 \times 7 - 77/7 &= 8 \times 88 + (88 + 8 + 8)/8 &= 9 \times 9 \times 9 - (99 + 9)/9 \\
 923 &= (1 + 1)^{(11-1)} + 11 - 111 - 1 &= 2 \times (22^2 - 22) - 2/2 &= 33 + 33 \times 3^3 - 3/3 \\
 &= 44 + 44 \times (4 \times 4 + 4) - 4/4 &= 5 \times (55 + 5) + (5^5 - 5 - 5)/5 &= (6 + 6 + 6/6) \times (66 + 6 - 6/6) \\
 &= 77 \times (77 + 7)/7 - 7/7 &= 888 + 8 + 8 + 8 + 88/8 &= 9 \times 99 + 9 + (99 + 99 + 9)/9 \\
 995 &= (11 - 1)^{(1+1+1)} - (11 - 1)/(1 + 1) &= 22 + 2 \times (22^2 + 2) + 2/2 &= 3 \times 333 - 3 - 3/3 \\
 &= 4 \times (4^4 - 4 - 4) + 4 - 4/4 &= 5 \times (5 + 5) \times (5 \times 5 - 5) - 5 &= 666 + 6 \times 66 - 66 - 6/6 \\
 &= (7 + 7) \times (77 - 7) + 7 + 7 + 7/7 &= 888 + 88 + 8 + 88/8 &= 999 - (9 + 9 + 9 + 9)/9.
 \end{aligned}$$

We see that the above numbers are written in **fractional-type** given by author [9]. The similar kind of work is done by author [4, 10] for **single letter a**. See below some examples,

$$\begin{aligned}
 717 &:= ((aaa - a) \times aa / (a + a) + aaa + a) / a \\
 923 &:= (aaaaa - aa - aa - aa - a - a) / (aa + a) \\
 995 &:= (aaaa - aaa - a - a - a - a - a) \\
 &\dots \dots
 \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

Above results are valid for any value of $a \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9\}$ with the properties given in (1). The another advantage in working with **single letter** is that the representations are uniform. These types of representations, let us call as **running-type** and are already studied by author [6]. The same three numbers can also be represented as **fractional-type** See below:

$$\begin{aligned}
 717 &:= \frac{\frac{(aaa - a) \times aa}{a + a} + aaa + a}{a} = \frac{(aaa - a) \times aa + (aaa + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 923 &:= \frac{aaaaa - aa - aa - aa - a - a}{aa + a} \\
 995 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa - a - a - a - a - a}{a} \quad \dots \quad \dots
 \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

For more details of this type of work refer Taneja [13].

1.2 Patterned Representations

Let's see some examples of patterns with single letter a done by author in another work [12]:

Example 1.1.

$$\begin{aligned}
 11 &= 1 \times 11 & := \frac{a \times aa}{a \times a} \\
 1221 &= 11 \times 111 & := \frac{aa \times aaa}{a \times a} \\
 123321 &= 111 \times 1111 & := \frac{aaa \times aaaa}{a \times a} \\
 12344321 &= 1111 \times 11111 & := \frac{aaaa \times aaaaa}{a \times a} \\
 1234554321 &= 11111 \times 111111 & := \frac{aaaaa \times aaaaaa}{a \times a} \\
 123456654321 &= 111111 \times 1111111 & := \frac{aaaaaa \times aaaaaaa}{a \times a} \\
 12345677654321 &= 1111111 \times 11111111 & := \frac{aaaaaaa \times aaaaaaaa}{a \times a} \\
 1234567887654321 &= 11111111 \times 111111111 & := \frac{aaaaaaaa \times aaaaaaaaa}{a \times a} \\
 123456789987654321 &= 111111111 \times 1111111111 & := \frac{aaaaaaaaa \times aaaaaaaaaa}{a \times a}
 \end{aligned}$$

Example 1.2.

$$\begin{aligned}
 1 &= 0 \times 9 + 1 & := \frac{a}{a} \\
 11 &= 1 \times 9 + 2 & := \frac{aa}{a} \\
 111 &= 12 \times 9 + 3 & := \frac{aaa}{a} \\
 1111 &= 123 \times 9 + 4 & := \frac{aaaa}{a} \\
 11111 &= 1234 \times 9 + 5 & := \frac{aaaaa}{a} \\
 111111 &= 12345 \times 9 + 6 & := \frac{aaaaaa}{a} \\
 1111111 &= 123456 \times 9 + 7 & := \frac{aaaaaaa}{a} \\
 11111111 &= 1234567 \times 9 + 8 & := \frac{aaaaaaaa}{a} \\
 111111111 &= 12345678 \times 9 + 9 & := \frac{aaaaaaaaa}{a} \\
 1111111111 &= 123456789 \times 9 + 10 & := \frac{aaaaaaaaaa}{a}
 \end{aligned}$$

Example 1.3.

$$\begin{aligned}
 77 &= 76 + 1 & := \frac{aa}{a} \times \frac{aa - a - a - a - a}{a} \\
 777 &= 765 + 12 & := \frac{aaa}{a} \times \frac{aa - a - a - a - a}{a} \\
 7777 &= 7654 + 123 & := \frac{aaaa}{a} \times \frac{aa - a - a - a - a}{a} \\
 777777 &= 76543 + 1234 & := \frac{aaaaa}{a} \times \frac{aa - a - a - a - a}{a} \\
 7777777 &= 765432 + 12345 & := \frac{aaaaaa}{a} \times \frac{aa - a - a - a - a}{a} \\
 77777777 &= 7654321 + 123456 & := \frac{aaaaaaa}{a} \times \frac{aa - a - a - a - a}{a} \\
 777777777 &= 76543210 + 1234567 & := \frac{aaaaaaaa}{a} \times \frac{aa - a - a - a - a}{a}
 \end{aligned}$$

Example 1.4.

$$\begin{aligned}
 88 &= 9 \times 9 + 7 & := \frac{aa - a - a - a}{a} \times \frac{aa}{a} \\
 888 &= 98 \times 9 + 6 & := \frac{aa - a - a - a}{a} \times \frac{aaa}{a} \\
 8888 &= 987 \times 9 + 5 & := \frac{aa - a - a - a}{a} \times \frac{aaaa}{a} \\
 88888 &= 9876 \times 9 + 4 & := \frac{aa - a - a - a}{a} \times \frac{aaaaa}{a} \\
 888888 &= 98765 \times 9 + 3 & := \frac{aa - a - a - a}{a} \times \frac{aaaaaa}{a} \\
 8888888 &= 987654 \times 9 + 2 & := \frac{aa - a - a - a}{a} \times \frac{aaaaaaa}{a} \\
 88888888 &= 9876543 \times 9 + 1 & := \frac{aa - a - a - a}{a} \times \frac{aaaaaaaa}{a} \\
 888888888 &= 98765432 \times 9 + 0 & := \frac{aa - a - a - a}{a} \times \frac{aaaaaaaaa}{a} \\
 8888888888 &= 987654321 \times 9 - 1 & := \frac{aa - a - a - a}{a} \times \frac{aaaaaaaaaa}{a} \\
 88888888888 &= 9876543210 \times 9 - 2 & := \frac{aa - a - a - a}{a} \times \frac{aaaaaaaaaaa}{a}
 \end{aligned}$$

Example 1.5.

$$\begin{aligned}
 121 &= 11 \times 11 & := \frac{aa \times aa}{a \times a \times a} \\
 1221 &= 11 \times 111 & := \frac{aa \times aaa}{a \times a \times a} \\
 12221 &= 11 \times 1111 & := \frac{aa \times aaaa}{a \times a \times a} \\
 122221 &= 11 \times 11111 & := \frac{aa \times aaaaa}{a \times a \times a} \\
 1222221 &= 11 \times 111111 & := \frac{aa \times aaaaaa}{a \times a \times a}
 \end{aligned}$$

Example 1.6.

$$\begin{aligned}
 16^2 &= 256 & := \left(\frac{aa + aa + aa - a}{a + a} \right)^{\frac{a+a}{a}} \\
 166^2 &= 27556 & := \left(\frac{aaa + aaa + aaa - a}{a + a} \right)^{\frac{a+a}{a}} \\
 1666^2 &= 2775556 & := \left(\frac{aaaa + aaaa + aaaa - a}{a + a} \right)^{\frac{a+a}{a}} \\
 16666^2 &= 277755556 & := \left(\frac{aaaaa + aaaaa + aaaaa - a}{a + a} \right)^{\frac{a+a}{a}} \\
 166666^2 &= 27777555556 & := \left(\frac{aaaaaa + aaaaaa + aaaaaa - a}{a + a} \right)^{\frac{a+a}{a}}
 \end{aligned}$$

Example 1.7.

$$\begin{aligned}
 34^2 = 1156 & := \left(\frac{aa + aa + aa + a}{a} \right)^{\frac{a+a}{a}} \\
 334^2 = 111556 & := \left(\frac{aaa + aaa + aaa + a}{a} \right)^{\frac{a+a}{a}} \\
 3334^2 = 11115556 & := \left(\frac{aaaa + aaaa + aaaa + a}{a} \right)^{\frac{a+a}{a}} \\
 33334^2 = 1111155556 & := \left(\frac{aaaaa + aaaaa + aaaaa + a}{a} \right)^{\frac{a+a}{a}} \\
 333334^2 = 111111555556 & := \left(\frac{aaaaaa + aaaaaa + aaaaaa + a}{a} \right)^{\frac{a+a}{a}}
 \end{aligned}$$

More details on examples refer to author's work [12]. Let's write representations of six numbers given in Expressions (2) and (4) in pattern forms:

$$\begin{aligned}
 5 & := \frac{aa - a}{a + a} & 6 & := \frac{aaa + a}{a + a} \\
 55 & := \frac{aaa - a}{a + a} & 56 & := \frac{aaaa + a}{a + a} \\
 555 & := \frac{aaaa - a}{a + a} & 556 & := \frac{aaaaa + a}{a + a} \\
 5555 & := \frac{aaaaa - a}{a + a} & 5556 & := \frac{aaaaaa + a}{a + a}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 111 & := \frac{aaa}{a} & 717 & := \frac{(aaa - a) \times aa + (aaa + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 1111 & := \frac{aaaa}{a} & 1717 & := \frac{(aaa - a) \times aa + (aaaa + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 11111 & := \frac{aaaaa}{a} & 11717 & := \frac{(aaa - a) \times aa + (aaaaa + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 111111 & := \frac{aaaaaa}{a} & 111717 & := \frac{(aaa - a) \times aa + (aaaaaa + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 923 & := \frac{aaaaa - aa - aa - aa - a - a}{aa + a} & 995 & := \frac{aaaa - aaa - a - a - a - a - a}{a} \\
 925923 & := \frac{aaaaaaaa - aa - aa - aa - a - a}{aa + a} & 9995 & := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - a - a - a - a - a}{a} \\
 925925923 & := \frac{aaaaaaaaaaa - aa - aa - aa - a - a}{aa + a} & 99995 & := \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa - a - a - a - a - a}{a} \\
 925925925923 & := \frac{aaaaaaaaaaaaa - aa - aa - aa - a - a}{aa + a} & 999995 & := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaaaa - a - a - a - a - a}{a}
 \end{aligned}$$

The aim of this work is to write the numbers 1 to 1000 in patterns forms similar to as given in above six numbers. It is done in section below. In another work we have written same numbers for the digits 1 to 9 separately (refer [13]).

2 Patterns in Fraction-Type Single Letter Representations

Below are **fraction-type** representations of natural numbers from 1 to 1000 using **single letter** a , with the property given in (1), where $a \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9\}$. We write these representations as **patterns in single letters representations**. In order to bring these representations only basic operations, such as, **addition, subtraction, multiplication and division** are used. By no means, we can say that these representations are unique. There may have alternative ways of representations with less or more number of letters " a ". Any way, if these representations are not minimum, but are very near to minimum.

$$\begin{aligned} 1 &:= \frac{a}{a} \\ 11 &:= \frac{aa}{a} \\ 111 &:= \frac{aaa}{a} \\ 1111 &:= \frac{aaaa}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2 &:= \frac{a+a}{a} \\ 12 &:= \frac{aa+a}{a} \\ 112 &:= \frac{aaa+a}{a} \\ 1112 &:= \frac{aaaa+a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3 &:= \frac{a+a+a}{a} \\ 13 &:= \frac{aa+a+a}{a} \\ 113 &:= \frac{aaa+a+a}{a} \\ 1113 &:= \frac{aaaa+a+a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4 &:= \frac{a+a+a+a}{a} \\ 14 &:= \frac{aa+a+a+a}{a} \\ 114 &:= \frac{aaa+a+a+a}{a} \\ 1114 &:= \frac{aaaa+a+a+a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5 &:= \frac{aa-a}{a+a} \\ 55 &:= \frac{aaa-a}{a+a} \\ 555 &:= \frac{aaaa-a}{a+a} \\ 5555 &:= \frac{aaaaa-a}{a+a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6 &:= \frac{aa+a}{a+a} \\ 56 &:= \frac{aaa+a}{a+a} \\ 556 &:= \frac{aaaa+a}{a+a} \\ 5556 &:= \frac{aaaaa+a}{a+a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7 &:= \frac{aa+a+a+a}{a+a} \\ 57 &:= \frac{aaa+a+a+a}{a+a} \\ 557 &:= \frac{aaaa+a+a+a}{a+a} \\ 5557 &:= \frac{aaaaa+a+a+a}{a+a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8 &:= \frac{aa-a-a-a}{a} \\ 98 &:= \frac{aaa-aa-a-a}{a} \\ 998 &:= \frac{aaaa-aaa-a-a}{a} \\ 9998 &:= \frac{aaaaa-aaaa-a-a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9 &:= \frac{aa - a - a}{a} \\ 99 &:= \frac{aaa - aa - a}{a} \\ 999 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa - a}{a} \\ 9999 &:= \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 10 &:= \frac{aa - a}{a} \\ 110 &:= \frac{aaa - a}{a} \\ 1110 &:= \frac{aaaa - a}{a} \\ 11110 &:= \frac{aaaaa - a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 11 &:= \frac{aa}{a} \\ 111 &:= \frac{aaa}{a} \\ 1111 &:= \frac{aaaa}{a} \\ 11111 &:= \frac{aaaaa}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 12 &:= \frac{aa + a}{a} \\ 112 &:= \frac{aaa + a}{a} \\ 1112 &:= \frac{aaaa + a}{a} \\ 11112 &:= \frac{aaaaa + a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 13 &:= \frac{aa + a + a}{a} \\ 113 &:= \frac{aaa + a + a}{a} \\ 1113 &:= \frac{aaaa + a + a}{a} \\ 11113 &:= \frac{aaaaa + a + a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 14 &:= \frac{aa + a + a + a}{a} \\ 114 &:= \frac{aaa + a + a + a}{a} \\ 1114 &:= \frac{aaaa + a + a + a}{a} \\ 11114 &:= \frac{aaaaa + a + a + a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 15 &:= \frac{aa + a + a + a + a}{a} \\ 115 &:= \frac{aaa + a + a + a + a}{a} \\ 1115 &:= \frac{aaaa + a + a + a + a}{a} \\ 11115 &:= \frac{aaaaa + a + a + a + a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 16 &:= \frac{aa - a}{a + a} + \frac{aa}{a} \\ 116 &:= \frac{aa - a}{a + a} + \frac{aaa}{a} \\ 1116 &:= \frac{aa - a}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa}{a} \\ 11116 &:= \frac{aa - a}{a + a} + \frac{aaaaa}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 17 &:= \frac{aa + a}{a + a} + \frac{aa}{a} \\ 117 &:= \frac{aa + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaa}{a} \\ 1117 &:= \frac{aa + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa}{a} \\ 11117 &:= \frac{aa + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaaaa}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 18 &:= \frac{(aa - a - a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\ 198 &:= \frac{(aa - a - a) \times (aa + aa)}{a \times a} \\ 1998 &:= \frac{(aa - a - a) \times (aaa + aaa)}{a \times a} \\ 19998 &:= \frac{(aa - a - a) \times (aaaa + aaaa)}{a \times a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 19 &:= \frac{aa + aa - a - a - a}{a} \\ 119 &:= \frac{aaa + aa - a - a - a}{a} \\ 1119 &:= \frac{aaaa + aa - a - a - a}{a} \\ 11119 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aa - a - a - a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 20 &:= \frac{aa + aa - a - a}{a} \\ 120 &:= \frac{aaa + aa - a - a}{a} \\ 1120 &:= \frac{aaaa + aa - a - a}{a} \\ 11120 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aa - a - a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 21 &:= \frac{aa + aa - a}{a} \\ 121 &:= \frac{aaa + aa - a}{a} \\ 1121 &:= \frac{aaaa + aa - a}{a} \\ 11121 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aa - a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 22 &:= \frac{aa + aa}{a} \\ 122 &:= \frac{aaa + aa}{a} \\ 1222 &:= \frac{aaaa + aaa}{a} \\ 12222 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aaaa}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 23 &:= \frac{aa + aa + a}{a} \\ 123 &:= \frac{aaa + aa + a}{a} \\ 1223 &:= \frac{aaaa + aaa + a}{a} \\ 12223 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aaaa + a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24 &:= \frac{aa + aa + a + a}{a} \\ 124 &:= \frac{aaa + aa + a + a}{a} \\ 1124 &:= \frac{aaaa + aa + a + a}{a} \\ 11124 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aa + a + a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25 &:= \frac{aa + aa + a + a + a}{a} \\ 125 &:= \frac{aaa + aa + a + a + a}{a} \\ 1125 &:= \frac{aaaa + aa + a + a + a}{a} \\ 11125 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aa + a + a + a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 26 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\ 226 &:= \frac{(aaa + a + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\ 2226 &:= \frac{(aaaa + a + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\ 22226 &:= \frac{(aaaaa + a + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 27 &:= \frac{aaa - a - a - a}{a + a + a + a} \\ 277 &:= \frac{aaaa - a - a - a}{a + a + a + a} \\ 2777 &:= \frac{aaaaa - a - a - a}{a + a + a + a} \\ 27777 &:= \frac{aaaaa - a - a - a}{a + a + a + a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 28 &:= \frac{aaa + a}{a + a + a + a} \\ 228 &:= \frac{aaaa + a}{a + a + a + a} \\ 2778 &:= \frac{aaaaa + a}{a + a + a + a} \\ 27778 &:= \frac{aaaaa + a}{a + a + a + a} \end{aligned}$$

$$29 := \frac{aa + aa + aa - a - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$129 := \frac{aa + aa + aaa - a - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$1129 := \frac{aa + aa + aaaa - a - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$11129 := \frac{aa + aa + aaaaa - a - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$30 := \frac{aa + aa + aa - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$130 := \frac{aa + aa + aaa - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$1130 := \frac{aa + aa + aaaa - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$11130 := \frac{aa + aa + aaaaa - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$31 := \frac{aa + aa + aa - a - a}{a}$$

$$131 := \frac{aa + aa + aaa - a - a}{a}$$

$$1131 := \frac{aa + aa + aaaa - a - a}{a}$$

$$11131 := \frac{aa + aa + aaaaa - a - a}{a}$$

$$32 := \frac{aa + aa + aa - a}{a}$$

$$132 := \frac{aa + aa + aaa - a}{a}$$

$$1132 := \frac{aa + aa + aaaa - a}{a}$$

$$11132 := \frac{aa + aa + aaaaa - a}{a}$$

$$33 := \frac{aa + aa + aa}{a}$$

$$133 := \frac{aa + aa + aaa}{a}$$

$$1133 := \frac{aa + aa + aaaa}{a}$$

$$11133 := \frac{aa + aa + aaaaa}{a}$$

$$34 := \frac{aa + aa + aa + a}{a}$$

$$134 := \frac{aa + aa + aaa + a}{a}$$

$$1134 := \frac{aa + aa + aaaa + a}{a}$$

$$11134 := \frac{aa + aa + aaaaa + a}{a}$$

$$35 := \frac{aa + aa + aa + a + a}{a}$$

$$135 := \frac{aa + aa + aaa + a + a}{a}$$

$$1135 := \frac{aa + aa + aaaa + a + a}{a}$$

$$11135 := \frac{aa + aa + aaaaa + a + a}{a}$$

$$36 := \frac{aa + aa + aa + a + a + a}{a}$$

$$136 := \frac{aa + aa + aaa + a + a + a}{a}$$

$$1136 := \frac{aa + aa + aaaa + a + a + a}{a}$$

$$11136 := \frac{aa + aa + aaaaa + a + a + a}{a}$$

$$37 := \frac{aaa}{a + a + a}$$

$$370 := \frac{aaaa - a}{a + a + a}$$

$$3700 := \frac{aaaaa - aa}{a + a + a}$$

$$37000 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaa}{a + a + a}$$

$$38 := \frac{aaa - aa - aa - aa - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$538 := \frac{aaaa - aa - aa - aa - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$5538 := \frac{aaaaa - aa - aa - aa - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$55538 := \frac{aaaaaa - aa - aa - aa - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$39 := \frac{aaa - aa - aa - aa}{a + a}$$

$$539 := \frac{aaaa - aa - aa - aa}{a + a}$$

$$5539 := \frac{aaaaa - aa - aa - aa}{a + a}$$

$$55539 := \frac{aaaaaa - aa - aa - aa}{a + a}$$

$$40 := \frac{(a + a + a + a) \times (aa - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$440 := \frac{(a + a + a + a) \times (aaa - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$4440 := \frac{(a + a + a + a) \times (aaaa - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$44440 := \frac{(a + a + a + a) \times (aaaaa - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$41 := \frac{aaa + aa + a}{a + a + a}$$

$$411 := \frac{aaaa + aaa + aa}{a + a + a}$$

$$4111 := \frac{aaaaa + aaaa + aaa}{a + a + a}$$

$$41111 := \frac{aaaaaa + aaaaa + aaaa}{a + a + a}$$

$$42 := \frac{(aa + aa - a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$242 := \frac{(aaa + aa - a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$2242 := \frac{(aaaa + aa - a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$22242 := \frac{(aaaaa + aa - a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$43 := \frac{(a + a + a + a) \times aa - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$443 := \frac{(a + a + a + a) \times aaa - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$4443 := \frac{(a + a + a + a) \times aaaa - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$44443 := \frac{(a + a + a + a) \times aaaaa - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$44 := \frac{(a + a + a + a) \times aa}{a \times a}$$

$$444 := \frac{(a + a + a + a) \times aaa}{a \times a}$$

$$4444 := \frac{(a + a + a + a) \times aaaa}{a \times a}$$

$$44444 := \frac{(a + a + a + a) \times aaaaa}{a \times a}$$

$$45 := \frac{aaa + a}{a + a} - \frac{aa}{a}$$

$$445 := \frac{aaaa + a}{a + a} - \frac{aaa}{a}$$

$$4445 := \frac{aaaaa + a}{a + a} - \frac{aaaa}{a}$$

$$44445 := \frac{aaaaaa + a}{a + a} - \frac{aaaaa}{a}$$

$$46 := \frac{(aa + aa + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$246 := \frac{(aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$2246 := \frac{(aaaa + aa + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$22246 := \frac{(aaaaa + aa + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$47 := \frac{(aa + aa + a) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$247 := \frac{(aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$2247 := \frac{(aaaa + aa + a) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$22247 := \frac{(aaaaa + aa + a) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$48 := \frac{aaa - aa - a - a - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$548 := \frac{aaaa - aa - a - a - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$5548 := \frac{aaaaa - aa - a - a - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$55548 := \frac{aaaaaa - aa - a - a - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$49 := \frac{aaa - aa - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$549 := \frac{aaaa - aa - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$5549 := \frac{aaaaa - aa - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$55549 := \frac{aaaaaa - aa - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$50 := \frac{aaa - aa}{a + a}$$

$$550 := \frac{aaaa - aa}{a + a}$$

$$5550 := \frac{aaaaa - aa}{a + a}$$

$$55550 := \frac{aaaaaa - aa}{a + a}$$

$$51 := \frac{aaa - aa + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$551 := \frac{aaaa - aa + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$5551 := \frac{aaaaa - aa + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$55551 := \frac{aaaaaa - aa + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$52 := \frac{(aa + a + a) \times (a + a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$452 := \frac{(aaa + a + a) \times (a + a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$4452 := \frac{(aaaa + a + a) \times (a + a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$44452 := \frac{(aaaaa + a + a) \times (a + a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$53 := \frac{aaa - a}{a + a} - \frac{a + a}{a}$$

$$553 := \frac{aaaa - a}{a + a} - \frac{a + a}{a}$$

$$5553 := \frac{aaaaa - a}{a + a} - \frac{a + a}{a}$$

$$55553 := \frac{aaaaaa - a}{a + a} - \frac{a + a}{a}$$

$$54 := \frac{aaa - a - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$554 := \frac{aaaa - a - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$5554 := \frac{aaaaa - a - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$55554 := \frac{aaaaaa - a - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$55 := \frac{aaa - a}{a + a}$$

$$555 := \frac{aaaa - a}{a + a}$$

$$5555 := \frac{aaaaa - a}{a + a}$$

$$55555 := \frac{aaaaaa - a}{a + a}$$

$$56 := \frac{aaa + a}{a + a}$$

$$556 := \frac{aaaa + a}{a + a}$$

$$5556 := \frac{aaaaa + a}{a + a}$$

$$55556 := \frac{aaaaaa + a}{a + a}$$

$$57 := \frac{aaa + a + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$557 := \frac{aaaa + a + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$5557 := \frac{aaaaa + a + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$55557 := \frac{aaaaaa + a + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$58 := \frac{aaa + a}{a + a} + \frac{a + a}{a}$$

$$558 := \frac{aaaa + a}{a + a} + \frac{a + a}{a}$$

$$5558 := \frac{aaaaa + a}{a + a} + \frac{a + a}{a}$$

$$55558 := \frac{aaaaaa + a}{a + a} + \frac{a + a}{a}$$

$$59 := \frac{aaa + aa - a - a - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$559 := \frac{aaaa + aa - a - a - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$5559 := \frac{aaaaa + aa - a - a - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$55559 := \frac{aaaaaa + aa - a - a - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$60 := \frac{aaa + aa - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$610 := \frac{aaaa + aaa - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$6110 := \frac{aaaaa + aaaa - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$61110 := \frac{aaaaaa + aaaaa - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$61 := \frac{aaa + aa}{a + a}$$

$$561 := \frac{aaaa + aa}{a + a}$$

$$5561 := \frac{aaaaa + aa}{a + a}$$

$$55561 := \frac{aaaaaa + aa}{a + a}$$

$$62 := \frac{aaa + aa + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$612 := \frac{aaaa + aaa + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$6112 := \frac{aaaaa + aaaa + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$61112 := \frac{aaaaaa + aaaaa + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$63 := \frac{aaa + aa + a + a + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$613 := \frac{aaaa + aaa + a + a + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$6113 := \frac{aaaaa + aaaa + a + a + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$61113 := \frac{aaaaaa + aaaaa + a + a + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$64 := \frac{(aa + a) \times aa - (a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$614 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times aa - (a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$6114 := \frac{(aaaa + a) \times aa - (a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$61114 := \frac{(aaaaa + a) \times aa - (a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$65 := \frac{aaa + aa + aa - a - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$565 := \frac{aaaa + aa + aa - a - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$5565 := \frac{aaaaa + aa + aa - a - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$55565 := \frac{aaaaaa + aa + aa - a - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$66 := \frac{aaa + aa + aa - a}{a + a}$$

$$566 := \frac{aaaa + aa + aa - a}{a + a}$$

$$5566 := \frac{aaaaa + aa + aa - a}{a + a}$$

$$55566 := \frac{aaaaaa + aa + aa - a}{a + a}$$

$$67 := \frac{aaa + aa + aa + a}{a + a}$$

$$567 := \frac{aaaa + aa + aa + a}{a + a}$$

$$5567 := \frac{aaaaa + aa + aa + a}{a + a}$$

$$55567 := \frac{aaaaaa + aa + aa + a}{a + a}$$

$$68 := \frac{aaa + a}{a + a} + \frac{aa + a}{a}$$

$$568 := \frac{aaaa + a}{a + a} + \frac{aa + a}{a}$$

$$5568 := \frac{aaaaa + a}{a + a} + \frac{aa + a}{a}$$

$$55568 := \frac{aaaaaa + a}{a + a} + \frac{aa + a}{a}$$

$$69 := \frac{aaa + a}{a + a} + \frac{aa + a + a}{a}$$

$$569 := \frac{aaaa + a}{a + a} + \frac{aa + a + a}{a}$$

$$5569 := \frac{aaaaa + a}{a + a} + \frac{aa + a + a}{a}$$

$$55569 := \frac{aaaaa + a}{a + a} + \frac{aa + a + a}{a}$$

$$70 := \frac{aaa + a}{a + a} + \frac{aa + a + a + a}{a}$$

$$570 := \frac{aaaa + a}{a + a} + \frac{aa + a + a + a}{a}$$

$$5570 := \frac{aaaaa + a}{a + a} + \frac{aa + a + a + a}{a}$$

$$55570 := \frac{aaaaa + a}{a + a} + \frac{aa + a + a + a}{a}$$

$$71 := \frac{aaa + a}{a + a} + \frac{aa + a + a + a + a}{a}$$

$$571 := \frac{aaaa + a}{a + a} + \frac{aa + a + a + a + a}{a}$$

$$5571 := \frac{aaaaa + a}{a + a} + \frac{aa + a + a + a + a}{a}$$

$$55571 := \frac{aaaaa + a}{a + a} + \frac{aa + a + a + a + a}{a}$$

$$72 := \frac{(aa + a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$672 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$6672 := \frac{(aaaa + a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$66672 := \frac{(aaaaa + a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$73 := \frac{aaa + aa + a + a}{a + a} + \frac{aa}{a}$$

$$723 := \frac{aaaa + aaa + a + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaa}{a}$$

$$7223 := \frac{aaaaa + aaaa + a + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa}{a}$$

$$72223 := \frac{aaaaaa + aaaaa + a + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaaaa}{a}$$

$$74 := \frac{aaa + aa + a + a}{a + a} + \frac{aa + a}{a}$$

$$724 := \frac{aaaa + aaa + a + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaa + a}{a}$$

$$7224 := \frac{aaaaa + aaaa + a + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa + a}{a}$$

$$72224 := \frac{aaaaaa + aaaaa + a + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaaaa + a}{a}$$

$$75 := \frac{aaa - aa - aa - aa - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$975 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aa - aa - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$9975 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - aa - aa - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$99975 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa - aa - aa - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$76 := \frac{aaa - aa - aa - aa - a - a}{a}$$

$$976 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aa - aa - a - a}{a}$$

$$9976 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - aa - aa - a - a}{a}$$

$$99976 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa - aa - aa - a - a}{a}$$

$$77 := \frac{aaa - aa - aa - aa - a}{a}$$

$$977 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aa - aa - a}{a}$$

$$9977 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - aa - aa - a}{a}$$

$$99977 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa - aa - aa - a}{a}$$

$$78 := \frac{aaa - aa - aa - aa}{a}$$

$$978 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aa - aa}{a}$$

$$9978 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - aa - aa}{a}$$

$$99978 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa - aa - aa}{a}$$

$$79 := \frac{aaa - aa - aa - aa + a}{a}$$

$$979 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aa - aa + a}{a}$$

$$9979 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - aa - aa + a}{a}$$

$$99979 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa - aa - aa + a}{a}$$

$$80 := \frac{aaa - aa - aa - aa + a + a}{a}$$

$$980 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aa - aa + a + a}{a}$$

$$9980 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - aa - aa + a + a}{a}$$

$$99980 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa - aa - aa + a + a}{a}$$

$$81 := \frac{(aa - a - a) \times (aa - a - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$981 := \frac{(aaa - a - a) \times (aa - a - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$9981 := \frac{(aaaa - a - a) \times (aa - a - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$99981 := \frac{(aaaaa - a - a) \times (aa - a - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$82 := \frac{(aa - a - a) \times (aa - a - a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$982 := \frac{(aa - a - a) \times (aaa - a - a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$9982 := \frac{(aa - a - a) \times (aaaa - a - a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$99982 := \frac{(aa - a - a) \times (aaaaa - a - a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$83 := \frac{(aa - a - a) \times (aa - a - a) + a \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$983 := \frac{(aa - a - a) \times (aaa - a - a) + a \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$9983 := \frac{(aa - a - a) \times (aaaa - a - a) + a \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$99983 := \frac{(aa - a - a) \times (aaaaa - a - a) + a \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$84 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a - a) \times (aa + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$784 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a - a) \times (aaa + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$7784 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a - a) \times (aaaa + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$77784 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a - a) \times (aaaaa + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$85 := \frac{aaa - aa - aa - a - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$985 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aa - a - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$9985 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - aa - a - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$99985 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa - aa - a - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$86 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aa - (a + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$886 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaa - (a + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$8886 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaa - (a + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$88886 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaaa - (a + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$87 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aa - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$887 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaa - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$8887 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaa - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$88887 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaaa - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$88 := \frac{aaa - aa - aa - a}{a}$$

$$988 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aa - a}{a}$$

$$9988 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - aa - a}{a}$$

$$999988 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa - aa - a}{a}$$

$$89 := \frac{aaa - aa - aa}{a}$$

$$989 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aa}{a}$$

$$9989 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - aa}{a}$$

$$999989 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa - aa}{a}$$

$$90 := \frac{aaa - aa - aa + a}{a}$$

$$990 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aa + a}{a}$$

$$9990 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - aa + a}{a}$$

$$999990 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa - aa + a}{a}$$

$$91 := \frac{aaa - aa - aa + a + a}{a}$$

$$991 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aa + a + a}{a}$$

$$9991 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - aa + a + a}{a}$$

$$99991 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa - aa + a + a}{a}$$

$$92 := \frac{aaa - aa - aa + a + a + a}{a}$$

$$992 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aa + a + a + a}{a}$$

$$9992 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - aa + a + a + a}{a}$$

$$99992 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa - aa + a + a + a}{a}$$

$$93 := \frac{aaa - aa - aa + a + a + a + a}{a}$$

$$993 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aa + a + a + a + a}{a}$$

$$9993 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - aa + a + a + a + a}{a}$$

$$99993 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa - aa + a + a + a + a}{a}$$

$$94 := \frac{aaa - aa - a - a - a - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$994 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - a - a - a - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$9994 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - a - a - a - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$99994 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa - a - a - a - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$95 := \frac{aaa - aa - a - a - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$995 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - a - a - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$9995 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - a - a - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$99995 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa - a - a - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$96 := \frac{aaa - aa - a - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$996 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - a - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$9996 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - a - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$99996 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa - a - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$97 := \frac{aaa - aa - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$997 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$9997 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$99997 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$98 := \frac{aaa - aa - a - a}{a}$$

$$998 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - a - a}{a}$$

$$9998 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - a - a}{a}$$

$$99998 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa - a - a}{a}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 99 &:= \frac{aaa - aa - a}{a} \\ 999 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa - a}{a} \\ 9999 &:= \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - a}{a} \\ 99999 &:= \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa - a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 100 &:= \frac{aaa - aa}{a} \\ 1100 &:= \frac{aaaa - aa}{a} \\ 11100 &:= \frac{aaaaa - aa}{a} \\ 111100 &:= \frac{aaaaaa - aa}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 101 &:= \frac{aaa - aa + a}{a} \\ 1001 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa + a}{a} \\ 10001 &:= \frac{aaaaa - aaaa + a}{a} \\ 100001 &:= \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa + a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 102 &:= \frac{aaa - aa + a + a}{a} \\ 1102 &:= \frac{aaaa - aa + a + a}{a} \\ 11102 &:= \frac{aaaaa - aa + a + a}{a} \\ 111102 &:= \frac{aaaaaa - aa + a + a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 103 &:= \frac{aaa - aa + a + a + a}{a} \\ 1003 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa + a + a + a}{a} \\ 10003 &:= \frac{aaaaa - aaaa + a + a + a}{a} \\ 100003 &:= \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa + a + a + a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 104 &:= \frac{aaa - aa + a + a + a + a}{a} \\ 1004 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa + a + a + a + a}{a} \\ 10004 &:= \frac{aaaaa - aaaa + a + a + a + a}{a} \\ 100004 &:= \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa + a + a + a + a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 105 &:= \frac{aaa - a - a - a - a - a - a}{a} \\ 1105 &:= \frac{aaaa - a - a - a - a - a - a}{a} \\ 11105 &:= \frac{aaaaa - a - a - a - a - a - a}{a} \\ 111105 &:= \frac{aaaaaa - a - a - a - a - a - a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 106 &:= \frac{aaa - a - a - a - a - a}{a} \\ 1106 &:= \frac{aaaa - a - a - a - a - a}{a} \\ 11106 &:= \frac{aaaaa - a - a - a - a - a}{a} \\ 111106 &:= \frac{aaaaaa - a - a - a - a - a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 107 &:= \frac{aaa - a - a - a - a}{a} \\ 1107 &:= \frac{aaaa - a - a - a - a}{a} \\ 11107 &:= \frac{aaaaa - a - a - a - a}{a} \\ 111107 &:= \frac{aaaaaa - a - a - a - a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 108 &:= \frac{aaa - a - a - a}{a} \\ 1108 &:= \frac{aaaa - a - a - a}{a} \\ 11108 &:= \frac{aaaaa - a - a - a}{a} \\ 111108 &:= \frac{aaaaaa - a - a - a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 109 &:= \frac{aaa - a - a}{a} \\ 1109 &:= \frac{aaaa - a - a}{a} \\ 11109 &:= \frac{aaaaa - a - a}{a} \\ 111109 &:= \frac{aaaaaa - a - a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 110 &:= \frac{aaa - a}{a} \\ 1110 &:= \frac{aaaa - a}{a} \\ 11110 &:= \frac{aaaaa - a}{a} \\ 111110 &:= \frac{aaaaaa - a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 111 &:= \frac{aaa}{a} \\ 1111 &:= \frac{aaaa}{a} \\ 11111 &:= \frac{aaaaa}{a} \\ 111111 &:= \frac{aaaaaa}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 112 &:= \frac{aaa + a}{a} \\ 1112 &:= \frac{aaaa + a}{a} \\ 11112 &:= \frac{aaaaa + a}{a} \\ 111112 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 113 &:= \frac{aaa + a + a}{a} \\ 1113 &:= \frac{aaaa + a + a}{a} \\ 11113 &:= \frac{aaaaa + a + a}{a} \\ 111113 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + a + a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 114 &:= \frac{aaa + a + a + a}{a} \\ 1114 &:= \frac{aaaa + a + a + a}{a} \\ 11114 &:= \frac{aaaaa + a + a + a}{a} \\ 111114 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + a + a + a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 115 &:= \frac{aaa + a + a + a + a}{a} \\ 1115 &:= \frac{aaaa + a + a + a + a}{a} \\ 11115 &:= \frac{aaaaa + a + a + a + a}{a} \\ 111115 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + a + a + a + a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 116 &:= \frac{aa - a}{a + a} + \frac{aaa}{a} \\ 1116 &:= \frac{aa - a}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa}{a} \\ 11116 &:= \frac{aa - a}{a + a} + \frac{aaaaa}{a} \\ 111116 &:= \frac{aa - a}{a + a} + \frac{aaaaaa}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 117 &:= \frac{aa + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaa}{a} \\ 1117 &:= \frac{aa + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa}{a} \\ 11117 &:= \frac{aa + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaaaa}{a} \\ 111117 &:= \frac{aa + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaaaaa}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 118 &:= \frac{aaa + aa - a - a - a - a}{a} \\ 1118 &:= \frac{aaaa + aa - a - a - a - a}{a} \\ 11118 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aa - a - a - a - a}{a} \\ 111118 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aa - a - a - a - a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 119 &:= \frac{aaa + aa - a - a - a}{a} \\ 1119 &:= \frac{aaaa + aa - a - a - a}{a} \\ 11119 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aa - a - a - a}{a} \\ 111119 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aa - a - a - a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 120 &:= \frac{aaa + aa - a - a}{a} \\ 1120 &:= \frac{aaaa + aa - a - a}{a} \\ 11120 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aa - a - a}{a} \\ 111120 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aa - a - a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 121 &:= \frac{aaa + aa - a}{a} \\ 1221 &:= \frac{aaaa + aaa - a}{a} \\ 12221 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aaaa - a}{a} \\ 122221 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aaaaa - a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 122 &:= \frac{aaa + aa}{a} \\ 1122 &:= \frac{aaaa + aa}{a} \\ 11122 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aa}{a} \\ 111122 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aa}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 123 &:= \frac{aaa + aa + a}{a} \\ 1123 &:= \frac{aaaa + aa + a}{a} \\ 11123 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aa + a}{a} \\ 111123 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aa + a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 124 &:= \frac{aaa + aa + a + a}{a} \\ 1124 &:= \frac{aaaa + aa + a + a}{a} \\ 11124 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aa + a + a}{a} \\ 111124 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aa + a + a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 125 &:= \frac{aaa + aa + a + a + a}{a} \\ 1125 &:= \frac{aaaa + aa + a + a + a}{a} \\ 11125 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aa + a + a + a}{a} \\ 111125 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aa + a + a + a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 126 &:= \frac{aaa + aa + a + a + a + a}{a} \\ 1126 &:= \frac{aaaa + aa + a + a + a + a}{a} \\ 11126 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aa + a + a + a + a}{a} \\ 111126 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aa + a + a + a + a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 127 &:= \frac{aaa + aa + a + a + a + a + a}{a} \\ 1127 &:= \frac{aaaa + aa + a + a + a + a + a}{a} \\ 11127 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aa + a + a + a + a + a}{a} \\ 111127 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aa + a + a + a + a + a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 128 &:= \frac{aaa + aa + a + a + a + a + a + a}{a} \\ 1128 &:= \frac{aaaa + aa + a + a + a + a + a + a}{a} \\ 11128 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aa + a + a + a + a + a + a}{a} \\ 111128 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aa + a + a + a + a + a + a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 129 &:= \frac{aa + aa + aaa - a - a - a - a}{a} \\ 1129 &:= \frac{aa + aa + aaaa - a - a - a - a}{a} \\ 11129 &:= \frac{aa + aa + aaaaa - a - a - a - a}{a} \\ 111129 &:= \frac{aa + aa + aaaaaa - a - a - a - a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 130 &:= \frac{aa + aa + aaa - a - a - a}{a} \\ 1130 &:= \frac{aa + aa + aaaa - a - a - a}{a} \\ 11130 &:= \frac{aa + aa + aaaaa - a - a - a}{a} \\ 111130 &:= \frac{aa + aa + aaaaaa - a - a - a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 131 &:= \frac{aa + aa + aaa - a - a}{a} \\ 1131 &:= \frac{aa + aa + aaaa - a - a}{a} \\ 11131 &:= \frac{aa + aa + aaaaa - a - a}{a} \\ 111131 &:= \frac{aa + aa + aaaaaa - a - a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 132 &:= \frac{aa + aa + aaa - a}{a} \\ 1132 &:= \frac{aa + aa + aaaa - a}{a} \\ 11132 &:= \frac{aa + aa + aaaaa - a}{a} \\ 111132 &:= \frac{aa + aa + aaaaaa - a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 133 &:= \frac{aaa + aa + aa}{a} \\ 1133 &:= \frac{aaaa + aa + aa}{a} \\ 11133 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aa + aa}{a} \\ 111133 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aa + aa}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 134 &:= \frac{aaa + aa + aa + a}{a} \\ 1134 &:= \frac{aaaa + aa + aa + a}{a} \\ 11134 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aa + aa + a}{a} \\ 111134 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aa + aa + a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 135 &:= \frac{aaa + aa + aa + a + a}{a} \\ 1135 &:= \frac{aaaa + aa + aa + a + a}{a} \\ 11135 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aa + aa + a + a}{a} \\ 111135 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aa + aa + a + a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 136 &:= \frac{aaa + aa + aa + a + a + a}{a} \\ 1136 &:= \frac{aaaa + aa + aa + a + a + a}{a} \\ 11136 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aa + aa + a + a + a}{a} \\ 111136 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aa + aa + a + a + a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 137 &:= \frac{aaa + aa + aa + a + a + a + a}{a} \\ 1137 &:= \frac{aaaa + aa + aa + a + a + a + a}{a} \\ 11137 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aa + aa + a + a + a + a}{a} \\ 111137 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aa + aa + a + a + a + a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 138 &:= \frac{aaa + aa + aa + a + a + a + a + a}{a} \\ 1138 &:= \frac{aaaa + aa + aa + a + a + a + a + a}{a} \\ 11138 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aa + aa + a + a + a + a + a}{a} \\ 111138 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aa + aa + a + a + a + a + a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 139 &:= \frac{aaaa + a}{aa - a - a - a} \\ 1389 &:= \frac{aaaaa + a}{aa - a - a - a} \\ 13889 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + a}{aa - a - a - a} \\ 138889 &:= \frac{aaaaaaa + a}{aa - a - a - a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 140 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a + a) \times (aa - a)}{a \times a} \\ 1140 &:= \frac{(aaa + a + a + a) \times (aa - a)}{a \times a} \\ 11140 &:= \frac{(aaaa + a + a + a) \times (aa - a)}{a \times a} \\ 111140 &:= \frac{(aaaaa + a + a + a) \times (aa - a)}{a \times a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 141 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a) \times aa - (a + a) \times a}{a \times a} \\ 1441 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a) \times aaa - (a + a) \times a}{a \times a} \\ 14441 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a) \times aaaa - (a + a) \times a}{a \times a} \\ 144441 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a) \times aaaaa - (a + a) \times a}{a \times a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 142 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a) \times aa - a \times a}{a \times a} \\ 1242 &:= \frac{(aaa + a + a) \times aa - a \times a}{a \times a} \\ 12242 &:= \frac{(aaaa + a + a) \times aa - a \times a}{a \times a} \\ 122242 &:= \frac{(aaaaa + a + a) \times aa - a \times a}{a \times a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 143 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a) \times aa}{a \times a} \\ 1243 &:= \frac{(aaa + a + a) \times aa}{a \times a} \\ 12243 &:= \frac{(aaaa + a + a) \times aa}{a \times a} \\ 122243 &:= \frac{(aaaaa + a + a) \times aa}{a \times a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 144 &:= \frac{aaa + aa + aa + aa}{a} \\ 1144 &:= \frac{aaaa + aa + aa + aa}{a} \\ 11144 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aa + aa + aa}{a} \\ 111144 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aa + aa + aa}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 145 &:= \frac{(aa + a) \times (aa + a) + a \times a}{a \times a} \\ 1335 &:= \frac{(aaa + a) \times (aa + a) + a \times a}{a \times a} \\ 13345 &:= \frac{(aaaa + a) \times (aa + a) + a \times a}{a \times a} \\ 133345 &:= \frac{(aaaaa + a) \times (aa + a) + a \times a}{a \times a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 146 &:= \frac{aaa + aa + aa + aa + a + a}{a} \\ 1146 &:= \frac{aaaa + aa + aa + aa + a + a}{a} \\ 11146 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aa + aa + aa + a + a}{a} \\ 111146 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aa + aa + aa + a + a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 147 &:= \frac{aaa + aa + aa + aa + a + a + a}{a} \\ 1147 &:= \frac{aaaa + aa + aa + aa + a + a + a}{a} \\ 11147 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aa + aa + aa + a + a + a}{a} \\ 111147 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aa + aa + aa + a + a + a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 148 &:= \frac{aaa \times a + aaa \times (a + a + a)}{a \times (a + a + a)} \\ 1148 &:= \frac{aaa \times a + aaaa \times (a + a + a)}{a \times (a + a + a)} \\ 11148 &:= \frac{aaa \times a + aaaaa \times (a + a + a)}{a \times (a + a + a)} \\ 111148 &:= \frac{aaa \times a + aaaaaa \times (a + a + a)}{a \times (a + a + a)} \end{aligned}$$

$$149 := \frac{aaa \times a + (aaa + a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times (a + a + a)}$$

$$1149 := \frac{aaa \times a + (aaaa + a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times (a + a + a)}$$

$$11149 := \frac{aaa \times a + (aaaaa + a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times (a + a + a)}$$

$$111149 := \frac{aaa \times a + (aaaaaa + a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times (a + a + a)}$$

$$150 := \frac{(aa + a + a + a + a) \times (aa - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$1650 := \frac{(aa + a + a + a + a) \times (aaa - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$16650 := \frac{(aa + a + a + a + a) \times (aaaa - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$166650 := \frac{(aa + a + a + a + a) \times (aaaaa - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$151 := \frac{(aa + a + a + a) \times aa - a \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$1551 := \frac{(aa + a + a + a) \times aaa - a \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$15551 := \frac{(aa + a + a + a) \times aaaa - a \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$155551 := \frac{(aa + a + a + a) \times aaaaa - a \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$152 := \frac{(aa + a + a + a) \times aa - a \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$1552 := \frac{(aa + a + a + a) \times aaa - a \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$15552 := \frac{(aa + a + a + a) \times aaaa - a \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$155552 := \frac{(aa + a + a + a) \times aaaaa - a \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$153 := \frac{(aa + a + a + a) \times aa - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$1553 := \frac{(aa + a + a + a) \times aaa - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$15553 := \frac{(aa + a + a + a) \times aaaa - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$155553 := \frac{(aa + a + a + a) \times aaaaa - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$154 := \frac{(aa + a + a + a) \times aa}{a \times a}$$

$$1554 := \frac{(aa + a + a + a) \times aaa}{a \times a}$$

$$15554 := \frac{(aa + a + a + a) \times aaaa}{a \times a}$$

$$155554 := \frac{(aa + a + a + a) \times aaaaa}{a \times a}$$

$$155 := \frac{aaa + aa + aa + aa + aa}{a}$$

$$1155 := \frac{aaaa + aa + aa + aa + aa}{a}$$

$$11155 := \frac{aaaaa + aa + aa + aa + aa}{a}$$

$$111155 := \frac{aaaaaa + aa + aa + aa + aa}{a}$$

$$156 := \frac{aaa + aa + aa + aa + aa + a}{a}$$

$$1156 := \frac{aaaa + aa + aa + aa + aa + a}{a}$$

$$11156 := \frac{aaaaa + aa + aa + aa + aa + a}{a}$$

$$111156 := \frac{aaaaaa + aa + aa + aa + aa + a}{a}$$

$$157 := \frac{aaa + aa + aa + aa + aa + a + a}{a}$$

$$1157 := \frac{aaaa + aa + aa + aa + aa + a + a}{a}$$

$$11157 := \frac{aaaaa + aa + aa + aa + aa + a + a}{a}$$

$$111157 := \frac{aaaaaa + aa + aa + aa + aa + a + a}{a}$$

$$158 := \frac{(aa + a + a) \times (aa + a) + (a + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$1358 := \frac{(aaa + a + a) \times (aa + a) + (a + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$13358 := \frac{(aaaa + a + a) \times (aa + a) + (a + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$133358 := \frac{(aaaaa + a + a) \times (aa + a) + (a + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$159 := \frac{(aa + a + a) \times (aa + a) + (a + a + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$1359 := \frac{(aaa + a + a) \times (aa + a) + (a + a + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$13359 := \frac{(aaaa + a + a) \times (aa + a) + (a + a + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$133359 := \frac{(aaaaa + a + a) \times (aa + a) + (a + a + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$160 := \frac{(aa + a + a + a + a + a) \times (aa - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$1160 := \frac{(aaa + a + a + a + a + a) \times (aa - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$11160 := \frac{(aaaa + a + a + a + a + a) \times (aa - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$111160 := \frac{(aaaaa + a + a + a + a + a) \times (aa - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$161 := \frac{aaa \times (a + a + a) - aa \times a}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$1661 := \frac{aaaa \times (a + a + a) - aa \times a}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$16661 := \frac{aaaaa \times (a + a + a) - aa \times a}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$166661 := \frac{aaaaaa \times (a + a + a) - aa \times a}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$162 := \frac{(aaa - a - a - a) \times (a + a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$1662 := \frac{(aaaa - a - a - a) \times (a + a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$16662 := \frac{(aaaaa - a - a - a) \times (a + a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$166662 := \frac{(aaaaaa - a - a - a) \times (a + a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$163 := \frac{(aa + a + a + a + a) \times aa - (a + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$1263 := \frac{(aaa + a + a + a + a) \times aa - (a + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$12263 := \frac{(aaaa + a + a + a + a) \times aa - (a + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$122263 := \frac{(aaaaa + a + a + a + a) \times aa - (a + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$164 := \frac{(aa + a + a + a + a) \times aa - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$1264 := \frac{(aaa + a + a + a + a) \times aa - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$12264 := \frac{(aaaa + a + a + a + a) \times aa - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$122264 := \frac{(aaaaa + a + a + a + a) \times aa - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$165 := \frac{(aa + a + a + a + a) \times aa}{a \times a}$$

$$1665 := \frac{(aa + a + a + a + a) \times aaa}{a \times a}$$

$$16665 := \frac{(aa + a + a + a + a) \times aaaa}{a \times a}$$

$$166665 := \frac{(aa + a + a + a + a) \times aaaaa}{a \times a}$$

$$166 := \frac{aaa + aaa + aaa - a}{a + a}$$

$$1166 := \frac{aaaa + aaaa + aaa - a}{a + a}$$

$$11166 := \frac{aaaaa + aaaaa + aaa - a}{a + a}$$

$$111166 := \frac{aaaaaa + aaaaaa + aaa - a}{a + a}$$

$$167 := \frac{aaa + aaa + aaa + a}{a + a}$$

$$1167 := \frac{aaaa + aaaa + aaa + a}{a + a}$$

$$11167 := \frac{aaaaa + aaaaa + aaa + a}{a + a}$$

$$111167 := \frac{aaaaaa + aaaaaa + aaa + a}{a + a}$$

$$168 := \frac{aaa + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaa + a}{a}$$

$$1668 := \frac{aaaa + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa + a}{a}$$

$$16668 := \frac{aaaaa + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaaaa + a}{a}$$

$$166668 := \frac{aaaaaa + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaaaaa + a}{a}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 169 &:= \frac{aaa + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaa + a + a}{a} \\ 1669 &:= \frac{aaaa + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa + a + a}{a} \\ 16669 &:= \frac{aaaaa + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaaaa + a + a}{a} \\ 166669 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaaaaa + a + a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 170 &:= \frac{aaa + aa}{a + a} + \frac{aaa - a - a}{a} \\ 1670 &:= \frac{aaaa + aa}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa - a - a}{a} \\ 16670 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aa}{a + a} + \frac{aaaaa - a - a}{a} \\ 166670 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aa}{a + a} + \frac{aaaaaa - a - a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 171 &:= \frac{aaa + aa}{a + a} + \frac{aaa - a}{a} \\ 1671 &:= \frac{aaaa + aa}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa - a}{a} \\ 16671 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aa}{a + a} + \frac{aaaaa - a}{a} \\ 166671 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aa}{a + a} + \frac{aaaaaa - a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 172 &:= \frac{aaa + aa}{a + a} + \frac{aaa}{a} \\ 1672 &:= \frac{aaaa + aa}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa}{a} \\ 16672 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aa}{a + a} + \frac{aaaaa}{a} \\ 166672 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aa}{a + a} + \frac{aaaaaa}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 173 &:= \frac{aaa + aa}{a + a} + \frac{aaa + a}{a} \\ 1673 &:= \frac{aaaa + aa}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa + a}{a} \\ 16673 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aa}{a + a} + \frac{aaaaa + a}{a} \\ 166673 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aa}{a + a} + \frac{aaaaaa + a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 174 &:= \frac{aaa + aa}{a + a} + \frac{aaa + a + a}{a} \\ 1674 &:= \frac{aaaa + aa}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa + a + a}{a} \\ 16674 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aa}{a + a} + \frac{aaaaa + a + a}{a} \\ 166674 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aa}{a + a} + \frac{aaaaaa + a + a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 175 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a + a + a + a) \times aa - a \times a}{a \times a} \\ 1775 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a + a + a + a) \times aaa - a \times a}{a \times a} \\ 17775 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a + a + a + a) \times aaaa - a \times a}{a \times a} \\ 177775 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a + a + a + a) \times aaaaa - a \times a}{a \times a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 176 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a + a + a + a) \times aa}{a \times a} \\ 1776 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a + a + a + a) \times aaa}{a \times a} \\ 17776 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a + a + a + a) \times aaaa}{a \times a} \\ 177776 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a + a + a + a) \times aaaaa}{a \times a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 177 &:= \frac{(aa + a) \times aa + (a + a) \times aaa}{(a + a) \times a} \\ 1777 &:= \frac{(aa + a) \times aa + (a + a) \times aaaa}{(a + a) \times a} \\ 17777 &:= \frac{(aa + a) \times aa + (a + a) \times aaaaa}{(a + a) \times a} \\ 177777 &:= \frac{(aa + a) \times aa + (a + a) \times aaaaaa}{(a + a) \times a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 178 &:= \frac{(aaa - aa - aa) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\ 2178 &:= \frac{(aaaa - aa - aa) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\ 22178 &:= \frac{(aaaaa - aa - aa) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\ 222178 &:= \frac{(aaaaaa - aa - aa) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \end{aligned}$$

$$179 := \frac{(aaa - aa - aa) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$2179 := \frac{(aaaa - aa - aa) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$22179 := \frac{(aaaaa - aa - aa) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$222179 := \frac{(aaaaaa - aa - aa) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$180 := \frac{(aa + a + a + a + a) \times (aa + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$1680 := \frac{(aa + a + a + a + a) \times (aaa + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$16680 := \frac{(aa + a + a + a + a) \times (aaaa + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$166680 := \frac{(aa + a + a + a + a) \times (aaaaa + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$181 := \frac{(aa + a + a + a + a) \times (aa + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$1381 := \frac{(aaa + a + a + a + a) \times (aa + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$13381 := \frac{(aaaa + a + a + a + a) \times (aa + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$133381 := \frac{(aaaaa + a + a + a + a) \times (aa + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$182 := \frac{(aa + a + a + a) \times (aa + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$1482 := \frac{(aaa + a + a + a) \times (aa + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$14482 := \frac{(aaaa + a + a + a) \times (aa + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$144482 := \frac{(aaaaa + a + a + a) \times (aa + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$183 := \frac{(aa + a + a + a) \times (aa + a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$1483 := \frac{(aaa + a + a + a) \times (aa + a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$14483 := \frac{(aaaa + a + a + a) \times (aa + a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$144483 := \frac{(aaaaa + a + a + a) \times (aa + a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$184 := \frac{(aaa + aa) \times (a + a + a) + a \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$1684 := \frac{(aaaa + aa) \times (a + a + a) + a \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$16684 := \frac{(aaaaa + aa) \times (a + a + a) + a \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$166684 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aa) \times (a + a + a) + a \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$185 := \frac{(aaaa - a) \times (a + a)}{(aa + a) \times a}$$

$$185185 := \frac{(aaaaaaa - a) \times (a + a)}{(aa + a) \times a}$$

$$185185185 := \frac{(aaaaaaaaaaa - a) \times (a + a)}{(aa + a) \times a}$$

$$185185185185 := \frac{(aaaaaaaaaaaaaaa - a) \times (a + a)}{(aa + a) \times a}$$

$$186 := \frac{(aa + aa - a) \times (aa - a - a) - a \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$1086 := \frac{(aaa + aa - a) \times (aa - a - a) - a \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$10086 := \frac{(aaaa + aa - a) \times (aa - a - a) - a \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$100086 := \frac{(aaaaa + aa - a) \times (aa - a - a) - a \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$187 := \frac{(aa + aa - a) \times (aa - a - a) - (a + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$1087 := \frac{(aaa + aa - a) \times (aa - a - a) - (a + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$10087 := \frac{(aaaa + aa - a) \times (aa - a - a) - (a + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$100087 := \frac{(aaaaa + aa - a) \times (aa - a - a) - (a + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$188 := \frac{(aa + aa - a) \times (aa - a - a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$1088 := \frac{(aaa + aa - a) \times (aa - a - a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$10088 := \frac{(aaaa + aa - a) \times (aa - a - a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$100088 := \frac{(aaaaa + aa - a) \times (aa - a - a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 189 &:= \frac{(aa + aa - a) \times (aa - a - a)}{a \times a} & 194 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a + a + a) \times (aa + a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 1089 &:= \frac{(aaa + aa - a) \times (aa - a - a)}{a \times a} & 1694 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a + a + a) \times (aaa + a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 10089 &:= \frac{(aaaa + aa - a) \times (aa - a - a)}{a \times a} & 16694 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a + a + a) \times (aaaa + a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 100089 &:= \frac{(aaaaa + aa - a) \times (aa - a - a)}{a \times a} & 166694 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a + a + a) \times (aaaaa + a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 \\
 190 &:= \frac{(aa + aa - a) \times (aa - a - a) + a \times a}{a \times a} & 195 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a + a + a) \times (aa + a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 1090 &:= \frac{(aaa + aa - a) \times (aa - a - a) + a \times a}{a \times a} & 1695 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a + a + a) \times (aaa + a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 10090 &:= \frac{(aaaa + aa - a) \times (aa - a - a) + a \times a}{a \times a} & 16695 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a + a + a) \times (aaaa + a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 100090 &:= \frac{(aaaaa + aa - a) \times (aa - a - a) + a \times a}{a \times a} & 166695 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a + a + a) \times (aaaaa + a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 \\
 191 &:= \frac{(aa + aa - a) \times (aa - a - a) + a \times (a + a)}{a \times a} & 196 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa - aa - aa - a - a - a - a}{a} \\
 1091 &:= \frac{(aaa + aa - a) \times (aa - a - a) + a \times (a + a)}{a \times a} & 1196 &:= \frac{aaaa + aaa - aa - aa - a - a - a - a}{a} \\
 10091 &:= \frac{(aaaa + aa - a) \times (aa - a - a) + a \times (a + a)}{a \times a} & 11196 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aaa - aa - aa - a - a - a - a}{a} \\
 100091 &:= \frac{(aaaaa + aa - a) \times (aa - a - a) + a \times (a + a)}{a \times a} & 111196 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aaa - aa - aa - a - a - a - a}{a} \\
 \\
 192 &:= \frac{(aa + aa - a) \times (aa - a - a) + a \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a} & 197 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa - aa - aa - a - a - a}{a} \\
 1092 &:= \frac{(aaa + aa - a) \times (aa - a - a) + a \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a} & 1197 &:= \frac{aaaa + aaa - aa - aa - a - a - a}{a} \\
 10092 &:= \frac{(aaaa + aa - a) \times (aa - a - a) + a \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a} & 11197 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aaa - aa - aa - a - a - a}{a} \\
 100092 &:= \frac{(aaaaa + aa - a) \times (aa - a - a) + a \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a} & 111197 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aaa - aa - aa - a - a - a}{a} \\
 \\
 193 &:= \frac{(aaa - aa - a - a - a) \times (a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a} & 198 &:= \frac{(aa - a - a) \times (aa + aa)}{a \times a} \\
 2193 &:= \frac{(aaaa - aa - a - a - a) \times (a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a} & 1998 &:= \frac{(aa - a - a) \times (aaa + aaa)}{a \times a} \\
 22193 &:= \frac{(aaaaa - aa - a - a - a) \times (a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a} & 19998 &:= \frac{(aa - a - a) \times (aaaa + aaaa)}{a \times a} \\
 222193 &:= \frac{(aaaaaa - aa - a - a - a) \times (a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a} & 199998 &:= \frac{(aa - a - a) \times (aaaaa + aaaaa)}{a \times a}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$199 := \frac{aaa + aaa - aa - aa - a}{a}$$

$$1199 := \frac{aaaa + aaa - aa - aa - a}{a}$$

$$11199 := \frac{aaaaa + aaa - aa - aa - a}{a}$$

$$111199 := \frac{aaaaaa + aaa - aa - aa - a}{a}$$

$$200 := \frac{aaa + aaa - aa - aa}{a}$$

$$1200 := \frac{aaaa + aaa - aa - aa}{a}$$

$$11200 := \frac{aaaaa + aaa - aa - aa}{a}$$

$$111200 := \frac{aaaaaa + aaa - aa - aa}{a}$$

$$201 := \frac{aaaa \times (a + a) - aa \times a}{aa \times a}$$

$$20201 := \frac{aaaaaa \times (a + a) - aa \times a}{aa \times a}$$

$$2020201 := \frac{aaaaaaaa \times (a + a) - aa \times a}{aa \times a}$$

$$202020201 := \frac{aaaaaaaaaa \times (a + a) - aa \times a}{aa \times a}$$

$$202 := \frac{(aaa - aa + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$2202 := \frac{(aaaa - aa + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$22202 := \frac{(aaaaa - aa + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$222202 := \frac{(aaaaaa - aa + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$203 := \frac{aaaa \times (a + a) + a \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$2020203 := \frac{aaaaaaaa \times (a + a) + a \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$202020203 := \frac{aaaaaaaaaaaa \times (a + a) + a \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$2020202020203 := \frac{aaaaaaaaaaaaaaaa \times (a + a) + a \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$204 := \frac{aaaa \times (a + a) + (a + a) \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$20404 := \frac{aaaa \times (a + a) + (a + a) \times aaaaaa}{a \times aa}$$

$$202020404 := \frac{aaaa \times (a + a) + (a + a) \times aaaaaaaaaa}{a \times aa}$$

$$20202020404 := \frac{aaaa \times (a + a) + (a + a) \times aaaaaaaaaaaa}{a \times aa}$$

$$205 := \frac{aaa + aaa - aa - a - a - a - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$1205 := \frac{aaaa + aaa - aa - a - a - a - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$11205 := \frac{aaaaa + aaa - aa - a - a - a - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$111205 := \frac{aaaaaa + aaa - aa - a - a - a - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$206 := \frac{aaa + aaa - aa - a - a - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$1206 := \frac{aaaa + aaa - aa - a - a - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$11206 := \frac{aaaaa + aaa - aa - a - a - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$111206 := \frac{aaaaaa + aaa - aa - a - a - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$207 := \frac{aaa + aaa - aa - a - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$1207 := \frac{aaaa + aaa - aa - a - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$11207 := \frac{aaaaa + aaa - aa - a - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$111207 := \frac{aaaaaa + aaa - aa - a - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$208 := \frac{aaa + aaa - aa - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$1208 := \frac{aaaa + aaa - aa - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$11208 := \frac{aaaaa + aaa - aa - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$111208 := \frac{aaaaaa + aaa - aa - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 209 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa - aa - a - a}{a} \\ 1209 &:= \frac{aaaa + aaa - aa - a - a}{a} \\ 11209 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aaa - aa - a - a}{a} \\ 111209 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aaa - aa - a - a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 210 &:= \frac{(aa + aa - a) \times (aa - a)}{a \times a} \\ 1210 &:= \frac{(aaa + aa - a) \times (aa - a)}{a \times a} \\ 11210 &:= \frac{(aaaa + aa - a) \times (aa - a)}{a \times a} \\ 111210 &:= \frac{(aaaaa + aa - a) \times (aa - a)}{a \times a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 211 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa - aa}{a} \\ 1211 &:= \frac{aaaa + aaa - aa}{a} \\ 11211 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aaa - aa}{a} \\ 111211 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aaa - aa}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 212 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa - aa + a}{a} \\ 1212 &:= \frac{aaaa + aaa - aa + a}{a} \\ 11212 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aaa - aa + a}{a} \\ 111212 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aaa - aa + a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 213 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa - aa + a + a}{a} \\ 1213 &:= \frac{aaaa + aaa - aa + a + a}{a} \\ 11213 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aaa - aa + a + a}{a} \\ 111213 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aaa - aa + a + a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 214 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa - aa + a + a + a}{a} \\ 1214 &:= \frac{aaaa + aaa - aa + a + a + a}{a} \\ 11214 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aaa - aa + a + a + a}{a} \\ 111214 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aaa - aa + a + a + a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 215 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa - aa + a + a + a + a}{a} \\ 1215 &:= \frac{aaaa + aaa - aa + a + a + a + a}{a} \\ 11215 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aaa - aa + a + a + a + a}{a} \\ 111215 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aaa - aa + a + a + a + a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 216 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa - aa + a + a + a + a + a}{a} \\ 1216 &:= \frac{aaaa + aaa - aa + a + a + a + a + a}{a} \\ 11216 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aaa - aa + a + a + a + a + a}{a} \\ 111216 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aaa - aa + a + a + a + a + a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 217 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa - aa + a + a + a + a + a + a}{a} \\ 1217 &:= \frac{aaaa + aaa - aa + a + a + a + a + a + a}{a} \\ 11217 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aaa - aa + a + a + a + a + a + a}{a} \\ 111217 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aaa - aa + a + a + a + a + a + a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 218 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa - a - a - a - a}{a} \\ 1218 &:= \frac{aaaa + aaa - a - a - a - a}{a} \\ 11218 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aaa - a - a - a - a}{a} \\ 111218 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aaa - a - a - a - a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 219 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa - a - a - a}{a} \\ 1219 &:= \frac{aaaa + aaa - a - a - a}{a} \\ 11219 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aaa - a - a - a}{a} \\ 111219 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aaa - a - a - a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 220 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa - a - a}{a} \\ 1220 &:= \frac{aaaa + aaa - a - a}{a} \\ 11220 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aaa - a - a}{a} \\ 111220 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aaa - a - a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 221 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa - a}{a} \\ 1221 &:= \frac{aaaa + aaa - a}{a} \\ 11221 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aaa - a}{a} \\ 111221 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aaa - a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 222 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa}{a} \\ 1222 &:= \frac{aaaa + aaa}{a} \\ 11222 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aaa}{a} \\ 111222 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aaa}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 223 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa + a}{a} \\ 1223 &:= \frac{aaaa + aaa + a}{a} \\ 11223 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aaa + a}{a} \\ 111223 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aaa + a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 224 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa + a + a}{a} \\ 1224 &:= \frac{aaaa + aaa + a + a}{a} \\ 11224 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aaa + a + a}{a} \\ 111224 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aaa + a + a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 225 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa + a + a + a}{a} \\ 1225 &:= \frac{aaaa + aaa + a + a + a}{a} \\ 11225 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aaa + a + a + a}{a} \\ 111225 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aaa + a + a + a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 226 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa + a + a + a + a}{a} \\ 1226 &:= \frac{aaaa + aaa + a + a + a + a}{a} \\ 11226 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aaa + a + a + a + a}{a} \\ 111226 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aaa + a + a + a + a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 227 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa + a + a + a + a + a}{a} \\ 1227 &:= \frac{aaaa + aaa + a + a + a + a + a}{a} \\ 11227 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aaa + a + a + a + a + a}{a} \\ 111227 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aaa + a + a + a + a + a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 228 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa + aa - a - a - a - a - a}{a} \\ 1228 &:= \frac{aaaa + aaa + aa - a - a - a - a - a}{a} \\ 11228 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aaa + aa - a - a - a - a - a}{a} \\ 111228 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aaa + aa - a - a - a - a - a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 229 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa + aa - a - a - a - a}{a} \\ 1229 &:= \frac{aaaa + aaa + aa - a - a - a - a}{a} \\ 11229 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aaa + aa - a - a - a - a}{a} \\ 111229 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aaa + aa - a - a - a - a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 230 &:= \frac{aa + aaa + aaa - a - a - a}{a} \\ 1230 &:= \frac{aa + aaa + aaaa - a - a - a}{a} \\ 11230 &:= \frac{aa + aaa + aaaaa - a - a - a}{a} \\ 111230 &:= \frac{aa + aaa + aaaaaa - a - a - a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 231 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa + aa - a - a}{a} \\ 1231 &:= \frac{aaaa + aaa + aa - a - a}{a} \\ 11231 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aaa + aa - a - a}{a} \\ 111231 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aaa + aa - a - a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 232 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa + aa - a}{a} \\ 1232 &:= \frac{aaaa + aaa + aa - a}{a} \\ 11232 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aaa + aa - a}{a} \\ 111232 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aaa + aa - a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 233 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa + aa}{a} \\ 1233 &:= \frac{aaaa + aaa + aa}{a} \\ 11233 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aaa + aa}{a} \\ 111233 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aaa + aa}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 234 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa + aa + a}{a} \\ 1234 &:= \frac{aaaa + aaa + aa + a}{a} \\ 11234 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aaa + aa + a}{a} \\ 111234 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aaa + aa + a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 235 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa + aa + a + a}{a} \\ 1235 &:= \frac{aaaa + aaa + aa + a + a}{a} \\ 11235 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aaa + aa + a + a}{a} \\ 111235 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aaa + aa + a + a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 236 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa + aa + a + a + a}{a} \\ 1236 &:= \frac{aaaa + aaa + aa + a + a + a}{a} \\ 11236 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aaa + aa + a + a + a}{a} \\ 111236 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aaa + aa + a + a + a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 237 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa + aa + a + a + a + a}{a} \\ 1237 &:= \frac{aaaa + aaa + aa + a + a + a + a}{a} \\ 11237 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aaa + aa + a + a + a + a}{a} \\ 111237 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aaa + aa + a + a + a + a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 238 &:= \frac{(aa + aa) \times aa - a \times (a + a + a + a)}{a \times a} \\ 2438 &:= \frac{(aa + aa) \times aaa - a \times (a + a + a + a)}{a \times a} \\ 24438 &:= \frac{(aa + aa) \times aaaa - a \times (a + a + a + a)}{a \times a} \\ 244438 &:= \frac{(aa + aa) \times aaaaa - a \times (a + a + a + a)}{a \times a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 239 &:= \frac{(aa + aa) \times aa - a \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a} \\ 2439 &:= \frac{(aa + aa) \times aaa - a \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a} \\ 24439 &:= \frac{(aa + aa) \times aaaa - a \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a} \\ 244439 &:= \frac{(aa + aa) \times aaaaa - a \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 240 &:= \frac{(aa + aa) \times aa - a \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\ 2440 &:= \frac{(aa + aa) \times aaa - a \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\ 24440 &:= \frac{(aa + aa) \times aaaa - a \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\ 244440 &:= \frac{(aa + aa) \times aaaaa - a \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 241 &:= \frac{(aa + aa) \times aa - a \times a}{a \times a} \\ 2441 &:= \frac{(aa + aa) \times aaa - a \times a}{a \times a} \\ 24441 &:= \frac{(aa + aa) \times aaaa - a \times a}{a \times a} \\ 244441 &:= \frac{(aa + aa) \times aaaaa - a \times a}{a \times a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 242 &:= \frac{(aa + aa) \times aa}{a \times a} \\ 2442 &:= \frac{(aa + aa) \times aaa}{a \times a} \\ 24442 &:= \frac{(aa + aa) \times aaaa}{a \times a} \\ 244442 &:= \frac{(aa + aa) \times aaaaa}{a \times a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 243 &:= \frac{(aa + aa) \times aa + a \times a}{a \times a} \\ 2443 &:= \frac{(aa + aa) \times aaa + a \times a}{a \times a} \\ 24443 &:= \frac{(aa + aa) \times aaaa + a \times a}{a \times a} \\ 244443 &:= \frac{(aa + aa) \times aaaaa + a \times a}{a \times a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 244 &:= \frac{(aaa + aa) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\ 2244 &:= \frac{(aaaa + aa) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\ 22244 &:= \frac{(aaaaa + aa) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\ 222244 &:= \frac{(aaaaaa + aa) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 245 &:= \frac{(aaa + aa) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a} \\ 2245 &:= \frac{(aaaa + aa) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a} \\ 22245 &:= \frac{(aaaaa + aa) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a} \\ 222245 &:= \frac{(aaaaaa + aa) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 246 &:= \frac{(aaa + a) \times (a + a) + (a + a) \times aa}{a \times a} \\ 2246 &:= \frac{(aaaa + a) \times (a + a) + (a + a) \times aa}{a \times a} \\ 22246 &:= \frac{(aaaaa + a) \times (a + a) + (a + a) \times aa}{a \times a} \\ 222246 &:= \frac{(aaaaaa + a) \times (a + a) + (a + a) \times aa}{a \times a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 247 &:= \frac{(aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a} \\ 2247 &:= \frac{(aaaa + aa + a) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a} \\ 22247 &:= \frac{(aaaaa + aa + a) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a} \\ 222247 &:= \frac{(aaaaaa + aa + a) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 248 &:= \frac{(aaa + aa + a + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\ 2248 &:= \frac{(aaaa + aa + a + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\ 22248 &:= \frac{(aaaaa + aa + a + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\ 222248 &:= \frac{(aaaaaa + aa + a + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \end{aligned}$$

$$249 := \frac{(aaa + aa + a + a) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$2249 := \frac{(aaaa + aa + a + a) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$22249 := \frac{(aaaaa + aa + a + a) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$222249 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aa + a + a) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$250 := \frac{aaaa - aaa}{a + a + a + a}$$

$$2500 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa}{a + a + a + a}$$

$$25000 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa}{a + a + a + a}$$

$$250000 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaaaa}{a + a + a + a}$$

$$251 := \frac{(aa + aa + a) \times aa - a \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$2551 := \frac{(aa + aa + a) \times aaa - a \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$25551 := \frac{(aa + aa + a) \times aaaa - a \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$255551 := \frac{(aa + aa + a) \times aaaaa - a \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$252 := \frac{(aa + aa + a) \times aa - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$2552 := \frac{(aa + aa + a) \times aaa - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$25552 := \frac{(aa + aa + a) \times aaaa - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$255552 := \frac{(aa + aa + a) \times aaaaa - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$253 := \frac{(aa + aa + a) \times aa}{a \times a}$$

$$2553 := \frac{(aa + aa + a) \times aaa}{a \times a}$$

$$25553 := \frac{(aa + aa + a) \times aaaa}{a \times a}$$

$$255553 := \frac{(aa + aa + a) \times aaaaa}{a \times a}$$

$$254 := \frac{(aa + aa + a) \times aa + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$2554 := \frac{(aa + aa + a) \times aaa + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$25554 := \frac{(aa + aa + a) \times aaaa + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$255554 := \frac{(aa + aa + a) \times aaaaa + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$255 := \frac{(aa + aa + a) \times aa + a \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$2555 := \frac{(aa + aa + a) \times aaa + a \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$25555 := \frac{(aa + aa + a) \times aaaa + a \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$255555 := \frac{(aa + aa + a) \times aaaaa + a \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$256 := \frac{(aa + aa + a) \times aa + a \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$2556 := \frac{(aa + aa + a) \times aaa + a \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$25556 := \frac{(aa + aa + a) \times aaaa + a \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$255556 := \frac{(aa + aa + a) \times aaaaa + a \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$257 := \frac{(aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a) + aa \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$2257 := \frac{(aaaa + aa + a) \times (a + a) + aa \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$22257 := \frac{(aaaaa + aa + a) \times (a + a) + aa \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$222257 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aa + a) \times (a + a) + aa \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$258 := \frac{aaaa - a}{a + a + a} - \frac{aaa + a}{a}$$

$$370258 := \frac{aaaaaaa - a}{a + a + a} - \frac{aaa + a}{a}$$

$$370370258 := \frac{aaaaaaaaaaa - a}{a + a + a} - \frac{aaa + a}{a}$$

$$370370370258 := \frac{aaaaaaaaaaaaaaa - a}{a + a + a} - \frac{aaa + a}{a}$$

$$259 := \frac{aaaa - a}{a + a + a} - \frac{aaa}{a}$$

$$370259 := \frac{aaaaaaaa - a}{a + a + a} - \frac{aaa}{a}$$

$$370370259 := \frac{aaaaaaaaaaaa - a}{a + a + a} - \frac{aaa}{a}$$

$$370370370259 := \frac{aaaaaaaaaaaaaaaa - a}{a + a + a} - \frac{aaa}{a}$$

$$260 := \frac{(aa + a + a) \times (aa - a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a \times a}$$

$$2260 := \frac{(aaa + a + a) \times (aa - a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a \times a}$$

$$22260 := \frac{(aaaa + a + a) \times (aa - a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a \times a}$$

$$222260 := \frac{(aaaaa + a + a) \times (aa - a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a \times a}$$

$$261 := \frac{(aa + aa) \times (aa + a) - (a + a + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$2661 := \frac{(aaa + aaa) \times (aa + a) - (a + a + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$26661 := \frac{(aaaa + aaaa) \times (aa + a) - (a + a + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$266661 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaaaa) \times (aa + a) - (a + a + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$262 := \frac{(aa + aa) \times (aa + a) - (a + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$2662 := \frac{(aaa + aaa) \times (aa + a) - (a + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$26662 := \frac{(aaaa + aaaa) \times (aa + a) - (a + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$266662 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaaaa) \times (aa + a) - (a + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$263 := \frac{(aa + aa) \times (aa + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$2663 := \frac{(aaa + aaa) \times (aa + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$26663 := \frac{(aaaa + aaaa) \times (aa + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$266663 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaaaa) \times (aa + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$264 := \frac{(aa + aa + a + a) \times aa}{a \times a}$$

$$2664 := \frac{(aa + aa + a + a) \times aaa}{a \times a}$$

$$26664 := \frac{(aa + aa + a + a) \times aaaa}{a \times a}$$

$$266664 := \frac{(aa + aa + a + a) \times aaaaa}{a \times a}$$

$$265 := \frac{(aa + aa) \times (aa + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$2665 := \frac{(aaa + aaa) \times (aa + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$26665 := \frac{(aaaa + aaaa) \times (aa + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$266665 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaaaa) \times (aa + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$266 := \frac{(aaa + aa + a + aa - a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$2266 := \frac{(aaaa + aa + a + aa - a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$22266 := \frac{(aaaaa + aa + a + aa - a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$222266 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aa + a + aa - a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$267 := \frac{(aa + aa) \times (aa + a) + (a + a + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$2667 := \frac{(aaa + aaa) \times (aa + a) + (a + a + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$26667 := \frac{(aaaa + aaaa) \times (aa + a) + (a + a + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$266667 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaaaa) \times (aa + a) + (a + a + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$268 := \frac{(aaa + aa + a + aa) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$2268 := \frac{(aaaa + aa + a + aa) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$22268 := \frac{(aaaaa + aa + a + aa) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$222268 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aa + a + aa) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$269 := \frac{(aaa + aa + a + aa + a) \times (a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$2269 := \frac{(aaaa + aa + a + aa + a) \times (a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$22269 := \frac{(aaaaa + aa + a + aa + a) \times (a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$222269 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aa + a + aa + a) \times (a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$270 := \frac{(aaa + aa + a + aa + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$2270 := \frac{(aaaa + aa + a + aa + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$22270 := \frac{(aaaaa + aa + a + aa + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$222270 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aa + a + aa + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$271 := \frac{(aa + aa - a) \times (aa + a + a) - (a + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$2871 := \frac{(aaa + aaa - a) \times (aa + a + a) - (a + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$28871 := \frac{(aaaa + aaaa - a) \times (aa + a + a) - (a + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$288871 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaaaa - a) \times (aa + a + a) - (a + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$272 := \frac{aaaa - aa - aa - a}{a + a + a + a}$$

$$2772 := \frac{aaaaa - aa - aa - a}{a + a + a + a}$$

$$27772 := \frac{aaaaa - aa - aa - a}{a + a + a + a}$$

$$277772 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aa - aa - a}{a + a + a + a}$$

$$273 := \frac{(aa + aa - a) \times (aa + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$2873 := \frac{(aaa + aaa - a) \times (aa + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$28873 := \frac{(aaaa + aaaa - a) \times (aa + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$288873 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaaaa - a) \times (aa + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$274 := \frac{(aa + aa + a + a + a) \times aa - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$2774 := \frac{(aa + aa + a + a + a) \times aaa - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$27774 := \frac{(aa + aa + a + a + a) \times aaaa - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$277774 := \frac{(aa + aa + a + a + a) \times aaaaa - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$275 := \frac{aaaa - aa}{a + a + a + a}$$

$$2775 := \frac{aaaaa - aa}{a + a + a + a}$$

$$27775 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aa}{a + a + a + a}$$

$$277775 := \frac{aaaaaaaa - aa}{a + a + a + a}$$

$$276 := \frac{(aa + aa + a) \times (aa + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$2576 := \frac{(aa + aa + a) \times (aaa + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$25576 := \frac{(aa + aa + a) \times (aaaa + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$255576 := \frac{(aa + aa + a) \times (aaaaa + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$277 := \frac{aaaa - a - a - a}{a + a + a + a}$$

$$2777 := \frac{aaaaa - a - a - a}{a + a + a + a}$$

$$27777 := \frac{aaaaa - a - a - a}{a + a + a + a}$$

$$277777 := \frac{aaaaaaa - a - a - a}{a + a + a + a}$$

$$278 := \frac{aaaa + a}{a + a + a + a}$$

$$2778 := \frac{aaaaa + a}{a + a + a + a}$$

$$27778 := \frac{aaaaaa + a}{a + a + a + a}$$

$$277778 := \frac{aaaaaaa + a}{a + a + a + a}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 279 &:= \frac{aaaa + a}{a + a + a + a} + \frac{a}{a} \\ 2779 &:= \frac{aaaaa + a}{a + a + a + a} + \frac{a}{a} \\ 27779 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + a}{a + a + a + a} + \frac{a}{a} \\ 277779 &:= \frac{aaaaaaa + a}{a + a + a + a} + \frac{a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 280 &:= \frac{(aaa + a) \times (aa - a)}{(a + a) \times (a + a)} \\ 2780 &:= \frac{(aaaa + a) \times (aa - a)}{(a + a) \times (a + a)} \\ 27780 &:= \frac{(aaaaa + a) \times (aa - a)}{(a + a) \times (a + a)} \\ 277780 &:= \frac{(aaaaaa + a) \times (aa - a)}{(a + a) \times (a + a)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 281 &:= \frac{aaaa + aa + a + a}{a + a + a + a} \\ 2781 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aa + a + a}{a + a + a + a} \\ 27781 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aa + a + a}{a + a + a + a} \\ 277781 &:= \frac{aaaaaaa + aa + a + a}{a + a + a + a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 282 &:= \frac{aaaa + aa + a + a}{a + a + a + a} + \frac{a}{a} \\ 2782 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aa + a + a}{a + a + a + a} + \frac{a}{a} \\ 27782 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aa + a + a}{a + a + a + a} + \frac{a}{a} \\ 277782 &:= \frac{aaaaaaa + aa + a + a}{a + a + a + a} + \frac{a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 283 &:= \frac{aaaa + aa + aa - a}{a + a + a + a} \\ 2783 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aa + aa - a}{a + a + a + a} \\ 27783 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aa + aa - a}{a + a + a + a} \\ 277783 &:= \frac{aaaaaaa + aa + aa - a}{a + a + a + a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 284 &:= \frac{aaaa + a}{a + a + a + a} + \frac{aa + a}{a + a} \\ 2784 &:= \frac{aaaaa + a}{a + a + a + a} + \frac{aa + a}{a + a} \\ 27784 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + a}{a + a + a + a} + \frac{aa + a}{a + a} \\ 277784 &:= \frac{aaaaaaa + a}{a + a + a + a} + \frac{aa + a}{a + a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 285 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a) \times (aa + aa) - a \times a}{a \times a} \\ 2485 &:= \frac{(aaa + a + a) \times (aa + aa) - a \times a}{a \times a} \\ 24485 &:= \frac{(aaaa + a + a) \times (aa + aa) - a \times a}{a \times a} \\ 244485 &:= \frac{(aaaaa + a + a) \times (aa + aa) - a \times a}{a \times a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 286 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a) \times (aa + aa)}{a \times a} \\ 2886 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a) \times (aaa + aaa)}{a \times a} \\ 28886 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a) \times (aaaa + aaaa)}{a \times a} \\ 288886 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a) \times (aaaaa + aaaaa)}{a \times a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 287 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a) \times (aa + aa) + a \times a}{a \times a} \\ 2487 &:= \frac{(aaa + a + a) \times (aa + aa) + a \times a}{a \times a} \\ 24487 &:= \frac{(aaaa + a + a) \times (aa + aa) + a \times a}{a \times a} \\ 244487 &:= \frac{(aaaaa + a + a) \times (aa + aa) + a \times a}{a \times a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 288 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + a + a) \times (aa + a)}{a \times a} \\ 2688 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + a + a) \times (aaa + a)}{a \times a} \\ 26688 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + a + a) \times (aaaa + a)}{a \times a} \\ 266688 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + a + a) \times (aaaaa + a)}{a \times a} \end{aligned}$$

$$289 := \frac{(aa + aa + a + a) \times (aa + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$2689 := \frac{(aa + aa + a + a) \times (aaa + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$26689 := \frac{(aa + aa + a + a) \times (aaaa + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$266689 := \frac{(aa + aa + a + a) \times (aaaaa + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$290 := \frac{(aaa + aa + aa + aa + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$2290 := \frac{(aaaa + aa + aa + aa + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$22290 := \frac{(aaaaa + aa + aa + aa + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$222290 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aa + aa + aa + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$291 := \frac{aaaa \times (a + a + a) - (aa + a) \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$30291 := \frac{aaaaaa \times (a + a + a) - (aa + a) \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$3030291 := \frac{aaaaaaaa \times (a + a + a) - (aa + a) \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$303030291 := \frac{aaaaaaaaaa \times (a + a + a) - (aa + a) \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$292 := \frac{aaaa \times (a + a + a) - aa \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$30292 := \frac{aaaaaa \times (a + a + a) - aa \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$3030292 := \frac{aaaaaaaa \times (a + a + a) - aa \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$303030292 := \frac{aaaaaaaaaa \times (a + a + a) - aa \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$293 := \frac{(aaa - aa - a - a) \times (a + a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$3293 := \frac{(aaaa - aa - a - a) \times (a + a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$33293 := \frac{(aaaaa - aa - a - a) \times (a + a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$333293 := \frac{(aaaaaa - aa - a - a) \times (a + a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$294 := \frac{(aaa - aa - a - a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$3294 := \frac{(aaaa - aa - a - a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$33294 := \frac{(aaaaa - aa - a - a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$333294 := \frac{(aaaaaa - aa - a - a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$295 := \frac{(aaa - aa - a - a) \times (a + a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$3295 := \frac{(aaaa - aa - a - a) \times (a + a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$33295 := \frac{(aaaaa - aa - a - a) \times (a + a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$333295 := \frac{(aaaaaa - aa - a - a) \times (a + a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$296 := \frac{(aaa - aa - a) \times (a + a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$3296 := \frac{(aaaa - aa - a) \times (a + a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$33296 := \frac{(aaaaa - aa - a) \times (a + a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$333296 := \frac{(aaaaaa - aa - a) \times (a + a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$297 := \frac{(aaa - aa - a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$3297 := \frac{(aaaa - aa - a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$33297 := \frac{(aaaaa - aa - a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$333297 := \frac{(aaaaaa - aa - a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$298 := \frac{(aaa - aa - a) \times (a + a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$3298 := \frac{(aaaa - aa - a) \times (a + a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$33298 := \frac{(aaaaa - aa - a) \times (a + a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$333298 := \frac{(aaaaaa - aa - a) \times (a + a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$299 := \frac{(aaa - aa) \times (a + a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$2999 := \frac{(aaaa - aaa) \times (a + a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$29999 := \frac{(aaaaa - aaaaa) \times (a + a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$299999 := \frac{(aaaaaa - aaaaaa) \times (a + a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$300 := \frac{(aaa - aa) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$3000 := \frac{(aaaa - aaa) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$30000 := \frac{(aaaaa - aaaaa) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$300000 := \frac{(aaaaaa - aaaaaa) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$301 := \frac{(aaa - aa) \times (a + a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$3001 := \frac{(aaaa - aaa) \times (a + a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$30001 := \frac{(aaaaa - aaaaa) \times (a + a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$300001 := \frac{(aaaaaa - aaaaaa) \times (a + a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$302 := \frac{aaaa \times (a + a + a) - a \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$30302 := \frac{aaaaaa \times (a + a + a) - a \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$3030302 := \frac{aaaaaaaa \times (a + a + a) - a \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$303030302 := \frac{aaaaaaaaaa \times (a + a + a) - a \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$303 := \frac{aaaa \times (a + a + a)}{aa \times a}$$

$$30303 := \frac{aaaaaa \times (a + a + a)}{aa \times a}$$

$$3030303 := \frac{aaaaaaaa \times (a + a + a)}{aa \times a}$$

$$303030303 := \frac{aaaaaaaaaa \times (a + a + a)}{aa \times a}$$

$$304 := \frac{aaaa \times (a + a + a) + a \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$30304 := \frac{aaaaaa \times (a + a + a) + a \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$3030304 := \frac{aaaaaaaa \times (a + a + a) + a \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$303030304 := \frac{aaaaaaaaaa \times (a + a + a) + a \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$305 := \frac{(aaa - aa + a) \times (a + a + a) + (a + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$3305 := \frac{(aaaa - aa + a) \times (a + a + a) + (a + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$33305 := \frac{(aaaaa - aa + a) \times (a + a + a) + (a + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$333305 := \frac{(aaaaaa - aa + a) \times (a + a + a) + (a + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$306 := \frac{(aaaa + aa) \times (a + a + a)}{aa \times a}$$

$$30306 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aa) \times (a + a + a)}{aa \times a}$$

$$3030306 := \frac{(aaaaaaaa + aa) \times (a + a + a)}{aa \times a}$$

$$303030306 := \frac{(aaaaaaaaaa + aa) \times (a + a + a)}{aa \times a}$$

$$307 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times aa - (a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times (a + a)}$$

$$3107 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times aaa - (a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times (a + a)}$$

$$31107 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times aaaa - (a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times (a + a)}$$

$$311107 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times aaaaa - (a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times (a + a)}$$

$$308 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times aa}{(a + a) \times (a + a)}$$

$$3058 := \frac{(aaaa + a) \times aa}{(a + a) \times (a + a)}$$

$$30558 := \frac{(aaaaa + a) \times aa}{(a + a) \times (a + a)}$$

$$305558 := \frac{(aaaaaa + a) \times aa}{(a + a) \times (a + a)}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 309 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa + aaa - aa - aa - a - a}{a} \\ 1309 &:= \frac{aaaa + aaa + aaa - aa - aa - a - a}{a} \\ 11309 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aaa + aaa - aa - aa - a - a}{a} \\ 111309 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aaa + aaa - aa - aa - a - a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 310 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa + aaa - aa - aa - a}{a} \\ 1310 &:= \frac{aaaa + aaa + aaa - aa - aa - a}{a} \\ 11310 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aaa + aaa - aa - aa - a}{a} \\ 111310 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aaa + aaa - aa - aa - a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 311 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa + aaa - aa - aa}{a} \\ 1311 &:= \frac{aaaa + aaa + aaa - aa - aa}{a} \\ 11311 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aaa + aaa - aa - aa}{a} \\ 111311 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aaa + aaa - aa - aa}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 312 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + a + a) \times (aa + a + a)}{a \times a} \\ 3192 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + a + a) \times (aaa + aa + aa)}{a \times a} \\ 31992 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + a + a) \times (aaaa + aaa + aaa)}{a \times a} \\ 319992 &:= \frac{(a + aa + a + a) \times (aaaaa + aaaa + aaaa)}{a \times a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 313 &:= \frac{aaaa \times (a + a) + aaa \times aa}{aa \times a} \\ 1313 &:= \frac{aaaa \times (a + a) + aaaa \times aa}{aa \times a} \\ 11313 &:= \frac{aaaa \times (a + a) + aaaaa \times aa}{aa \times a} \\ 111313 &:= \frac{aaaa \times (a + a) + aaaaaa \times aa}{aa \times a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 314 &:= \frac{aaaa \times (a + a) + (aaa + a) \times aa}{aa \times a} \\ 1314 &:= \frac{aaaa \times (a + a) + (aaaa + a) \times aa}{aa \times a} \\ 11314 &:= \frac{aaaa \times (a + a) + (aaaaa + a) \times aa}{aa \times a} \\ 111314 &:= \frac{aaaa \times (a + a) + (aaaaaa + a) \times aa}{aa \times a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 315 &:= \frac{aaaa \times (a + a) + (aaa + a + a) \times aa}{aa \times a} \\ 1315 &:= \frac{aaaa \times (a + a) + (aaaa + a + a) \times aa}{aa \times a} \\ 11315 &:= \frac{aaaa \times (a + a) + (aaaaa + a + a) \times aa}{aa \times a} \\ 111315 &:= \frac{aaaa \times (a + a) + (aaaaaa + a + a) \times aa}{aa \times a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 316 &:= \frac{aaaa \times (a + a) + (aaa + a + a + a) \times aa}{aa \times a} \\ 1316 &:= \frac{aaaa \times (a + a) + (aaaa + a + a + a) \times aa}{aa \times a} \\ 11316 &:= \frac{aaaa \times (a + a) + (aaaaa + a + a + a) \times aa}{aa \times a} \\ 111316 &:= \frac{aaaa \times (a + a) + (aaaaaa + a + a + a) \times aa}{aa \times a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 317 &:= \frac{(aaaa + aa) \times (a + a + a) + aa \times aa}{a \times aa} \\ 30317 &:= \frac{(aaaaaa + aa) \times (a + a + a) + aa \times aa}{a \times aa} \\ 3030317 &:= \frac{(aaaaaaaa + aa) \times (a + a + a) + aa \times aa}{a \times aa} \\ 303030317 &:= \frac{(aaaaaaaaaa + aa) \times (a + a + a) + aa \times aa}{a \times aa} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 318 &:= \frac{(aaa - a) \times (a + a + a) - (aa + a) \times a}{a \times a} \\ 3318 &:= \frac{(aaaa - a) \times (a + a + a) - (aa + a) \times a}{a \times a} \\ 33318 &:= \frac{(aaaaa - a) \times (a + a + a) - (aa + a) \times a}{a \times a} \\ 333318 &:= \frac{(aaaaaa - a) \times (a + a + a) - (aa + a) \times a}{a \times a} \end{aligned}$$

$$319 := \frac{(aaa - a) \times (a + a + a) - aa \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$3319 := \frac{(aaaa - a) \times (a + a + a) - aa \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$33319 := \frac{(aaaaa - a) \times (a + a + a) - aa \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$333319 := \frac{(aaaaaa - a) \times (a + a + a) - aa \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$320 := \frac{aaa + aaa + aaa - aa - a - a}{a}$$

$$1320 := \frac{aaaa + aaa + aaa - aa - a - a}{a}$$

$$11320 := \frac{aaaaa + aaa + aaa - aa - a - a}{a}$$

$$111320 := \frac{aaaaaa + aaa + aaa - aa - a - a}{a}$$

$$321 := \frac{aaa + aaa + aaa - aa - a}{a}$$

$$1321 := \frac{aaaa + aaa + aaa - aa - a}{a}$$

$$11321 := \frac{aaaaa + aaa + aaa - aa - a}{a}$$

$$111321 := \frac{aaaaaa + aaa + aaa - aa - a}{a}$$

$$322 := \frac{aaa + aaa + aaa - aa}{a}$$

$$1322 := \frac{aaaa + aaa + aaa - aa}{a}$$

$$11322 := \frac{aaaaa + aaa + aaa - aa}{a}$$

$$111322 := \frac{aaaaaa + aaa + aaa - aa}{a}$$

$$323 := \frac{aaa + aaa + aaa - aa + a}{a}$$

$$1323 := \frac{aaaa + aaa + aaa - aa + a}{a}$$

$$11323 := \frac{aaaaa + aaa + aaa - aa + a}{a}$$

$$111323 := \frac{aaaaaa + aaa + aaa - aa + a}{a}$$

$$324 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times (a + a + a) - aa \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$3324 := \frac{(aaaa + a) \times (a + a + a) - aa \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$33324 := \frac{(aaaaa + a) \times (a + a + a) - aa \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$333324 := \frac{(aaaaaa + a) \times (a + a + a) - aa \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$325 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times (a + a + a) - aa \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$3325 := \frac{(aaaa + a) \times (a + a + a) - aa \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$33325 := \frac{(aaaaa + a) \times (a + a + a) - aa \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$333325 := \frac{(aaaaaa + a) \times (a + a + a) - aa \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$326 := \frac{(aaa - a - a) \times (a + a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$3326 := \frac{(aaaa - a - a) \times (a + a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$33326 := \frac{(aaaaa - a - a) \times (a + a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$333326 := \frac{(aaaaaa - a - a) \times (a + a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$327 := \frac{(aaa - a - a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$3327 := \frac{(aaaa - a - a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$33327 := \frac{(aaaaa - a - a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$333327 := \frac{(aaaaaa - a - a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$328 := \frac{(aaa - a - a) \times (a + a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$3328 := \frac{(aaaa - a - a) \times (a + a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$33328 := \frac{(aaaaa - a - a) \times (a + a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$333328 := \frac{(aaaaaa - a - a) \times (a + a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$329 := \frac{(aaa - a) \times (a + a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$3399 := \frac{(aaaa - a) \times (a + a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$33399 := \frac{(aaaaa - a) \times (a + a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$333399 := \frac{(aaaaaa - a) \times (a + a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$330 := \frac{(aa + aa + aa) \times (aa - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$3630 := \frac{(aa + aa + aa) \times (aaa - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$36630 := \frac{(aa + aa + aa) \times (aaaa - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$366630 := \frac{(aa + aa + aa) \times (aaaaa - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$331 := \frac{aaa + aaa + aaa - a - a}{a}$$

$$1331 := \frac{aaa + aaa + aaaa - a - a}{a}$$

$$11331 := \frac{aaa + aaa + aaaaa - a - a}{a}$$

$$111331 := \frac{aaa + aaa + aaaaaa - a - a}{a}$$

$$332 := \frac{aaa + aaa + aaa - a}{a}$$

$$1332 := \frac{aaa + aaa + aaaa - a}{a}$$

$$11332 := \frac{aaa + aaa + aaaaa - a}{a}$$

$$111332 := \frac{aaa + aaa + aaaaaa - a}{a}$$

$$333 := \frac{(a + a + a) \times aaa}{a \times a}$$

$$3333 := \frac{(a + a + a) \times aaaa}{a \times a}$$

$$33333 := \frac{(a + a + a) \times aaaaa}{a \times a}$$

$$333333 := \frac{(a + a + a) \times aaaaaa}{a \times a}$$

$$334 := \frac{aaa + aaa + aaa + a}{a}$$

$$1334 := \frac{aaa + aaa + aaaa + a}{a}$$

$$11334 := \frac{aaa + aaa + aaaaa + a}{a}$$

$$111334 := \frac{aaa + aaa + aaaaaa + a}{a}$$

$$335 := \frac{aaa + aaa + aaa + a + a}{a}$$

$$1335 := \frac{aaa + aaa + aaaa + a + a}{a}$$

$$11335 := \frac{aaa + aaa + aaaaa + a + a}{a}$$

$$111335 := \frac{aaa + aaa + aaaaaa + a + a}{a}$$

$$336 := \frac{aaa + aaa + aaa + a + a + a}{a}$$

$$1336 := \frac{aaa + aaa + aaaa + a + a + a}{a}$$

$$11336 := \frac{aaa + aaa + aaaaa + a + a + a}{a}$$

$$111336 := \frac{aaa + aaa + aaaaaa + a + a + a}{a}$$

$$337 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times (a + a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$3337 := \frac{(aaaa + a) \times (a + a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$33337 := \frac{(aaaaa + a) \times (a + a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$333337 := \frac{(aaaaaa + a) \times (a + a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

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$$33338 := \frac{(aaaaa + a) \times (a + a + a) + (a + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

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$$339 := \frac{(aaa + a + a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$3339 := \frac{(aaaa + a + a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$33339 := \frac{(aaaaa + a + a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

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$$1340 := \frac{(aaa + aa + aa + a) \times (aa - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$11340 := \frac{(aaaa + aa + aa + a) \times (aa - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$111340 := \frac{(aaaaa + aa + aa + a) \times (aa - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$341 := \frac{(aa + aa + aa - a - a) \times aa}{a \times a}$$

$$3441 := \frac{(aa + aa + aa - a - a) \times aaa}{a \times a}$$

$$34441 := \frac{(aa + aa + aa - a - a) \times aaaa}{a \times a}$$

$$344441 := \frac{(aa + aa + aa - a - a) \times aaaaa}{a \times a}$$

$$342 := \frac{(aaa + a + a + a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$3342 := \frac{(aaaa + a + a + a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

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$$1343 := \frac{aaaa + aaa + aaa + aa - a}{a}$$

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$$111343 := \frac{aaaaaa + aaa + aaa + aa - a}{a}$$

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$$1344 := \frac{aaaa + aaa + aaa + aa}{a}$$

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$$111344 := \frac{aaaaaa + aaa + aaa + aa}{a}$$

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$$111345 := \frac{aaaaaa + aaa + aaa + aa + a}{a}$$

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$$1346 := \frac{aaaa + aaa + aaa + aa + a + a}{a}$$

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$$347 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times (a + a + a) + aa \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$3347 := \frac{(aaaa + a) \times (a + a + a) + aa \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$33347 := \frac{(aaaaa + a) \times (a + a + a) + aa \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$333347 := \frac{(aaaaaa + a) \times (a + a + a) + aa \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$348 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times (a + a + a) + (aa + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$3348 := \frac{(aaaa + a) \times (a + a + a) + (aa + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$33348 := \frac{(aaaaa + a) \times (a + a + a) + (aa + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$333348 := \frac{(aaaaaa + a) \times (a + a + a) + (aa + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

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$$3349 := \frac{(aaaa + a) \times (a + a + a) + (aa + a + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$33349 := \frac{(aaaaa + a) \times (a + a + a) + (aa + a + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

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$$1352 := \frac{(aa + aa) \times aa + (aaaa - a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$11352 := \frac{(aa + aa) \times aa + (aaaaa - a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$111352 := \frac{(aa + aa) \times aa + (aaaaaa - a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

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$$1353 := \frac{(aa + aa) \times aa + aaaa \times a}{a \times a}$$

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$$111353 := \frac{(aa + aa) \times aa + aaaaaa \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$354 := \frac{aaa + aaa + aaa + aa + aa - a}{a}$$

$$1354 := \frac{aaaa + aaa + aaa + aa + aa - a}{a}$$

$$11354 := \frac{aaaaa + aaa + aaa + aa + aa - a}{a}$$

$$111354 := \frac{aaaaaa + aaa + aaa + aa + aa - a}{a}$$

$$355 := \frac{aaa + aaa + aaa + aa + aa}{a}$$

$$1355 := \frac{aaaa + aaa + aaa + aa + aa}{a}$$

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$$111355 := \frac{aaaaaa + aaa + aaa + aa + aa}{a}$$

$$356 := \frac{aaa + aaa + aaa + aa + aa + a}{a}$$

$$1356 := \frac{aaaa + aaa + aaa + aa + aa + a}{a}$$

$$11356 := \frac{aaaaa + aaa + aaa + aa + aa + a}{a}$$

$$111356 := \frac{aaaaaa + aaa + aaa + aa + aa + a}{a}$$

$$357 := \frac{(aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a) + aaa \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$1357 := \frac{(aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a) + aaaa \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$11357 := \frac{(aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a) + aaaaa \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$111357 := \frac{(aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a) + aaaaaa \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$358 := \frac{(aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a) + (aaa + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$1358 := \frac{(aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a) + (aaaa + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$11358 := \frac{(aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a) + (aaaaa + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$111358 := \frac{(aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a) + (aaaaaa + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$359 := \frac{aaaa - aa - aa - aa - a}{a + a + a}$$

$$370359 := \frac{aaaaaaaa - aa - aa - aa - a}{a + a + a}$$

$$370370359 := \frac{aaaaaaaaaaaa - aa - aa - aa - a}{a + a + a}$$

$$370370370359 := \frac{aaaaaaaaaaaaaaaa - aa - aa - aa - a}{a + a + a}$$

$$360 := \frac{(aaa + aa - a - a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$3360 := \frac{(aaaa + aa - a - a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$33360 := \frac{(aaaaa + aa - a - a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$333360 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aa - a - a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

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$$33361 := \frac{(aaaaa + aa - a - a) \times (a + a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$333361 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aa - a - a) \times (a + a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$362 := \frac{(aa + aa + aa) \times aa - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$3662 := \frac{(aa + aa + aa) \times aaa - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

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$$366662 := \frac{(aa + aa + aa) \times aaaaa - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$363 := \frac{(aa + aa + aa) \times aa}{a \times a}$$

$$3663 := \frac{(aa + aa + aa) \times aaa}{a \times a}$$

$$36663 := \frac{(aa + aa + aa) \times aaaa}{a \times a}$$

$$366663 := \frac{(aa + aa + aa) \times aaaaa}{a \times a}$$

$$364 := \frac{(aa + aa + aa) \times aa + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$3664 := \frac{(aa + aa + aa) \times aaa + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

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$$365 := \frac{(aaa + aa) \times (a + a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$3365 := \frac{(aaaa + aa) \times (a + a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$33365 := \frac{(aaaaa + aa) \times (a + a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$333365 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aa) \times (a + a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$366 := \frac{(aaa + aa) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$3366 := \frac{(aaaa + aa) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$33366 := \frac{(aaaaa + aa) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$333366 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aa) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$367 := \frac{(aaa + aa) \times (a + a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$3367 := \frac{(aaaa + aa) \times (a + a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$33367 := \frac{(aaaaa + aa) \times (a + a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$333367 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aa) \times (a + a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$368 := \frac{(aaa + aa) \times (a + a + a) + a \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$3368 := \frac{(aaaa + aa) \times (a + a + a) + a \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$33368 := \frac{(aaaaa + aa) \times (a + a + a) + a \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$333368 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aa) \times (a + a + a) + a \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$369 := \frac{aaaa - a - a - a - a}{a + a + a}$$

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$$370 := \frac{aaaa - a}{a + a + a}$$

$$3700 := \frac{aaaaa - aa}{a + a + a}$$

$$37000 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaa}{a + a + a}$$

$$370000 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaa}{a + a + a}$$

$$371 := \frac{(aaa + aa + a + a) \times (a + a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$3371 := \frac{(aaaa + aa + a + a) \times (a + a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$33371 := \frac{(aaaaa + aa + a + a) \times (a + a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$333371 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aa + a + a) \times (a + a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$372 := \frac{(aaa + aa + a + a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$3372 := \frac{(aaaa + aa + a + a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$33372 := \frac{(aaaaa + aa + a + a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

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$$373 := \frac{(aa + aa + aa + a) \times aa - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

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$$374 := \frac{(aa + aa + aa + a) \times aa}{a \times a}$$

$$3774 := \frac{(aa + aa + aa + a) \times aaa}{a \times a}$$

$$37774 := \frac{(aa + aa + aa + a) \times aaaa}{a \times a}$$

$$377774 := \frac{(aa + aa + aa + a) \times aaaaa}{a \times a}$$

$$375 := \frac{(aa + aa + aa + a) \times aa + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$3775 := \frac{(aa + aa + aa + a) \times aaa + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

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$$376 := \frac{(aa + aa + aa + a) \times aa + a \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$3776 := \frac{(aa + aa + aa + a) \times aaa + a \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

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$$3777 := \frac{(aa + aa + aa + a) \times aaa + a \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$37777 := \frac{(aa + aa + aa + a) \times aaaa + a \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$377777 := \frac{(aa + aa + aa + a) \times aaaaa + a \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$378 := \frac{aaaa + aa + aa + a}{a + a + a}$$

$$370378 := \frac{aaaaaaa + aa + aa + a}{a + a + a}$$

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$$370370370378 := \frac{aaaaaaaaaaaaa + aa + aa + a}{a + a + a}$$

$$379 := \frac{aaaa + a}{a + a + a + a} + \frac{aaaa}{aa}$$

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$$1010379 := \frac{aaaa + a}{a + a + a + a} + \frac{aaaaaaaa}{aa}$$

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$$380 := \frac{aaaa - a}{a + a + a} + \frac{aa - a}{a}$$

$$3810 := \frac{aaaaa - aa}{a + a + a} + \frac{aaa - a}{a}$$

$$38110 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaa}{a + a + a} + \frac{aaaa - a}{a}$$

$$381110 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaa}{a + a + a} + \frac{aaaaa - a}{a}$$

$$381 := \frac{aaaa - a}{a + a + a} + \frac{aa}{a}$$

$$3811 := \frac{aaaaa - aa}{a + a + a} + \frac{aaa}{a}$$

$$38111 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaa}{a + a + a} + \frac{aaaa}{a}$$

$$381111 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaa}{a + a + a} + \frac{aaaaa}{a}$$

$$382 := \frac{aaaa - a}{a + a + a} + \frac{aa + a}{a}$$

$$3812 := \frac{aaaaa - aa}{a + a + a} + \frac{aaa + a}{a}$$

$$38112 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaa}{a + a + a} + \frac{aaaa + a}{a}$$

$$381112 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaa}{a + a + a} + \frac{aaaaa + a}{a}$$

$$383 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - aaa - aa - a}{a + a}$$

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$$55383 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaa - aaa - aaa - aa - a}{a + a}$$

$$555383 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaa - aaa - aaa - aa - a}{a + a}$$

$$384 := \frac{(aa + aa + aa - a) \times (aa + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$3984 := \frac{(aaa + aaa + aaa - a) \times (aa + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$39984 := \frac{(aaaa + aaaa + aaaa - a) \times (aa + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$399984 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaaaa + aaaaa - a) \times (aa + a)}{a \times a}$$

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$$3885 := \frac{(aa + aa + aa + a + a) \times aaa}{a \times a}$$

$$38885 := \frac{(aa + aa + aa + a + a) \times aaaa}{a \times a}$$

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$$386 := \frac{(aa + aa + aa + a + a) \times aa + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$3886 := \frac{(aa + aa + aa + a + a) \times aaa + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$38886 := \frac{(aa + aa + aa + a + a) \times aaaa + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

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$$555388 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaa - aaa - aaa - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 389 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - aaa}{a + a} \\
 5389 &:= \frac{aaaaa - aaa - aaa - aaa}{a + a} \\
 55389 &:= \frac{aaaaaa - aaa - aaa - aaa}{a + a} \\
 555389 &:= \frac{aaaaaaa - aaa - aaa - aaa}{a + a} \\
 \\
 390 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - aaa + a + a}{a + a} \\
 5390 &:= \frac{aaaaa - aaa - aaa - aaa + a + a}{a + a} \\
 55390 &:= \frac{aaaaaa - aaa - aaa - aaa + a + a}{a + a} \\
 555390 &:= \frac{aaaaaaa - aaa - aaa - aaa + a + a}{a + a} \\
 \\
 391 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - aaa + a + a + a + a}{a + a} \\
 5391 &:= \frac{aaaaa - aaa - aaa - aaa + a + a + a + a}{a + a} \\
 55391 &:= \frac{aaaaaa - aaa - aaa - aaa + a + a + a + a}{a + a} \\
 555391 &:= \frac{aaaaaaa - aaa - aaa - aaa + a + a + a + a}{a + a} \\
 \\
 392 &:= \frac{(aaa - aa - a - a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a} \\
 4392 &:= \frac{(aaaa - aa - a - a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a} \\
 44392 &:= \frac{(aaaaa - aa - a - a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a} \\
 444392 &:= \frac{(aaaaaa - aa - a - a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a} \\
 \\
 393 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + aa) \times (aa + a) - (a + a + a) \times a}{a \times a} \\
 3693 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + aa) \times (aaa + a) - (a + a + a) \times a}{a \times a} \\
 36693 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + aa) \times (aaaa + a) - (a + a + a) \times a}{a \times a} \\
 366693 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + aa) \times (aaaaa + a) - (a + a + a) \times a}{a \times a}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 394 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + aa) \times (aa + a) - (a + a) \times a}{a \times a} \\
 3694 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + aa) \times (aaa + a) - (a + a) \times a}{a \times a} \\
 36694 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + aa) \times (aaaa + a) - (a + a) \times a}{a \times a} \\
 366694 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + aa) \times (aaaaa + a) - (a + a) \times a}{a \times a} \\
 \\
 395 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + aa) \times (aa + a) - a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 3695 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + aa) \times (aaa + a) - a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 36695 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + aa) \times (aaaa + a) - a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 366695 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + aa) \times (aaaaa + a) - a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 \\
 396 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + aa) \times (aa + a)}{a \times a} \\
 3696 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + aa) \times (aaa + a)}{a \times a} \\
 36696 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + aa) \times (aaaa + a)}{a \times a} \\
 366696 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + aa) \times (aaaaa + a)}{a \times a} \\
 \\
 397 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + aa) \times (aa + a) + a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 3697 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + aa) \times (aaa + a) + a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 36697 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + aa) \times (aaaa + a) + a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 366697 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + aa) \times (aaaaa + a) + a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 \\
 398 &:= \frac{(aaa + aaa - aa - aa - a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 2398 &:= \frac{(aaaa + aaa - aa - aa - a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 22398 &:= \frac{(aaaaa + aaa - aa - aa - a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 222398 &:= \frac{(aaaaaa + aaa - aa - aa - a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 399 &:= \frac{(aaa + aa + aa) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 3399 &:= \frac{(aaaa + aa + aa) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 33399 &:= \frac{(aaaaa + aa + aa) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 333399 &:= \frac{(aaaaaa + aa + aa) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 \\
 400 &:= \frac{(aaa - aa) \times (a + a + a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 4400 &:= \frac{(aaaa - aa) \times (a + a + a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 44400 &:= \frac{(aaaaa - aa) \times (a + a + a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 444400 &:= \frac{(aaaaaa - aa) \times (a + a + a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 \\
 401 &:= \frac{(aaa - aa) \times (a + a + a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 4401 &:= \frac{(aaaa - aa) \times (a + a + a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 44401 &:= \frac{(aaaaa - aa) \times (a + a + a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 444401 &:= \frac{(aaaaaa - aa) \times (a + a + a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 \\
 402 &:= \frac{(aaa - aa) \times (a + a + a + a) + a \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 4402 &:= \frac{(aaaa - aa) \times (a + a + a + a) + a \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 44402 &:= \frac{(aaaaa - aa) \times (a + a + a + a) + a \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 444402 &:= \frac{(aaaaaa - aa) \times (a + a + a + a) + a \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 \\
 403 &:= \frac{(aaaa + aaaa) \times (a + a) - a \times aa}{a \times aa} \\
 20403 &:= \frac{(aaaaaa + aaaa) \times (a + a) - a \times aa}{a \times aa} \\
 2020403 &:= \frac{(aaaaaaaa + aaaa) \times (a + a) - a \times aa}{a \times aa} \\
 202020403 &:= \frac{(aaaaaaaaaa + aaaa) \times (a + a) - a \times aa}{a \times aa}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 404 &:= \frac{aaaa \times (a + a + a + a)}{aa \times a} \\
 40404 &:= \frac{aaaaaa \times (a + a + a + a)}{aa \times a} \\
 4040404 &:= \frac{aaaaaaaa \times (a + a + a + a)}{aa \times a} \\
 404040404 &:= \frac{aaaaaaaaaa \times (a + a + a + a)}{aa \times a} \\
 \\
 405 &:= \frac{aaa \times aa - (a + a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a} \\
 4105 &:= \frac{aaa \times aaa - (a + a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a} \\
 41105 &:= \frac{aaa \times aaaa - (a + a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a} \\
 411105 &:= \frac{aaa \times aaaaa - (a + a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a} \\
 \\
 406 &:= \frac{aaa \times aa - (a + a + a) \times a}{(a + a + a) \times a} \\
 4106 &:= \frac{aaa \times aaa - (a + a + a) \times a}{(a + a + a) \times a} \\
 41106 &:= \frac{aaa \times aaaa - (a + a + a) \times a}{(a + a + a) \times a} \\
 411106 &:= \frac{aaa \times aaaaa - (a + a + a) \times a}{(a + a + a) \times a} \\
 \\
 407 &:= \frac{aaa \times aa}{(a + a + a) \times a} \\
 4107 &:= \frac{aaa \times aaa}{(a + a + a) \times a} \\
 41107 &:= \frac{aaa \times aaaa}{(a + a + a) \times a} \\
 411107 &:= \frac{aaa \times aaaaa}{(a + a + a) \times a}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$408 := \frac{aaa \times aa + (a + a + a) \times a}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$4108 := \frac{aaa \times aaa + (a + a + a) \times a}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$41108 := \frac{aaa \times aaaa + (a + a + a) \times a}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$411108 := \frac{aaa \times aaaaa + (a + a + a) \times a}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$409 := \frac{aaa \times aa + (a + a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$4109 := \frac{aaa \times aaa + (a + a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$41109 := \frac{aaa \times aaaa + (a + a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$411109 := \frac{aaa \times aaaaa + (a + a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$410 := \frac{aaaa + aaa + aa - a - a - a}{a + a + a}$$

$$4110 := \frac{aaaaa + aaaa + aaa - a - a - a}{a + a + a}$$

$$41110 := \frac{aaaaaa + aaaaa + aaaa - a - a - a}{a + a + a}$$

$$411110 := \frac{aaaaaaa + aaaaaa + aaaaa - a - a - a}{a + a + a}$$

$$411 := \frac{aaaa + aaa + aa}{a + a + a}$$

$$4111 := \frac{aaaaa + aaaa + aaa}{a + a + a}$$

$$41111 := \frac{aaaaaa + aaaaa + aaaa}{a + a + a}$$

$$411111 := \frac{aaaaaaa + aaaaaa + aaaaa}{a + a + a}$$

$$412 := \frac{aaaa + aaa + aa + a + a + a}{a + a + a}$$

$$4112 := \frac{aaaaa + aaaa + aaa + a + a + a}{a + a + a}$$

$$41112 := \frac{aaaaaa + aaaaa + aaaa + a + a + a}{a + a + a}$$

$$411112 := \frac{aaaaaaa + aaaaaa + aaaaa + a + a + a}{a + a + a}$$

$$413 := \frac{aaaa \times (a + a + a) + (aaa - a) \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$1413 := \frac{aaaa \times (a + a + a) + (aaa - a) \times aaa}{a \times aa}$$

$$11413 := \frac{aaaa \times (a + a + a) + (aaa - a) \times aaaa}{a \times aa}$$

$$111413 := \frac{aaaa \times (a + a + a) + (aaa - a) \times aaaaa}{a \times aa}$$

$$414 := \frac{aaaa \times (a + a + a) + aaa \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$30414 := \frac{aaaaaa \times (a + a + a) + aaa \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$3030414 := \frac{aaaaaaaa \times (a + a + a) + aaa \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$303030414 := \frac{aaaaaaaaaa \times (a + a + a) + aaa \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$415 := \frac{aaaa \times (a + a + a) + (aaa + a) \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$30415 := \frac{aaaaaa \times (a + a + a) + (aaa + a) \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$3030415 := \frac{aaaaaaaa \times (a + a + a) + (aaa + a) \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$303030415 := \frac{aaaaaaaaaa \times (a + a + a) + (aaa + a) \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$416 := \frac{aaa \times aa + (aa - a - a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times (a + a + a)}$$

$$4116 := \frac{aaa \times aaa + (aa - a - a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times (a + a + a)}$$

$$41116 := \frac{aaa \times aaaa + (aa - a - a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times (a + a + a)}$$

$$411116 := \frac{aaa \times aaaaa + (aa - a - a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times (a + a + a)}$$

$$417 := \frac{aaa \times aa + (aa - a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times (a + a + a)}$$

$$4117 := \frac{aaa \times aaa + (aa - a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times (a + a + a)}$$

$$41117 := \frac{aaa \times aaaa + (aa - a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times (a + a + a)}$$

$$411117 := \frac{aaa \times aaaaa + (aa - a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times (a + a + a)}$$

$$418 := \frac{aaa \times aa + aa \times (a + a + a)}{a \times (a + a + a)}$$

$$4118 := \frac{aaa \times aaa + aa \times (a + a + a)}{a \times (a + a + a)}$$

$$41118 := \frac{aaa \times aaaa + aa \times (a + a + a)}{a \times (a + a + a)}$$

$$411118 := \frac{aaa \times aaaaa + aa \times (a + a + a)}{a \times (a + a + a)}$$

$$419 := \frac{aaa \times aa + (aa + a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times (a + a + a)}$$

$$4119 := \frac{aaa \times aaa + (aa + a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times (a + a + a)}$$

$$41119 := \frac{aaa \times aaaa + (aa + a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times (a + a + a)}$$

$$411119 := \frac{aaa \times aaaaa + (aa + a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times (a + a + a)}$$

$$420 := \frac{(aaa + aaa - aa - a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$2420 := \frac{(aaaa + aaa - aa - a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$22420 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaa - aa - a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$222420 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aaa - aa - a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$421 := \frac{(aaa + aaa - aa) \times (a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$2421 := \frac{(aaaa + aaa - aa) \times (a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$22421 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaa - aa) \times (a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$222421 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aaa - aa) \times (a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$422 := \frac{(aaa + aaa - aa) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$2422 := \frac{(aaaa + aaa - aa) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$22422 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaa - aa) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$222422 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aaa - aa) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$423 := \frac{(aaa + aaa - aa) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$2423 := \frac{(aaaa + aaa - aa) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$22423 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaa - aa) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$222423 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aaa - aa) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$424 := \frac{(aaa + aaa - aa + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$2424 := \frac{(aaaa + aaa - aa + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$22424 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaa - aa + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$222424 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aaa - aa + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$425 := \frac{(aaa + aaa - aa + a) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$2425 := \frac{(aaaa + aaa - aa + a) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$22425 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaa - aa + a) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$222425 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aaa - aa + a) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$426 := \frac{(aaa + aaa - aa + a + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$2426 := \frac{(aaaa + aaa - aa + a + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$22426 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaa - aa + a + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$222426 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aaa - aa + a + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$427 := \frac{(aaa + aaa - aa + a + a) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$2427 := \frac{(aaaa + aaa - aa + a + a) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$22427 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaa - aa + a + a) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$222427 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aaa - aa + a + a) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 428 &:= \frac{(aaa + aaa - aa + a + a + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 2428 &:= \frac{(aaaa + aaa - aa + a + a + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 22428 &:= \frac{(aaaaa + aaa - aa + a + a + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 222428 &:= \frac{(aaaaaa + aaa - aa + a + a + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 \\
 429 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a) \times (aa + aa + aa)}{a \times a} \\
 4329 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a) \times (aaa + aaa + aaa)}{a \times a} \\
 43329 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a) \times (aaaa + aaaa + aaaa)}{a \times a} \\
 433329 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a) \times (aaaaa + aaaaa + aaaaa)}{a \times a} \\
 \\
 430 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a) \times (aa + aa + aa) + a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 4330 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a) \times (aaa + aaa + aaa) + a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 43330 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a) \times (aaaa + aaaa + aaaa) + a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 433330 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a) \times (aaaaa + aaaaa + aaaaa) + a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 \\
 431 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa + aaa + aaa - aa - a - a}{a} \\
 1431 &:= \frac{aaaa + aaa + aaa + aaa - aa - a - a}{a} \\
 11431 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aaa + aaa + aaa - aa - a - a}{a} \\
 111431 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aaa + aaa + aaa - aa - a - a}{a} \\
 \\
 432 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa + aaa + aaa - aa - a}{a} \\
 1432 &:= \frac{aaaa + aaa + aaa + aaa - aa - a}{a} \\
 11432 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aaa + aaa + aaa - aa - a}{a} \\
 111432 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aaa + aaa + aaa - aa - a}{a}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 433 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa + aaa + aaa - aa}{a} \\
 1433 &:= \frac{aaaa + aaa + aaa + aaa - aa}{a} \\
 11433 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aaa + aaa + aaa - aa}{a} \\
 111433 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aaa + aaa + aaa - aa}{a} \\
 \\
 434 &:= \frac{aaa + aaa + aaa + aaa - aa + a}{a} \\
 1434 &:= \frac{aaaa + aaa + aaa + aaa - aa + a}{a} \\
 11434 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aaa + aaa + aaa - aa + a}{a} \\
 111434 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aaa + aaa + aaa - aa + a}{a} \\
 \\
 435 &:= \frac{(aaa - a - a) \times (a + a + a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 4435 &:= \frac{(aaaa - a - a) \times (a + a + a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 44435 &:= \frac{(aaaaa - a - a) \times (a + a + a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 444435 &:= \frac{(aaaaaa - a - a) \times (a + a + a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 \\
 436 &:= \frac{(aaa - a - a) \times (a + a + a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 4436 &:= \frac{(aaaa - a - a) \times (a + a + a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 44436 &:= \frac{(aaaaa - a - a) \times (a + a + a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 444436 &:= \frac{(aaaaaa - a - a) \times (a + a + a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 \\
 437 &:= \frac{aaaa - aa - a - a}{a + a} - \frac{aaa + a}{a} \\
 5437 &:= \frac{aaaaa - aa - a - a}{a + a} - \frac{aaa + a}{a} \\
 55437 &:= \frac{aaaaaa - aa - a - a}{a + a} - \frac{aaa + a}{a} \\
 555437 &:= \frac{aaaaaaa - aa - a - a}{a + a} - \frac{aaa + a}{a}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$438 := \frac{aaaa - aa - a - a}{a + a} - \frac{aaa}{a}$$

$$4438 := \frac{aaaaa - aa - a - a}{a + a} - \frac{aaaa}{a}$$

$$44438 := \frac{aaaaaa - aa - a - a}{a + a} - \frac{aaaaa}{a}$$

$$444438 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aa - a - a}{a + a} - \frac{aaaaaa}{a}$$

$$439 := \frac{aaaa - aa - a - a}{a + a} - \frac{aaa - a}{a}$$

$$5439 := \frac{aaaaa - aa - a - a}{a + a} - \frac{aaa - a}{a}$$

$$55439 := \frac{aaaaaa - aa - a - a}{a + a} - \frac{aaa - a}{a}$$

$$555439 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aa - a - a}{a + a} - \frac{aaa - a}{a}$$

$$440 := \frac{(a + a + a + a) \times (aaa - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$4440 := \frac{(a + a + a + a) \times (aaaa - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$44440 := \frac{(a + a + a + a) \times (aaaaa - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$444440 := \frac{(a + a + a + a) \times (aaaaaa - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$441 := \frac{(aaa + aaa - a) \times (a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$2441 := \frac{(aaaa + aaa - a) \times (a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$22441 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaa - a) \times (a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$222441 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aaa - a) \times (a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$442 := \frac{(aaa + aaa - a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$2442 := \frac{(aaaa + aaa - a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$22442 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaa - a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$222442 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aaa - a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$443 := \frac{(a + a + a + a) \times aaa - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$4443 := \frac{(a + a + a + a) \times aaaa - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$44443 := \frac{(a + a + a + a) \times aaaaa - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$444443 := \frac{(a + a + a + a) \times aaaaaa - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$444 := \frac{(a + a + a + a) \times aaa}{a \times a}$$

$$4444 := \frac{(a + a + a + a) \times aaaa}{a \times a}$$

$$44444 := \frac{(a + a + a + a) \times aaaaa}{a \times a}$$

$$444444 := \frac{(a + a + a + a) \times aaaaaa}{a \times a}$$

$$445 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa + a}{a + a}$$

$$5445 := \frac{aaaaa - aaa - aaa + a}{a + a}$$

$$55445 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaa - aaa + a}{a + a}$$

$$555445 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaa - aaa + a}{a + a}$$

$$446 := \frac{(aaa + aaa + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$2446 := \frac{(aaaa + aaa + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$22446 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaa + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$222446 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aaa + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$447 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times (a + a + a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$4447 := \frac{(aaaa + a) \times (a + a + a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$44447 := \frac{(aaaaa + a) \times (a + a + a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$444447 := \frac{(aaaaaa + a) \times (a + a + a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$448 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times (a + a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$4448 := \frac{(aaaa + a) \times (a + a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$44448 := \frac{(aaaaa + a) \times (a + a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$444448 := \frac{(aaaaaa + a) \times (a + a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$449 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times (a + a + a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$4449 := \frac{(aaaa + a) \times (a + a + a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$44449 := \frac{(aaaaa + a) \times (a + a + a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$444449 := \frac{(aaaaaa + a) \times (a + a + a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$450 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa + aa}{a + a}$$

$$5450 := \frac{aaaaa - aaa - aaa + aa}{a + a}$$

$$55450 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaa - aaa + aa}{a + a}$$

$$555450 := \frac{aaaaaaaa - aaa - aaa + aa}{a + a}$$

$$451 := \frac{(aaa + aa + a) \times aa}{((a + a + a) \times a)}$$

$$4551 := \frac{(aaa + aa + a) \times aaa}{((a + a + a) \times a)}$$

$$45551 := \frac{(aaa + aa + a) \times aaaa}{((a + a + a) \times a)}$$

$$455551 := \frac{(aaa + aa + a) \times aaaaa}{((a + a + a) \times a)}$$

$$452 := \frac{(aaa + a + a) \times (a + a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$4452 := \frac{(aaaa + a + a) \times (a + a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$44452 := \frac{(aaaaa + a + a) \times (a + a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$444452 := \frac{(aaaaaa + a + a) \times (a + a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$453 := \frac{aaa \times (a + a + a) + aa \times aa - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$3453 := \frac{aaaa \times (a + a + a) + aa \times aa - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$33453 := \frac{aaaaa \times (a + a + a) + aa \times aa - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$333453 := \frac{aaaaaa \times (a + a + a) + aa \times aa - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$454 := \frac{aaa \times (a + a + a) + aa \times aa}{a \times a}$$

$$3454 := \frac{aaaa \times (a + a + a) + aa \times aa}{a \times a}$$

$$33454 := \frac{aaaaa \times (a + a + a) + aa \times aa}{a \times a}$$

$$333454 := \frac{aaaaaa \times (a + a + a) + aa \times aa}{a \times a}$$

$$455 := \frac{(a + a + a + a) \times aaa + aa \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$4455 := \frac{(a + a + a + a) \times aaaa + aa \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$44455 := \frac{(a + a + a + a) \times aaaaa + aa \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$444455 := \frac{(a + a + a + a) \times aaaaaa + aa \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$456 := \frac{(a + a + a + a) \times aaa + (aa + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$4456 := \frac{(a + a + a + a) \times aaaa + (aa + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$44456 := \frac{(a + a + a + a) \times aaaaa + (aa + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$444456 := \frac{(a + a + a + a) \times aaaaaa + (aa + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$457 := \frac{(a + a + a + a) \times aaa + (aa + a + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$4457 := \frac{(a + a + a + a) \times aaaa + (aa + a + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$44457 := \frac{(a + a + a + a) \times aaaaa + (aa + a + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$444457 := \frac{(a + a + a + a) \times aaaaaa + (aa + a + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$458 := \frac{(aaa + aaa + a) \times (aa + aa) + (aa + a) \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$2458 := \frac{(aaaa + aaa + a) \times (aa + aa) + (aa + a) \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$22458 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaa + a) \times (aa + aa) + (aa + a) \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$222458 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aaa + a) \times (aa + aa) + (aa + a) \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$459 := \frac{(aaaa + aa) \times (aa - a - a)}{(a + a) \times aa}$$

$$45459 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aa) \times (aa - a - a)}{(a + a) \times aa}$$

$$4545459 := \frac{(aaaaaaaa + aa) \times (aa - a - a)}{(a + a) \times aa}$$

$$454545459 := \frac{(aaaaaaaaaa + aa) \times (aa - a - a)}{(a + a) \times aa}$$

$$460 := \frac{aaaa \times (aa - a - a) + aa \times aa}{(a + a) \times aa}$$

$$45460 := \frac{aaaaaa \times (aa - a - a) + aa \times aa}{(a + a) \times aa}$$

$$4545460 := \frac{aaaaaaaa \times (aa - a - a) + aa \times aa}{(a + a) \times aa}$$

$$454545460 := \frac{aaaaaaaaaa \times (aa - a - a) + aa \times aa}{(a + a) \times aa}$$

$$461 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa + aa + aa + aa}{a + a}$$

$$5461 := \frac{aaaaa - aaa - aaa + aa + aa + aa}{a + a}$$

$$55461 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaa - aaa + aa + aa + aa}{a + a}$$

$$555461 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaa - aaa + aa + aa + aa}{a + a}$$

$$462 := \frac{aa + a + a + a) \times (aa + aa + aa)}{a \times a}$$

$$4662 := \frac{aa + a + a + a) \times (aaa + aaa + aaa)}{a \times a}$$

$$46662 := \frac{aa + a + a + a) \times (aaaa + aaaa + aaaa)}{a \times a}$$

$$466662 := \frac{aa + a + a + a) \times (aaaaa + aaaaa + aaaaa)}{a \times a}$$

$$463 := \frac{(aa + a + a + a) \times (aa + aa + aa) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$4663 := \frac{(aa + a + a + a) \times (aaa + aaa + aaa) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$46663 := \frac{(aa + a + a + a) \times (aaaa + aaaa + aaaa) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$466663 := \frac{(aa + a + a + a) \times (aaaaa + aaaaa + aaaaa) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$464 := \frac{(aaa + aaa + aa - a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$2464 := \frac{(aaaa + aaa + aa - a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$22464 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaa + aa - a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$222464 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aaa + aa - a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$465 := \frac{(aaa + aaa + aa) \times (a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$2465 := \frac{(aaaa + aaa + aa) \times (a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$22465 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaa + aa) \times (a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$222465 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aaa + aa) \times (a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$466 := \frac{(aaa + aaa + aa) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$2466 := \frac{(aaaa + aaa + aa) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$22466 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaa + aa) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$222466 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aaa + aa) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$467 := \frac{(aaa + aaa + aa) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$2467 := \frac{(aaaa + aaa + aa) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$22467 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaa + aa) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$222467 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aaa + aa) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$468 := \frac{(aaa + aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$2468 := \frac{(aaaa + aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$22468 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$222468 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$469 := \frac{(aaa + aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$2469 := \frac{(aaaa + aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$22469 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$222469 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$470 := \frac{(aaa + aaa + aa + a + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$2470 := \frac{(aaaa + aaa + aa + a + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$22470 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaa + aa + a + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$222470 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aaa + aa + a + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$471 := \frac{aaaa - a}{a + a + a} + \frac{aaaa}{aa}$$

$$10471 := \frac{aaaa - a}{a + a + a} + \frac{aaaaaa}{aa}$$

$$1010471 := \frac{aaaa - a}{a + a + a} + \frac{aaaaaaaa}{aa}$$

$$101010471 := \frac{aaaa - a}{a + a + a} + \frac{aaaaaaaaaa}{aa}$$

$$472 := \frac{(aaa + aaa + aa + a + a + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$2472 := \frac{(aaaa + aaa + aa + a + a + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$22472 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaa + aa + a + a + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$222472 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aaa + aa + a + a + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$473 := \frac{(aa + aa) \times (aa + aa) - aa \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$4873 := \frac{(aaa + aaa) \times (aa + aa) - aa \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$48873 := \frac{(aaaa + aaaa) \times (aa + aa) - aa \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$488873 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaaaa) \times (aa + aa) - aa \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$474 := \frac{(aaa + aaa + aa + a + a + a + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$2474 := \frac{(aaaa + aaa + aa + a + a + a + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$22474 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaa + aa + a + a + a + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$222474 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aaa + aa + a + a + a + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$475 := \frac{(aaa + aaa + aa - a) \times (a + a) + aa \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$2475 := \frac{(aaaa + aaa + aa - a) \times (a + a) + aa \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$22475 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaa + aa - a) \times (a + a) + aa \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$222475 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aaa + aa - a) \times (a + a) + aa \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$476 := \frac{(aa + a + a + a) \times (aa + aa + aa + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$4676 := \frac{(aa + a + a + a) \times (aaa + aaa + aaa + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$46676 := \frac{(aa + a + a + a) \times (aaaa + aaaa + aaaa + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$466676 := \frac{(aa + a + a + a) \times (aaaaa + aaaaa + aaaaa + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$477 := \frac{(aaa + aaa + aa) \times (a + a) + a \times aa}{a \times a}$$

$$2477 := \frac{(aaaa + aaa + aa) \times (a + a) + a \times aa}{a \times a}$$

$$22477 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaa + aa) \times (a + a) + a \times aa}{a \times a}$$

$$222477 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aaa + aa) \times (a + a) + a \times aa}{a \times a}$$

$$478 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aa - aa - aa - aa}{a + a}$$

$$5478 := \frac{aaaaa - aaa - aa - aa - aa - aa}{a + a}$$

$$55478 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaa - aa - aa - aa - aa}{a + a}$$

$$555478 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaa - aa - aa - aa - aa}{a + a}$$

$$479 := \frac{(aaa + aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a) + a \times aa}{a \times a}$$

$$2479 := \frac{(aaaa + aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a) + a \times aa}{a \times a}$$

$$22479 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a) + a \times aa}{a \times a}$$

$$222479 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a) + a \times aa}{a \times a}$$

$$480 := \frac{(aaa + aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a) + a \times (aa + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$2480 := \frac{(aaaa + aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a) + a \times (aa + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$22480 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a) + a \times (aa + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$222480 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a) + a \times (aa + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$481 := \frac{(aa + a + a) \times aaa}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$4181 := \frac{(aaa + a + a) \times aaa}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$41181 := \frac{(aaaa + a + a) \times aaa}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$411181 := \frac{(aaaaa + a + a) \times aaa}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$482 := \frac{(aa + aa) \times (aa + aa) - a \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$4882 := \frac{(aaa + aaa) \times (aa + aa) - a \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$48882 := \frac{(aaaa + aaaa) \times (aa + aa) - a \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$488882 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaaaa) \times (aa + aa) - a \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$483 := \frac{(aa + aa) \times (aa + aa) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$4883 := \frac{(aaa + aaa) \times (aa + aa) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$48883 := \frac{(aaaa + aaaa) \times (aa + aa) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$488883 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaaaa) \times (aa + aa) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$484 := \frac{(aa + aa) \times (aa + aa)}{a \times a}$$

$$4884 := \frac{(aaa + aaa) \times (aa + aa)}{a \times a}$$

$$48884 := \frac{(aaaa + aaaa) \times (aa + aa)}{a \times a}$$

$$488884 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaaaa) \times (aa + aa)}{a \times a}$$

$$485 := \frac{(aa + aa) \times (aa + aa) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$4885 := \frac{(aaa + aaa) \times (aa + aa) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$48885 := \frac{(aaaa + aaaa) \times (aa + aa) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$488885 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaaaa) \times (aa + aa) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$486 := \frac{(aa + aa) \times (aa + aa) + a \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$4886 := \frac{(aaa + aaa) \times (aa + aa) + a \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$48886 := \frac{(aaaa + aaaa) \times (aa + aa) + a \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$488886 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaaaa) \times (aa + aa) + a \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$487 := \frac{(aa + aa) \times (aa + aa) + a \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$4887 := \frac{(aaa + aaa) \times (aa + aa) + a \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$48887 := \frac{(aaaa + aaaa) \times (aa + aa) + a \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$488887 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaaaa) \times (aa + aa) + a \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$488 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aa - aa - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$5488 := \frac{aaaaa - aaa - aa - aa - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$55488 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaa - aa - aa - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$555488 := \frac{aaaaaaaa - aaa - aa - aa - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$489 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aa - aa}{a + a}$$

$$5489 := \frac{aaaaa - aaa - aa - aa}{a + a}$$

$$55489 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaa - aa - aa}{a + a}$$

$$555489 := \frac{aaaaaaaa - aaa - aa - aa}{a + a}$$

$$490 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aa - aa + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$5490 := \frac{aaaaa - aaa - aa - aa + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$55490 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaa - aa - aa + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$555490 := \frac{aaaaaaaa - aaa - aa - aa + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$491 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aa - aa + a + a + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$5491 := \frac{aaaaa - aaa - aa - aa + a + a + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$55491 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaa - aa - aa + a + a + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$555491 := \frac{aaaaaaaa - aaa - aa - aa + a + a + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$492 := \frac{(aaa + aa + a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$4492 := \frac{(aaaa + aa + a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$44492 := \frac{(aaaaa + aa + a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$444492 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aa + a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$493 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aa - a - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$4993 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - aa - a - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$49993 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaaa - aa - a - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$499993 := \frac{aaaaaaaa - aaaaaa - aa - a - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$494 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aa - a}{a + a}$$

$$5494 := \frac{aaaaa - aaa - aa - a}{a + a}$$

$$55494 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaa - aa - a}{a + a}$$

$$555494 := \frac{aaaaaaaa - aaa - aa - a}{a + a}$$

$$495 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aa + a}{a + a}$$

$$5495 := \frac{aaaaa - aaa - aa + a}{a + a}$$

$$55495 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaa - aa + a}{a + a}$$

$$555495 := \frac{aaaaaaaa - aaa - aa + a}{a + a}$$

$$496 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aa + a + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$5496 := \frac{aaaaa - aaa - aa + a + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$55496 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaa - aa + a + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$555496 := \frac{aaaaaaaa - aaa - aa + a + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$497 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - a - a - a - a - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$4997 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - a - a - a - a - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$49997 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaaa - a - a - a - a - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$499997 := \frac{aaaaaaaa - aaaaaa - a - a - a - a - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$498 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - a - a - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$4998 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - a - a - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$49998 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa - a - a - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$499998 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaaaa - a - a - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$499 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$4999 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$49999 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$499999 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaaaa - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$500 := \frac{aaaa - aaa}{a + a}$$

$$5000 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa}{a + a}$$

$$50000 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa}{a + a}$$

$$500000 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaaaa}{a + a}$$

$$501 := \frac{aaaa - aaa + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$5001 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$50001 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$500001 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaaaa + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$502 := \frac{aaaa - aaa + a + a + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$5002 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa + a + a + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$50002 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa + a + a + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$500002 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaaaa + a + a + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$503 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times (aa - a - a) - a \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$5003 := \frac{(aaaa + a) \times (aa - a - a) - a \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$50003 := \frac{(aaaaa + a) \times (aa - a - a) - a \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$500003 := \frac{(aaaaaa + a) \times (aa - a - a) - a \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$504 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times (aa - a - a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$5004 := \frac{(aaaa + a) \times (aa - a - a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$50004 := \frac{(aaaaa + a) \times (aa - a - a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$500004 := \frac{(aaaaaa + a) \times (aa - a - a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$505 := \frac{aaaaa - a}{aa + aa}$$

$$50505 := \frac{aaaaaaa - a}{aa + aa}$$

$$5050505 := \frac{aaaaaaaaa - a}{aa + aa}$$

$$505050505 := \frac{aaaaaaaaaaa - a}{aa + aa}$$

$$506 := \frac{aaaa - aaa + aa + a}{a + a}$$

$$5506 := \frac{aaaaa - aaa + aa + a}{a + a}$$

$$55506 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaa + aa + a}{a + a}$$

$$555506 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaa + aa + a}{a + a}$$

$$507 := \frac{aaaa - aaa + aa + a + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$5507 := \frac{aaaaa - aaa + aa + a + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$55507 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaa + aa + a + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$555507 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaa + aa + a + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$508 := \frac{aaaa - aaa + aa + a + a + a + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$5508 := \frac{aaaaa - aaa + aa + a + a + a + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$55508 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaa + aa + a + a + a + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$555508 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaa + aa + a + a + a + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$509 := \frac{aaaa - aaa}{a + a} + \frac{aa - a - a}{a}$$

$$5109 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa}{a + a} + \frac{aaa - a - a}{a}$$

$$51109 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa - a - a}{a}$$

$$511109 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaaaa}{a + a} + \frac{aaaaa - a - a}{a}$$

$$510 := \frac{aaaa - aaa}{a + a} + \frac{aa - a}{a}$$

$$5110 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa}{a + a} + \frac{aaa - a}{a}$$

$$51110 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa - a}{a}$$

$$511110 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaaaa}{a + a} + \frac{aaaaa - a}{a}$$

$$511 := \frac{aaaa - aaa}{a + a} + \frac{aa}{a}$$

$$5111 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa}{a + a} + \frac{aaa}{a}$$

$$51111 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa}{a}$$

$$511111 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaaaa}{a + a} + \frac{aaaaa}{a}$$

$$512 := \frac{aaaa - aaa + aa + aa + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$5512 := \frac{aaaaa - aaa + aa + aa + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$55512 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaa + aa + aa + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$555512 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaa + aa + aa + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$513 := \frac{aaaa - aaa}{a + a} + \frac{aa + a + a}{a}$$

$$5113 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa}{a + a} + \frac{aaa + a + a}{a}$$

$$51113 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa + a + a}{a}$$

$$511113 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaaaa}{a + a} + \frac{aaaaa + a + a}{a}$$

$$514 := \frac{aaaa - aaa}{a + a} + \frac{aa + a + a + a}{a}$$

$$5114 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa}{a + a} + \frac{aaa + a + a + a}{a}$$

$$51114 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa + a + a + a}{a}$$

$$511114 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaaaa}{a + a} + \frac{aaaaa + a + a + a}{a}$$

$$515 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times (aa - a - a) + (a + a) \times aa}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$5015 := \frac{(aaaa + a) \times (aa - a - a) + (a + a) \times aa}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$50015 := \frac{(aaaaa + a) \times (aa - a - a) + (a + a) \times aa}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$500015 := \frac{(aaaaaa + a) \times (aa - a - a) + (a + a) \times aa}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$516 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times (aa - a - a) + (a + a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$5016 := \frac{(aaaa + a) \times (aa - a - a) + (a + a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$50016 := \frac{(aaaaa + a) \times (aa - a - a) + (a + a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$500016 := \frac{(aaaaaa + a) \times (aa - a - a) + (a + a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$517 := \frac{aaaa - aaa + aa + aa + aa + a}{a + a}$$

$$5517 := \frac{aaaaa - aaa + aa + aa + aa + a}{a + a}$$

$$55517 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaa + aa + aa + aa + a}{a + a}$$

$$555517 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaa + aa + aa + aa + a}{a + a}$$

$$518 := \frac{aaa \times aa + aaa \times (a + a + a)}{a \times (a + a + a)}$$

$$1518 := \frac{aaa \times aa + aaaa \times (a + a + a)}{a \times (a + a + a)}$$

$$11518 := \frac{aaa \times aa + aaaaa \times (a + a + a)}{a \times (a + a + a)}$$

$$111518 := \frac{aaa \times aa + aaaaaa \times (a + a + a)}{a \times (a + a + a)}$$

$$519 := \frac{aaa \times aa + (aaa + a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times (a + a + a)}$$

$$1519 := \frac{aaa \times aa + (aaaa + a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times (a + a + a)}$$

$$11519 := \frac{aaa \times aa + (aaaaa + a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times (a + a + a)}$$

$$111519 := \frac{aaa \times aa + (aaaaaa + a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times (a + a + a)}$$

$$520 := \frac{aaa \times aa + (aaa + a + a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times (a + a + a)}$$

$$5220 := \frac{aaa \times aaa + (aaaa + a + a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times (a + a + a)}$$

$$52220 := \frac{aaa \times aaaa + (aaaaa + a + a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times (a + a + a)}$$

$$522220 := \frac{aaa \times aaaaa + (aaaaaa + a + a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times (a + a + a)}$$

$$521 := \frac{aaaa - aaa + aa + aa + aa + aa - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$5521 := \frac{aaaaa - aaa + aa + aa + aa + aa - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$55521 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaa + aa + aa + aa + aa - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$555521 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaa + aa + aa + aa + aa - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$522 := \frac{aaaa - aaa + aa + aa + aa + aa}{a + a}$$

$$5522 := \frac{aaaaa - aaa + aa + aa + aa + aa}{a + a}$$

$$55522 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaa + aa + aa + aa + aa}{a + a}$$

$$555522 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaa + aa + aa + aa + aa}{a + a}$$

$$523 := \frac{aaaa - aaa + aa + aa + aa + aa + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$5523 := \frac{aaaaa - aaa + aa + aa + aa + aa + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$55523 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaa + aa + aa + aa + aa + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$555523 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaa + aa + aa + aa + aa + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$524 := \frac{aaaa + aa}{a + a} - \frac{aaa}{a + a + a}$$

$$5524 := \frac{aaaaa + aa}{a + a} - \frac{aaa}{a + a + a}$$

$$55524 := \frac{aaaaaa + aa}{a + a} - \frac{aaa}{a + a + a}$$

$$555524 := \frac{aaaaaaa + aa}{a + a} - \frac{aaa}{a + a + a}$$

$$525 := \frac{(aa + aa + a + a + a) \times (aa + aa - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$5525 := \frac{(aa + aa + a + a + a) \times (aaa + aaa - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$55525 := \frac{(aa + aa + a + a + a) \times (aaaa + aaaa - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$555525 := \frac{(aa + aa + a + a + a) \times (aaaaa + aaaaa - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$526 := \frac{(aa + aa + a + a + a) \times (aa + aa - a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$5526 := \frac{(aa + aa + a + a + a) \times (aaa + aaa - a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$55526 := \frac{(aa + aa + a + a + a) \times (aaaa + aaaa - a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$555526 := \frac{(aa + aa + a + a + a) \times (aaaaa + aaaaa - a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$527 := \frac{(aa + aa + aa + aa) \times (aa + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$5327 := \frac{(aaa + aaa + aaa + aaa) \times (aa + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$53327 := \frac{(aaaa + aaaa + aaaa + aaaa) \times (aa + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$533327 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaaaa + aaaaa + aaaaa) \times (aa + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$528 := \frac{(aa + aa + aa + aa) \times (aa + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$5328 := \frac{(aaa + aaa + aaa + aaa) \times (aa + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$53328 := \frac{(aaaa + aaaa + aaaa + aaaa) \times (aa + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$533328 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaaaa + aaaaa + aaaaa) \times (aa + a)}{a \times a}$$

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$$51129 := \frac{(aaaa + aaaa + a) \times (aa + aa + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$511129 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaaaa + a) \times (aa + aa + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$530 := \frac{(aa + aa + a) \times (aa + aa + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$5130 := \frac{(aaa + aaa + a) \times (aa + aa + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$51130 := \frac{(aaaa + aaaa + a) \times (aa + aa + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$511130 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaaaa + a) \times (aa + aa + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$531 := \frac{(aa + aa + a) \times (aa + aa + a) + a \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$5131 := \frac{(aaa + aaa + a) \times (aa + aa + a) + a \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$51131 := \frac{(aaaa + aaaa + a) \times (aa + aa + a) + a \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$511131 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaaaa + a) \times (aa + aa + a) + a \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$532 := \frac{(aaa + aa + aa) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$4532 := \frac{(aaaa + aa + aa) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$44532 := \frac{(aaaaa + aa + aa) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$444532 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aa + aa) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

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$$5343 := \frac{(aaaa + aaa + aa) \times (aa + a + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$53443 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaaa + aaa) \times (aa + a + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$534443 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aaaaa + aaaa) \times (aa + a + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

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$$5434 := \frac{aaaaa - aa - aa - aa - aa + a}{a + a}$$

$$55534 := \frac{aaaaaa - aa - aa - aa - aa + a}{a + a}$$

$$555534 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aa - aa - aa - aa + a}{a + a}$$

$$535 := \frac{(aaa - a - a - a - a) \times (aaa - a)}{(aa + aa) \times a}$$

$$5535 := \frac{(aaaa - a - a - a - a) \times (aaa - a)}{(aa + aa) \times a}$$

$$55535 := \frac{(aaaaa - a - a - a - a) \times (aaa - a)}{(aa + aa) \times a}$$

$$555535 := \frac{(aaaaaa - a - a - a - a) \times (aaa - a)}{(aa + aa) \times a}$$

$$536 := \frac{(aaa + aa + aa + a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

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$$44536 := \frac{(aaaaa + aa + aa + a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$444536 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aa + aa + a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

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$$555537 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aa - aa - aa - a - a - a - a}{a + a}$$

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$$55538 := \frac{aaaaaa - aa - aa - aa - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$555538 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aa - aa - aa - a - a}{a + a}$$

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$$55539 := \frac{aaaaaa - aa - aa - aa}{a + a}$$

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$$553 := \frac{aaaa - a}{a + a} - \frac{a + a}{a}$$

$$5553 := \frac{aaaaa - a}{a + a} - \frac{a + a}{a}$$

$$55553 := \frac{aaaaaa - a}{a + a} - \frac{a + a}{a}$$

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$$555554 := \frac{a \times (aaaaaaa - a - a - a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

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$$555555 := \frac{aaaaaaa - a}{a + a}$$

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$$555556 := \frac{aaaaaaa + a}{a + a}$$

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$$55560 := \frac{aaaaaa + aa - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$555560 := \frac{aaaaaaa + aa - a - a}{a + a}$$

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$$6565 := \frac{(aaaa + a + a) \times (aa - a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$66565 := \frac{(aaaaa + a + a) \times (aa - a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$666565 := \frac{(aaaaaa + a + a) \times (aa - a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

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$$575554 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aaaaa + aaaa) \times (aaa + a)}{(aa + a) \times (a + a)}$$

$$575 := \frac{(aaa - aa) \times (aa + aa + a)}{(a + a + a + a) \times a}$$

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$$583 := \frac{aaa + a}{a + a + a + a} + \frac{aaaa - a}{a + a}$$

$$5583 := \frac{aaa + a}{a + a + a + a} + \frac{aaaaa - a}{a + a}$$

$$55583 := \frac{aaa + a}{a + a + a + a} + \frac{aaaaaa - a}{a + a}$$

$$555583 := \frac{aaa + a}{a + a + a + a} + \frac{aaaaaaa - a}{a + a}$$

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$$5584 := \frac{aaa + a}{a + a + a + a} + \frac{aaaaa + a}{a + a}$$

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$$555584 := \frac{aaa + a}{a + a + a + a} + \frac{aaaaaaa + a}{a + a}$$

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$$5585 := \frac{(aaaa + aaaa + aa + a) \times (aa - a)}{(a + a) \times (a + a)}$$

$$55585 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaaaa + aa + a) \times (aa - a)}{(a + a) \times (a + a)}$$

$$555585 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aaaaaa + aa + a) \times (aa - a)}{(a + a) \times (a + a)}$$

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$$588886 := \frac{(aa + aa + a) \times aaaaa + aaaaaa \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$587 := \frac{aaaa - aa}{a + a} + \frac{aaa}{a + a + a}$$

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$$66589 := \frac{(aaaaa - aa) \times (aa + a) - aa \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$666589 := \frac{(aaaaaa - aa) \times (aa + a) - aa \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$590 := \frac{(aaa - aa) \times (aa + a) - (aa - a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$6590 := \frac{(aaaa - aa) \times (aa + a) - (aa - a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$66590 := \frac{(aaaaa - aa) \times (aa + a) - (aa - a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$666590 := \frac{(aaaaaa - aa) \times (aa + a) - (aa - a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$591 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times aaa - a \times (aa + aa - a)}{a \times (aa + aa - a)}$$

$$592591 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times aaaaa - a \times (aa + aa - a)}{a \times (aa + aa - a)}$$

$$592592591 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times aaaaaaaaa - a \times (aa + aa - a)}{a \times (aa + aa - a)}$$

$$592592592591 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times aaaaaaaaaaa - a \times (aa + aa - a)}{a \times (aa + aa - a)}$$

$$592 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times aaa}{(aa + aa - a) \times a}$$

$$592592 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times aaaaaa}{(aa + aa - a) \times a}$$

$$592592592 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times aaaaaaaaa}{(aa + aa - a) \times a}$$

$$592592592592 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times aaaaaaaaaaa}{(aa + aa - a) \times a}$$

$$593 := \frac{(aaa - a - a) \times aa - a \times (aa + a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$5983 := \frac{(aaaa - aa - aa) \times aa - a \times (aa + a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$59883 := \frac{(aaaaa - aaa - aaa) \times aa - a \times (aa + a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$598883 := \frac{(aaaaaa - aaaa - aaaa) \times aa - a \times (aa + a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$594 := \frac{(aaa - a - a) \times aa - a \times aa}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$5984 := \frac{(aaaa - aa - aa) \times aa - a \times aa}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$59884 := \frac{(aaaaa - aaa - aaa) \times aa - a \times aa}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$598884 := \frac{(aaaaaa - aaaa - aaaa) \times aa - a \times aa}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$595 := \frac{(aaa - a - a) \times aa - a \times (aa - a - a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$5985 := \frac{(aaaa - aa - aa) \times aa - a \times (aa - a - a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$59885 := \frac{(aaaaa - aaa - aaa) \times aa - a \times (aa - a - a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$598885 := \frac{(aaaaaa - aaaa - aaaa) \times aa - a \times (aa - a - a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$596 := \frac{aaaa \times (aa + a) - (aa - a) \times (aa + aa)}{a \times (aa + aa)}$$

$$60596 := \frac{aaaaaa \times (aa + a) - (aa - a) \times (aa + aa)}{a \times (aa + aa)}$$

$$6060596 := \frac{aaaaaaaa \times (aa + a) - (aa - a) \times (aa + aa)}{a \times (aa + aa)}$$

$$606060596 := \frac{aaaaaaaaaa \times (aa + a) - (aa - a) \times (aa + aa)}{a \times (aa + aa)}$$

$$597 := \frac{(aaa - aa) \times (aa + a) - (a + a) \times (a + a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$6597 := \frac{(aaaa - aa) \times (aa + a) - (a + a) \times (a + a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$66597 := \frac{(aaaaa - aa) \times (aa + a) - (a + a) \times (a + a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$666597 := \frac{(aaaaaa - aa) \times (aa + a) - (a + a) \times (a + a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$598 := \frac{(aaa - aa) \times (aa + a) - (a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$6598 := \frac{(aaaa - aa) \times (aa + a) - (a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$66598 := \frac{(aaaaa - aa) \times (aa + a) - (a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$666598 := \frac{(aaaaaa - aa) \times (aa + a) - (a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$599 := \frac{(aaa - a - a) \times aa - a \times a}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$5989 := \frac{(aaaa - aa - aa) \times aa - a \times a}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$59889 := \frac{(aaaaa - aaa - aaa) \times aa - a \times a}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$598889 := \frac{(aaaaaa - aaaa - aaaa) \times aa - a \times a}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$600 := \frac{aaaa + aaa + a + a}{a + a} - \frac{aa + a}{a}$$

$$6100 := \frac{aaaaa + aaaa + a + a}{a + a} - \frac{aa + a}{a}$$

$$61100 := \frac{aaaaaa + aaaaa + a + a}{a + a} - \frac{aa + a}{a}$$

$$611100 := \frac{aaaaaaa + aaaaaa + a + a}{a + a} - \frac{aa + a}{a}$$

$$601 := \frac{aaaa + aaa + a + a}{a + a} - \frac{aa}{a}$$

$$6101 := \frac{aaaaa + aaaa + a + a}{a + a} - \frac{aa}{a}$$

$$61101 := \frac{aaaaaa + aaaaa + a + a}{a + a} - \frac{aa}{a}$$

$$611101 := \frac{aaaaaaa + aaaaaa + a + a}{a + a} - \frac{aa}{a}$$

$$602 := \frac{aaaa + aaa + a + a}{a + a} - \frac{aa - a}{a}$$

$$6102 := \frac{aaaaa + aaaa + a + a}{a + a} - \frac{aa - a}{a}$$

$$61102 := \frac{aaaaaa + aaaaa + a + a}{a + a} - \frac{aa - a}{a}$$

$$611102 := \frac{aaaaaaa + aaaaaa + a + a}{a + a} - \frac{aa - a}{a}$$

$$603 := \frac{(aaa - a) \times aa - (a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$6103 := \frac{(aaaa - a) \times aa - (a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$61103 := \frac{(aaaaa - a) \times aa - (a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$611103 := \frac{(aaaaaa - a) \times aa - (a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$604 := \frac{(aaa - a) \times aa - (a + a) \times a}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$6104 := \frac{(aaaa - a) \times aa - (a + a) \times a}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$61104 := \frac{(aaaaa - a) \times aa - (a + a) \times a}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$611104 := \frac{(aaaaaa - a) \times aa - (a + a) \times a}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$605 := \frac{(aaa - a) \times aa}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$6105 := \frac{(aaa - a) \times aaa}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$61105 := \frac{(aaa - a) \times aaaa}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$611105 := \frac{(aaa - a) \times aaaaa}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$606 := \frac{(aaa - a) \times aa + (a + a) \times a}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$6106 := \frac{(aaaa - a) \times aa + (a + a) \times a}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$61106 := \frac{(aaaaa - a) \times aa + (a + a) \times a}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$611106 := \frac{(aaaaaa - a) \times aa + (a + a) \times a}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$607 := \frac{(aaa - a) \times aa + (a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$6107 := \frac{(aaa - a) \times aaa + (a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$61107 := \frac{(aaa - a) \times aaaa + (a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$611107 := \frac{(aaa - a) \times aaaaa + (a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$608 := \frac{aaaa + aaa - a - a - a - a - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$6108 := \frac{aaaaa + aaaa - a - a - a - a - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$61108 := \frac{aaaaaa + aaaaa - a - a - a - a - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$611108 := \frac{aaaaaaa + aaaaaa - a - a - a - a - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$609 := \frac{aaaa + aaa - a - a - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$6109 := \frac{aaaaa + aaaa - a - a - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$61109 := \frac{aaaaaa + aaaaa - a - a - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$611109 := \frac{aaaaaaa + aaaaaa - a - a - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$610 := \frac{aaaa + aaa - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$6110 := \frac{aaaaa + aaaa - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$61110 := \frac{aaaaaa + aaaaa - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$611110 := \frac{aaaaaaa + aaaaaa - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$611 := \frac{aaaa + aaa}{a + a}$$

$$6111 := \frac{aaaaa + aaaa}{a + a}$$

$$61111 := \frac{aaaaaa + aaaaa}{a + a}$$

$$611111 := \frac{aaaaaaa + aaaaaa}{a + a}$$

$$612 := \frac{aaaa + aaa + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$6112 := \frac{aaaaa + aaaa + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$61112 := \frac{aaaaaa + aaaaa + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$611112 := \frac{aaaaaaa + aaaaaa + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$613 := \frac{aaaa + aaa + a + a + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$6113 := \frac{aaaaa + aaaa + a + a + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$61113 := \frac{aaaaaa + aaaaa + a + a + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$611113 := \frac{aaaaaaa + aaaaaa + a + a + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$614 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times aa - (a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$6114 := \frac{(aaaa + a) \times aa - (a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$61114 := \frac{(aaaaa + a) \times aa - (a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$611114 := \frac{(aaaaaa + a) \times aa - (a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$615 := \frac{aaaa + aa + aaa - a - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$5615 := \frac{aaaaa + aa + aaa - a - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$55615 := \frac{aaaaaa + aa + aaa - a - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$555615 := \frac{aaaaaaa + aa + aaa - a - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$616 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times aa}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$6216 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times aaa}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$62216 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times aaaa}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$622216 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times aaaaa}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$617 := \frac{aaaa + aa + aaa + a}{a + a}$$

$$5617 := \frac{aaaaa + aa + aaa + a}{a + a}$$

$$55617 := \frac{aaaaaa + aa + aaa + a}{a + a}$$

$$555617 := \frac{aaaaaaa + aa + aaa + a}{a + a}$$

$$618 := \frac{aaaa + aa + aaa + a + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$5618 := \frac{aaaaa + aa + aaa + a + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$55618 := \frac{aaaaaa + aa + aaa + a + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$555618 := \frac{aaaaaaa + aa + aaa + a + a + a}{a + a}$$

$$619 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times aa + (a + a) \times (a + a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$6219 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times aaa + (a + a) \times (a + a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$62219 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times aaaa + (a + a) \times (a + a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$622219 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times aaaaa + (a + a) \times (a + a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$620 := \frac{aaaa + aa + aaa + aa - a - a - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$5620 := \frac{aaaaa + aa + aaa + aa - a - a - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$55620 := \frac{aaaaaa + aa + aaa + aa - a - a - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$555620 := \frac{aaaaaaa + aa + aaa + aa - a - a - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$621 := \frac{aaaa + aa + aaa + aa - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$5621 := \frac{aaaaa + aa + aaa + aa - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$55621 := \frac{aaaaaa + aa + aaa + aa - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$555621 := \frac{aaaaaaa + aa + aaa + aa - a - a}{a + a}$$

$$622 := \frac{aaaa + aaa + a + a}{a + a} + \frac{aa - a}{a}$$

$$6122 := \frac{aaaaa + aaaa + a + a}{a + a} + \frac{aa - a}{a}$$

$$61122 := \frac{aaaaaa + aaaaa + a + a}{a + a} + \frac{aa - a}{a}$$

$$611122 := \frac{aaaaaaa + aaaaaa + a + a}{a + a} + \frac{aa - a}{a}$$

$$623 := \frac{aaaa + aaa + a + a}{a + a} + \frac{aa}{a}$$

$$6123 := \frac{aaaaa + aaaa + a + a}{a + a} + \frac{aa}{a}$$

$$61123 := \frac{aaaaaa + aaaaa + a + a}{a + a} + \frac{aa}{a}$$

$$611123 := \frac{aaaaaaa + aaaaaa + a + a}{a + a} + \frac{aa}{a}$$

$$624 := \frac{aaaa + aaa + a + a}{a + a} + \frac{aa + a}{a}$$

$$6124 := \frac{aaaaa + aaaa + a + a}{a + a} + \frac{aa + a}{a}$$

$$61124 := \frac{aaaaaa + aaaaa + a + a}{a + a} + \frac{aa + a}{a}$$

$$611124 := \frac{aaaaaaa + aaaaaa + a + a}{a + a} + \frac{aa + a}{a}$$

$$625 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times aa + (aa - a - a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$6225 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times aaa + (aa - a - a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$62225 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times aaaa + (aa - a - a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$622225 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times aaaaa + (aa - a - a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$626 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times aa + (aa - a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$6226 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times aaa + (aa - a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$62226 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times aaaa + (aa - a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$622226 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times aaaaa + (aa - a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$627 := \frac{(aaa + a + a + a) \times aa}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$6127 := \frac{(aaaa + a + a + a) \times aa}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$61127 := \frac{(aaaaa + a + a + a) \times aa}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$611127 := \frac{(aaaaaa + a + a + a) \times aa}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$628 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times aa + (a + a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$6228 := \frac{(aaaa + a) \times aa + (a + a) \times (aaa + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$62228 := \frac{(aaaaa + a) \times aa + (a + a) \times (aaaa + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$622228 := \frac{(aaaaaa + a) \times aa + (a + a) \times (aaaaa + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$629 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times aa + (a + a) \times (aa + a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$6329 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times aaa + (a + a) \times (aaa + a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$63329 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times aaaa + (a + a) \times (aaaa + a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$633329 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times aaaaa + (a + a) \times (aaaaa + a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$630 := \frac{(aaa + aaa - aa - a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$3630 := \frac{(aaaa + aaa - aa - a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$33630 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaa - aa - a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$333630 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aaa - aa - a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$631 := \frac{(aaa + aaa - aa - a) \times (a + a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$3631 := \frac{(aaaa + aaa - aa - a) \times (a + a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$33631 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaa - aa - a) \times (a + a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$333631 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aaa - aa - a) \times (a + a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$632 := \frac{(aaa + aaa - aa) \times (a + a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$3632 := \frac{(aaaa + aaa - aa) \times (a + a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$33632 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaa - aa) \times (a + a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$333632 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aaa - aa) \times (a + a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$633 := \frac{(aaa + aaa - aa) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$3633 := \frac{(aaaa + aaa - aa) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$33633 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaa - aa) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$333633 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aaa - aa) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$634 := \frac{(aaa + aaa - aa) \times (a + a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$3634 := \frac{(aaaa + aaa - aa) \times (a + a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$33634 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaa - aa) \times (a + a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$333634 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aaa - aa) \times (a + a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$635 := \frac{(aaa + aaa - aa + a) \times (a + a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$3635 := \frac{(aaaa + aaa - aa + a) \times (a + a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$33635 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaa - aa + a) \times (a + a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$333635 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aaa - aa + a) \times (a + a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$636 := \frac{(aaa + aaa - aa + a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$3636 := \frac{(aaaa + aaa - aa + a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$33636 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaa - aa + a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$333636 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aaa - aa + a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$637 := \frac{(aaa + aaa - aa + a) \times (a + a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$3637 := \frac{(aaaa + aaa - aa + a) \times (a + a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$33637 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaa - aa + a) \times (a + a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$333637 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aaa - aa + a) \times (a + a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$638 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times aa + (aa + aa) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$6238 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times aaa + (aa + aa) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$62238 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times aaaa + (aa + aa) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$622238 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times aaaaa + (aa + aa) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$639 := \frac{aaaa + aaa}{a + a} + \frac{aaa + a}{a + a + a + a}$$

$$5639 := \frac{aaaaa + aaa}{a + a} + \frac{aaa + a}{a + a + a + a}$$

$$55639 := \frac{aaaaaa + aaa}{a + a} + \frac{aaa + a}{a + a + a + a}$$

$$555639 := \frac{aaaaaaa + aaa}{a + a} + \frac{aaa + a}{a + a + a + a}$$

$$640 := \frac{aaaa - aa - aa - aa}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa}{aa}$$

$$5640 := \frac{aaaaa - aa - aa - aa}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa}{aa}$$

$$55640 := \frac{aaaaaa - aa - aa - aa}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa}{aa}$$

$$555640 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aa - aa - aa}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa}{aa}$$

$$641 := \frac{(aaa + aaa + aaa - aa - a) \times (a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$2641 := \frac{(aaaa + aaa + aaa - aa - a) \times (a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$22641 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaa + aaa - aa - a) \times (a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$222641 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aaa + aaa - aa - a) \times (a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$642 := \frac{(aaa + aaa + aaa - aa - a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$2642 := \frac{(aaaa + aaa + aaa - aa - a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$22642 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaa + aaa - aa - a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$222642 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aaa + aaa - aa - a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$643 := \frac{(aaa + aaa + aaa - aa - a) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$2643 := \frac{(aaaa + aaa + aaa - aa - a) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$22643 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaa + aaa - aa - a) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$222643 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aaa + aaa - aa - a) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$644 := \frac{aaa \times (aa + a) - (aa + aa) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$6644 := \frac{aaaa \times (aa + a) - (aa + aa) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$66644 := \frac{aaaaa \times (aa + a) - (aa + aa) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$666644 := \frac{aaaaaa \times (aa + a) - (aa + aa) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$645 := \frac{aaaa - aa - aa - a}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa}{aa}$$

$$5645 := \frac{aaaaa - aa - aa - a}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa}{aa}$$

$$55645 := \frac{aaaaaa - aa - aa - a}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa}{aa}$$

$$555645 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aa - aa - a}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa}{aa}$$

$$646 := \frac{aaaa - aa - aa + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa}{aa}$$

$$5646 := \frac{aaaaa - aa - aa + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa}{aa}$$

$$55646 := \frac{aaaaaa - aa - aa + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa}{aa}$$

$$555646 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aa - aa + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa}{aa}$$

$$647 := \frac{aaaa + aaa - a - a}{a + a} + \frac{aaa}{a + a + a}$$

$$5647 := \frac{aaaaa + aaa - a - a}{a + a} + \frac{aaa}{a + a + a}$$

$$55647 := \frac{aaaaaa + aaa - a - a}{a + a} + \frac{aaa}{a + a + a}$$

$$555647 := \frac{aaaaaaa + aaa - a - a}{a + a} + \frac{aaa}{a + a + a}$$

$$648 := \frac{aaaa + aaa}{a + a} + \frac{aaa}{a + a + a}$$

$$5648 := \frac{aaaaa + aaa}{a + a} + \frac{aaa}{a + a + a}$$

$$55648 := \frac{aaaaaa + aaa}{a + a} + \frac{aaa}{a + a + a}$$

$$555648 := \frac{aaaaaaa + aaa}{a + a} + \frac{aaa}{a + a + a}$$

$$649 := \frac{aaaa + aaa + a + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaa}{a + a + a}$$

$$5649 := \frac{aaaaa + aaa + a + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaa}{a + a + a}$$

$$55649 := \frac{aaaaaa + aaa + a + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaa}{a + a + a}$$

$$555649 := \frac{aaaaaaa + aaa + a + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaa}{a + a + a}$$

$$650 := \frac{aaaa - aa - a - a}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa}{aa}$$

$$5650 := \frac{aaaaa - aa - a - a}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa}{aa}$$

$$55650 := \frac{aaaaaa - aa - a - a}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa}{aa}$$

$$555650 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aa - a - a}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa}{aa}$$

$$651 := \frac{aaaa - aa}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa}{aa}$$

$$5651 := \frac{aaaaa - aa}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa}{aa}$$

$$55651 := \frac{aaaaaa - aa}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa}{aa}$$

$$555651 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aa}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa}{aa}$$

$$652 := \frac{aaaa - aa + a + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa}{aa}$$

$$5652 := \frac{aaaaa - aa + a + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa}{aa}$$

$$55652 := \frac{aaaaaa - aa + a + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa}{aa}$$

$$555652 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aa + a + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa}{aa}$$

$$653 := \frac{(aaa - a - a) \times (aa + a) - a \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$6653 := \frac{(aaaa - a - a) \times (aa + a) - a \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$66653 := \frac{(aaaaa - a - a) \times (aa + a) - a \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$666653 := \frac{(aaaaaa - a - a) \times (aa + a) - a \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 654 &:= \frac{(aaa - a - a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 6654 &:= \frac{(aaaa - a - a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 66654 &:= \frac{(aaaaa - a - a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 666654 &:= \frac{(aaaaaa - a - a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 \\
 655 &:= \frac{aaa \times (aa + a) - aa \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 6655 &:= \frac{aaaa \times (aa + a) - aa \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 66655 &:= \frac{aaaaa \times (aa + a) - aa \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 666655 &:= \frac{aaaaaa \times (aa + a) - aa \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 \\
 656 &:= \frac{aaa \times (aa + a) - (aa - a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 6656 &:= \frac{aaaa \times (aa + a) - (aa - a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 66656 &:= \frac{aaaaa \times (aa + a) - (aa - a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 666656 &:= \frac{aaaaaa \times (aa + a) - (aa - a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 \\
 657 &:= \frac{aaa \times (aa + a) - (aa - a - a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 6657 &:= \frac{aaaa \times (aa + a) - (aa - a - a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 66657 &:= \frac{aaaaa \times (aa + a) - (aa - a - a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 666657 &:= \frac{aaaaaa \times (aa + a) - (aa - a - a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 658 &:= \frac{(aaa + aa) \times aa - (aa + a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 6758 &:= \frac{(aaa + aa) \times aaa - (aa + a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 67758 &:= \frac{(aaa + aa) \times aaaa - (aa + a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 677758 &:= \frac{(aaa + aa) \times aaaaa - (aa + a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 \\
 659 &:= \frac{aaaa - aa - a - a}{a + a} + \frac{aaa - a}{a} \\
 5659 &:= \frac{aaaaa - aa - a - a}{a + a} + \frac{aaa - a}{a} \\
 55659 &:= \frac{aaaaaa - aa - a - a}{a + a} + \frac{aaa - a}{a} \\
 555659 &:= \frac{aaaaaaa - aa - a - a}{a + a} + \frac{aaa - a}{a} \\
 \\
 660 &:= \frac{aaaa - aa}{a + a} + \frac{aaa - a}{a} \\
 5660 &:= \frac{aaaaa - aa}{a + a} + \frac{aaa - a}{a} \\
 55660 &:= \frac{aaaaaa - aa}{a + a} + \frac{aaa - a}{a} \\
 555660 &:= \frac{aaaaaaa - aa}{a + a} + \frac{aaa - a}{a} \\
 \\
 661 &:= \frac{aaaa - aa + a + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaa - a}{a} \\
 5661 &:= \frac{aaaaa - aa + a + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaa - a}{a} \\
 55661 &:= \frac{aaaaaa - aa + a + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaa - a}{a} \\
 555661 &:= \frac{aaaaaaa - aa + a + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaa - a}{a} \\
 \\
 662 &:= \frac{aaaa + aa}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa}{aa} \\
 5662 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aa}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa}{aa} \\
 55662 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aa}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa}{aa} \\
 555662 &:= \frac{aaaaaaa + aa}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa}{aa}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 663 &:= \frac{aaaa + aa + a + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa}{aa} \\ 5663 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aa + a + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa}{aa} \\ 55663 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aa + a + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa}{aa} \\ 555663 &:= \frac{aaaaaaa + aa + a + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa}{aa} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 664 &:= \frac{aaa \times (aa + a) - (a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\ 6664 &:= \frac{aaaa \times (aa + a) - (a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\ 66664 &:= \frac{aaaaa \times (aa + a) - (a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\ 666664 &:= \frac{aaaaaa \times (aa + a) - (a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 665 &:= \frac{aaa \times (aa + a) - (a + a) \times a}{(a + a) \times a} \\ 6665 &:= \frac{aaaa \times (aa + a) - (a + a) \times a}{(a + a) \times a} \\ 66665 &:= \frac{aaaaa \times (aa + a) - (a + a) \times a}{(a + a) \times a} \\ 666665 &:= \frac{aaaaaa \times (aa + a) - (a + a) \times a}{(a + a) \times a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 666 &:= \frac{aaa \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\ 6666 &:= \frac{aaaa \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\ 66666 &:= \frac{aaaaa \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\ 666666 &:= \frac{aaaaaa \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 667 &:= \frac{aaa \times (aa + a) + (a + a) \times a}{(a + a) \times a} \\ 6667 &:= \frac{aaaa \times (aa + a) + (a + a) \times a}{(a + a) \times a} \\ 66667 &:= \frac{aaaaa \times (aa + a) + (a + a) \times a}{(a + a) \times a} \\ 666667 &:= \frac{aaaaaa \times (aa + a) + (a + a) \times a}{(a + a) \times a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 668 &:= \frac{aaaa + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaa + a}{a} \\ 6668 &:= \frac{aaaaa + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa + a}{a} \\ 66668 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaaaa + a}{a} \\ 666668 &:= \frac{aaaaaaa + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaaaaa + a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 669 &:= \frac{aaaa + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaa + a + a}{a} \\ 6669 &:= \frac{aaaaa + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa + a + a}{a} \\ 66669 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaaaa + a + a}{a} \\ 666669 &:= \frac{aaaaaaa + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaaaaa + a + a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 670 &:= \frac{aaaa + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaa + a + a + a}{a} \\ 6670 &:= \frac{aaaaa + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa + a + a + a}{a} \\ 66670 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaaaa + a + a + a}{a} \\ 666670 &:= \frac{aaaaaaa + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaaaaa + a + a + a}{a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 671 &:= \frac{(aaa + aa) \times (aa + aa)}{(a + a) \times (a + a)} \\ 6171 &:= \frac{(aaaa + aa) \times (aa + aa)}{(a + a) \times (a + a)} \\ 61171 &:= \frac{(aaaaa + aa) \times (aa + aa)}{(a + a) \times (a + a)} \\ 611171 &:= \frac{(aaaaaa + aa) \times (aa + aa)}{(a + a) \times (a + a)} \end{aligned}$$

$$672 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$6672 := \frac{(aaaa + a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$66672 := \frac{(aaaaa + a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$666672 := \frac{(aaaaaa + a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$673 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times (aa + a) + (a + a) \times a}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$6673 := \frac{(aaaa + a) \times (aa + a) + (a + a) \times a}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$66673 := \frac{(aaaaa + a) \times (aa + a) + (a + a) \times a}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$666673 := \frac{(aaaaaa + a) \times (aa + a) + (a + a) \times a}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$674 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times (aa + a) + (a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$6674 := \frac{(aaaa + a) \times (aa + a) + (a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$66674 := \frac{(aaaaa + a) \times (aa + a) + (a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$666674 := \frac{(aaaaaa + a) \times (aa + a) + (a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$675 := \frac{(aa + a) \times aaa + (aa - a - a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$6675 := \frac{(aa + a) \times aaaa + (aa - a - a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$66675 := \frac{(aa + a) \times aaaaa + (aa - a - a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$666675 := \frac{(aa + a) \times aaaaaa + (aa - a - a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$676 := \frac{aaa \times (aa + a) + (aa - a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$6676 := \frac{aaaa \times (aa + a) + (aa - a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$66676 := \frac{aaaaa \times (aa + a) + (aa - a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$666676 := \frac{aaaaaa \times (aa + a) + (aa - a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$677 := \frac{aaa \times (aa + a) + aa \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$6677 := \frac{aaaa \times (aa + a) + aa \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$66677 := \frac{aaaaa \times (aa + a) + aa \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$666677 := \frac{aaaaaa \times (aa + a) + aa \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$678 := \frac{(aaa + a + a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$6678 := \frac{(aaaa + a + a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$66678 := \frac{(aaaaa + a + a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$666678 := \frac{(aaaaaa + a + a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$679 := \frac{aaaa + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaa + aa + a}{a}$$

$$6679 := \frac{aaaaa + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa + aa + a}{a}$$

$$66679 := \frac{aaaaaa + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaaaa + aa + a}{a}$$

$$666679 := \frac{aaaaaaa + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaaaaa + aa + a}{a}$$

$$680 := \frac{aaaa + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaa + aa + a + a}{a}$$

$$6680 := \frac{aaaaa + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa + aa + a + a}{a}$$

$$66680 := \frac{aaaaaa + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaaaa + aa + a + a}{a}$$

$$666680 := \frac{aaaaaaa + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaaaaa + aa + a + a}{a}$$

$$681 := \frac{(aaa + aa) \times aa + (aa - a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$6181 := \frac{(aaaa + aa) \times aa + (aa - a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$61181 := \frac{(aaaaa + aa) \times aa + (aa - a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$611181 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aa) \times aa + (aa - a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$682 := \frac{(aaa + aa) \times aa + aa \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$6182 := \frac{(aaaa + aa) \times aa + aa \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$61182 := \frac{(aaaaa + aa) \times aa + aa \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$611182 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aa) \times aa + aa \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$683 := \frac{aaaa + aa}{a + a} + \frac{aaa + aa}{a}$$

$$6683 := \frac{aaaaa + aa}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa + aa}{a}$$

$$66683 := \frac{aaaaaa + aa}{a + a} + \frac{aaaaa + aa}{a}$$

$$666683 := \frac{aaaaaaa + aa}{a + a} + \frac{aaaaaa + aa}{a}$$

$$684 := \frac{aaaa + aa}{a + a} + \frac{aaa + aa + a}{a}$$

$$6684 := \frac{aaaaa + aa}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa + aa + a}{a}$$

$$66684 := \frac{aaaaaa + aa}{a + a} + \frac{aaaaa + aa + a}{a}$$

$$666684 := \frac{aaaaaaa + aa}{a + a} + \frac{aaaaaa + aa + a}{a}$$

$$685 := \frac{aaaa + aa}{a + a} + \frac{aaa + aa + a + a}{a}$$

$$6685 := \frac{aaaaa + aa}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa + aa + a + a}{a}$$

$$66685 := \frac{aaaaaa + aa}{a + a} + \frac{aaaaa + aa + a + a}{a}$$

$$666685 := \frac{aaaaaaa + aa}{a + a} + \frac{aaaaaa + aa + a + a}{a}$$

$$686 := \frac{(aaa + aaa + aaa + aa - a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$2686 := \frac{(aaaa + aaa + aaa + aa - a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$22686 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaa + aaa + aa - a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$222686 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aaa + aaa + aa - a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$687 := \frac{(aaa + aaa + aaa + aa) \times (a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$2687 := \frac{(aaaa + aaa + aaa + aa) \times (a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$22687 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaa + aaa + aa) \times (a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$222687 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aaa + aaa + aa) \times (a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$688 := \frac{(aaa + aaa + aaa + aa) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$2688 := \frac{(aaaa + aaa + aaa + aa) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$22688 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaa + aaa + aa) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$222688 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aaa + aaa + aa) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$689 := \frac{(aaa + aaa + aaa + aa) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$2689 := \frac{(aaaa + aaa + aaa + aa) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$22689 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaa + aaa + aa) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$222689 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aaa + aaa + aa) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$690 := \frac{(aaa + aaa + aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$2690 := \frac{(aaaa + aaa + aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$22690 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaa + aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$222690 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aaa + aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$691 := \frac{(aaa + aaa + aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$2691 := \frac{(aaaa + aaa + aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$22691 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaa + aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$222691 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aaa + aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$692 := \frac{(aaa + aaa + aaa + aa + a + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$2692 := \frac{(aaaa + aaa + aaa + aa + a + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$22692 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaa + aaa + aa + a + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$222692 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aaa + aaa + aa + a + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$693 := \frac{(aa + aa + aa) \times (aa + aa - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$6993 := \frac{(aaa + aaa + aaa) \times (aa + aa - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$69993 := \frac{(aaaa + aaaa + aaaa) \times (aa + aa - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$699993 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaaaa + aaaaa) \times (aa + aa - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$694 := \frac{(aa + aa + aa) \times (aa + aa - a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$6994 := \frac{(aaa + aaa + aaa) \times (aa + aa - a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$69994 := \frac{(aaaa + aaaa + aaaa) \times (aa + aa - a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$699994 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaaaa + aaaaa) \times (aa + aa - a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$695 := \frac{aaaa + aa}{a + a} + \frac{aaa + aa + aa + a}{a}$$

$$6695 := \frac{aaaaa + aa}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa + aa + aa + a}{a}$$

$$66695 := \frac{aaaaaa + aa}{a + a} + \frac{aaaaa + aa + aa + a}{a}$$

$$666695 := \frac{aaaaaaa + aa}{a + a} + \frac{aaaaaa + aa + aa + a}{a}$$

$$696 := \frac{(aaa + aaa + aa - a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$3696 := \frac{(aaaa + aaa + aa - a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$33696 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaa + aa - a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$333696 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aaa + aa - a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$697 := \frac{(aaa + aaa + aa) \times (a + a + a) - a \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$3697 := \frac{(aaaa + aaa + aa) \times (a + a + a) - a \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$33697 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaa + aa) \times (a + a + a) - a \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$333697 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aaa + aa) \times (a + a + a) - a \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$698 := \frac{(aaa + aaa + aa) \times (a + a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$3698 := \frac{(aaaa + aaa + aa) \times (a + a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$33698 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaa + aa) \times (a + a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$333698 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aaa + aa) \times (a + a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$699 := \frac{(aaa + aaa + aa) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$3699 := \frac{(aaaa + aaa + aa) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$33699 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaa + aa) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$333699 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aaa + aa) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$700 := \frac{(aaa + aaa + aa) \times (a + a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$3700 := \frac{(aaaa + aaa + aa) \times (a + a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$33700 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaa + aa) \times (a + a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$333700 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aaa + aa) \times (a + a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$701 := \frac{(aaa + aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$3701 := \frac{(aaaa + aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$33701 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$333701 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$702 := \frac{(aaa + aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$3702 := \frac{(aaaa + aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$33702 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$333702 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$703 := \frac{(aaa + aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$3703 := \frac{(aaaa + aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$33703 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$333703 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$704 := \frac{(aaa + aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a + a) + a \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$3704 := \frac{(aaaa + aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a + a) + a \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$33704 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a + a) + a \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$333704 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aaa + aa + a) \times (a + a + a) + a \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$705 := \frac{aaaa + aa}{a + a} + \frac{aaa + aa + aa + aa}{a}$$

$$6705 := \frac{aaaaa + aa}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa + aa + aa + aa}{a}$$

$$66705 := \frac{aaaaaa + aa}{a + a} + \frac{aaaaa + aa + aa + aa}{a}$$

$$666705 := \frac{aaaaaaa + aa}{a + a} + \frac{aaaaaa + aa + aa + aa}{a}$$

$$706 := \frac{aaaa + aa}{a + a} + \frac{aaa + aa + aa + aa + a}{a}$$

$$6706 := \frac{aaaaa + aa}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa + aa + aa + aa + a}{a}$$

$$66706 := \frac{aaaaaa + aa}{a + a} + \frac{aaaaa + aa + aa + aa + a}{a}$$

$$666706 := \frac{aaaaaaa + aa}{a + a} + \frac{aaaaaa + aa + aa + aa + a}{a}$$

$$707 := \frac{(aa + a + a + a) \times aaaa}{aa \times (a + a)}$$

$$70707 := \frac{(aa + a + a + a) \times aaaaaa}{aa \times (a + a)}$$

$$7070707 := \frac{(aa + a + a + a) \times aaaaaaaaa}{aa \times (a + a)}$$

$$707070707 := \frac{(aa + a + a + a) \times aaaaaaaaaa}{aa \times (a + a)}$$

$$708 := \frac{(aa + a + a + a) \times aaaa + aa \times (a + a)}{aa \times (a + a)}$$

$$70708 := \frac{(aa + a + a + a) \times aaaaaa + aa \times (a + a)}{aa \times (a + a)}$$

$$7070708 := \frac{(aa + a + a + a) \times aaaaaaaaa + aa \times (a + a)}{aa \times (a + a)}$$

$$707070708 := \frac{(aa + a + a + a) \times aaaaaaaaaa + aa \times (a + a)}{aa \times (a + a)}$$

$$709 := \frac{(aaa - aa) \times (aa + a) + (aaa - a - a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$6709 := \frac{(aaaa - aa) \times (aa + a) + (aaa - a - a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$66709 := \frac{(aaaaa - aa) \times (aa + a) + (aaa - a - a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$666709 := \frac{(aaaaaa - aa) \times (aa + a) + (aaa - a - a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 710 &:= \frac{(aaa - aa) \times (aa + a) + (aaa - a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 6710 &:= \frac{(aaaa - aa) \times (aa + a) + (aaa - a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 66710 &:= \frac{(aaaaa - aa) \times (aa + a) + (aaa - a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 666710 &:= \frac{(aaaaaa - aa) \times (aa + a) + (aaa - a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 711 &:= \frac{(aaa - aa - aa) \times (aa - a - a - a) - a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 8711 &:= \frac{(aaaa - aa - aa) \times (aa - a - a - a) - a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 88711 &:= \frac{(aaaaa - aa - aa) \times (aa - a - a - a) - a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 888711 &:= \frac{(aaaaaa - aa - aa) \times (aa - a - a - a) - a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 712 &:= \frac{(aaa - aa - aa) \times (aa - a - a - a)}{a \times a} \\
 8712 &:= \frac{(aaaa - aa - aa) \times (aa - a - a - a)}{a \times a} \\
 88712 &:= \frac{(aaaaa - aa - aa) \times (aa - a - a - a)}{a \times a} \\
 888712 &:= \frac{(aaaaaa - aa - aa) \times (aa - a - a - a)}{a \times a} \\
 713 &:= \frac{(aaa - aa - aa) \times (aa - a - a - a) + a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 8713 &:= \frac{(aaaa - aa - aa) \times (aa - a - a - a) + a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 88713 &:= \frac{(aaaaa - aa - aa) \times (aa - a - a - a) + a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 888713 &:= \frac{(aaaaaa - aa - aa) \times (aa - a - a - a) + a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 714 &:= \frac{(aaa - aa - aa) \times (aa - a - a - a) + a \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 8714 &:= \frac{(aaaa - aa - aa) \times (aa - a - a - a) + a \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 88714 &:= \frac{(aaaaa - aa - aa) \times (aa - a - a - a) + a \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 888714 &:= \frac{(aaaaaa - aa - aa) \times (aa - a - a - a) + a \times (a + a)}{a \times a}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 715 &:= \frac{(aaa - a) \times (aa + a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 7215 &:= \frac{(aaaa - a) \times (aa + a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 72215 &:= \frac{(aaaaa - a) \times (aa + a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 722215 &:= \frac{(aaaaaa - a) \times (aa + a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 716 &:= \frac{(aaa - a) \times aa + aaa \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 1716 &:= \frac{(aaa - a) \times aa + aaaa \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 11716 &:= \frac{(aaa - a) \times aa + aaaaa \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 111716 &:= \frac{(aaa - a) \times aa + aaaaaa \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 717 &:= \frac{(aaa - a) \times aa + (aaa + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 1717 &:= \frac{(aaa - a) \times aa + (aaaa + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 11717 &:= \frac{(aaa - a) \times aa + (aaaaa + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 111717 &:= \frac{(aaa - a) \times aa + (aaaaaa + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 718 &:= \frac{(aaa - a) \times aa + (aaa + a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 1718 &:= \frac{(aaa - a) \times aa + (aaaa + a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 11718 &:= \frac{(aaa - a) \times aa + (aaaaa + a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 111718 &:= \frac{(aaa - a) \times aa + (aaaaaa + a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$719 := \frac{(aaa - a) \times aa + (aaa + a + a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$1719 := \frac{(aaa - a) \times aa + (aaaa + a + a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$11719 := \frac{(aaa - a) \times aa + (aaaaa + a + a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$111719 := \frac{(aaa - a) \times aa + (aaaaaa + a + a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$720 := \frac{(aa + a + a) \times aaa - (a + a + a) \times a}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$7220 := \frac{(aa + a + a) \times aaaa - (a + a + a) \times a}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$72220 := \frac{(aa + a + a) \times aaaaa - (a + a + a) \times a}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$722220 := \frac{(aa + a + a) \times aaaaaa - (a + a + a) \times a}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$721 := \frac{(aa + a + a) \times aaa - a \times a}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$7221 := \frac{(aa + a + a) \times aaaa - a \times a}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$72221 := \frac{(aa + a + a) \times aaaaa - a \times a}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$722221 := \frac{(aa + a + a) \times aaaaaa - a \times a}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$722 := \frac{(aa + a + a) \times aaa + a \times a}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$7222 := \frac{(aa + a + a) \times aaaa + a \times a}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$72222 := \frac{(aa + a + a) \times aaaaa + a \times a}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$722222 := \frac{(aa + a + a) \times aaaaaa + a \times a}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$723 := \frac{aaaa + aaa + a + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaa}{a}$$

$$7223 := \frac{aaaaa + aaaa + a + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa}{a}$$

$$72223 := \frac{aaaaaa + aaaaa + a + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaaaa}{a}$$

$$722223 := \frac{aaaaaaa + aaaaaa + a + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaaaaa}{a}$$

$$724 := \frac{aaaa + aaa + a + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaa + a}{a}$$

$$7224 := \frac{aaaaa + aaaa + a + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaaa + a}{a}$$

$$72224 := \frac{aaaaaa + aaaaa + a + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaaaa + a}{a}$$

$$722224 := \frac{aaaaaaa + aaaaaa + a + a}{a + a} + \frac{aaaaaa + a}{a}$$

$$725 := \frac{(aa + aa + aa) \times (aa + aa) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$7325 := \frac{(aaa + aaa + aaa) \times (aa + aa) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$73325 := \frac{(aaaa + aaaa + aaaa) \times (aa + aa) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$733325 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaaaa + aaaaa) \times (aa + aa) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$726 := \frac{(aa + a) \times aa \times aa}{(a + a) \times a \times a}$$

$$7326 := \frac{(aa + a) \times aa \times aaa}{(a + a) \times a \times a}$$

$$73326 := \frac{(aa + a) \times aa \times aaaa}{(a + a) \times a \times a}$$

$$733326 := \frac{(aa + a) \times aa \times aaaaa}{(a + a) \times a \times a}$$

$$727 := \frac{(aa + aa + aa) \times (aa + aa) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$7327 := \frac{(aaa + aaa + aaa) \times (aa + aa) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$73327 := \frac{(aaaa + aaaa + aaaa) \times (aa + aa) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$733327 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaaaa + aaaaa) \times (aa + aa) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$728 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times (aa + a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$7228 := \frac{(aaaa + a) \times (aa + a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$72228 := \frac{(aaaaa + a) \times (aa + a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$722228 := \frac{(aaaaaa + a) \times (aa + a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$729 := \frac{(aaa + a) \times (aa + a + a) + (a + a) \times a}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$7229 := \frac{(aaaa + a) \times (aa + a + a) + (a + a) \times a}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$72229 := \frac{(aaaaa + a) \times (aa + a + a) + (a + a) \times a}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$722229 := \frac{(aaaaaa + a) \times (aa + a + a) + (a + a) \times a}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$730 := \frac{(aaa + aa) \times (aa + a) - (a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$6730 := \frac{(aaaa + aa) \times (aa + a) - (a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$66730 := \frac{(aaaaa + aa) \times (aa + a) - (a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$666730 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aa) \times (aa + a) - (a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$731 := \frac{(aaa + aa) \times (aa + a) - (a + a) \times a}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$6731 := \frac{(aaaa + aa) \times (aa + a) - (a + a) \times a}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$66731 := \frac{(aaaaa + aa) \times (aa + a) - (a + a) \times a}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$666731 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aa) \times (aa + a) - (a + a) \times a}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$732 := \frac{(aaa + aa) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$6732 := \frac{(aaaa + aa) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$66732 := \frac{(aaaaa + aa) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$666732 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aa) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$733 := \frac{(aaa + aa) \times (aa + a) + a \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$6733 := \frac{(aaaa + aa) \times (aa + a) + a \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$66733 := \frac{(aaaaa + aa) \times (aa + a) + a \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$666733 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aa) \times (aa + a) + a \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$734 := \frac{(aaa + aa) \times (aa + a) + (a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$6734 := \frac{(aaaa + aa) \times (aa + a) + (a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$66734 := \frac{(aaaaa + aa) \times (aa + a) + (a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$666734 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aa) \times (aa + a) + (a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$735 := \frac{(aaa + aa) \times (aa + a) + (a + a) \times (a + a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$6735 := \frac{(aaaa + aa) \times (aa + a) + (a + a) \times (a + a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$66735 := \frac{(aaaaa + aa) \times (aa + a) + (a + a) \times (a + a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$666735 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aa) \times (aa + a) + (a + a) \times (a + a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$736 := \frac{aaaa + aaaa - aa - a - a - a}{a + a + a}$$

$$370736 := \frac{aaaaaaaa + aaaa - aa - a - a - a}{a + a + a}$$

$$370370736 := \frac{aaaaaaaaaaaa + aaaa - aa - a - a - a}{a + a + a}$$

$$370370370736 := \frac{aaaaaaaaaaaaaaaa + aaaa - aa - a - a - a}{a + a + a}$$

$$737 := \frac{aaaa + aaaa - aa}{a + a + a}$$

$$370737 := \frac{aaaaaaaa + aaaa - aa}{a + a + a}$$

$$370370737 := \frac{aaaaaaaaaaaa + aaaa - aa}{a + a + a}$$

$$370370370737 := \frac{aaaaaaaaaaaaaaaa + aaaa - aa}{a + a + a}$$

$$738 := \frac{(aaaa - a) \times (a + a) - (a + a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$740738 := \frac{(aaaaaaaa - a) \times (a + a) - (a + a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$740740738 := \frac{(aaaaaaaaaaaa - a) \times (a + a) - (a + a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$740740740738 := \frac{(aaaaaaaaaaaaaaaa - a) \times (a + a) - (a + a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$739 := \frac{(aaaa - a) \times (a + a) - (a + a + a) \times a}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$740739 := \frac{(aaaaaaaa - a) \times (a + a) - (a + a + a) \times a}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$740740739 := \frac{(aaaaaaaaaaaa - a) \times (a + a) - (a + a + a) \times a}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$740740740739 := \frac{(aaaaaaaaaaaaaaaa - a) \times (a + a) - (a + a + a) \times a}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$740 := \frac{(aaaa - a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$740740 := \frac{(aaaaaaaa - a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$740740740 := \frac{(aaaaaaaaaaaa - a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$740740740740 := \frac{(aaaaaaaaaaaaaaaa - a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$741 := \frac{(aaaa - a) \times (a + a) + (a + a + a) \times a}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$740741 := \frac{(aaaaaaaa - a) \times (a + a) + (a + a + a) \times a}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$740740741 := \frac{(aaaaaaaaaaaa - a) \times (a + a) + (a + a + a) \times a}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$740740740741 := \frac{(aaaaaaaaaaaaaaaa - a) \times (a + a) + (a + a + a) \times a}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$742 := \frac{(aaaa + a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$740742 := \frac{(aaaaaaaa + a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$740740742 := \frac{(aaaaaaaaaaaa + a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$740740740742 := \frac{(aaaaaaaaaaaaaaaa + a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$743 := \frac{(aaa + aa) \times (aa + a) + aa \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$6743 := \frac{(aaaa + aa) \times (aa + a) + aa \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$66743 := \frac{(aaaaa + aa) \times (aa + a) + aa \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$666743 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aa) \times (aa + a) + aa \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$744 := \frac{aaaa + aaaa + aa - a}{a + a + a}$$

$$7444 := \frac{aaaaa + aaaaa + aaa - a}{a + a + a}$$

$$74444 := \frac{aaaaaa + aaaaaa + aaaa - a}{a + a + a}$$

$$744444 := \frac{aaaaaaa + aaaaaaa + aaaaa - a}{a + a + a}$$

$$745 := \frac{aaaa + aaaa + aa + a + a}{a + a + a}$$

$$7445 := \frac{aaaaa + aaaaa + aaa + a + a}{a + a + a}$$

$$74445 := \frac{aaaaaa + aaaaaa + aaaa + a + a}{a + a + a}$$

$$744445 := \frac{aaaaaaa + aaaaaaa + aaaaa + a + a}{a + a + a}$$

$$746 := \frac{aaaa + aaaa + aa + a + a + a + a + a}{a + a + a}$$

$$7446 := \frac{aaaaa + aaaaa + aaa + a + a + a + a + a}{a + a + a}$$

$$74446 := \frac{aaaaaaa + aaaaaa + aaaa + a + a + a + a + a}{a + a + a}$$

$$744446 := \frac{aaaaaaaa + aaaaaaa + aaaaa + a + a + a + a + a}{a + a + a}$$

$$747 := \frac{(aa + aa + aa) \times (aa + aa + a) - (aa + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$7647 := \frac{(aaa + aaa + aaa) \times (aa + aa + a) - (aa + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$76647 := \frac{(aaaa + aaaa + aaaa) \times (aa + aa + a) - (a + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$766647 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaaaa + aaaaa) \times (aa + aa + a) - (a + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$748 := \frac{(aaaa + aa) \times (a + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$740748 := \frac{(aaaaaaa + aa) \times (a + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$7407407488 := \frac{(aaaaaaaaaaa + aa) \times (a + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$740740740748 := \frac{(aaaaaaaaaaaaaaa + aa) \times (a + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$749 := \frac{(aaaa + aa) \times (a + a) + (a + a + a) \times a}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$740749 := \frac{(aaaaaaa + aa) \times (a + a) + (a + a + a) \times a}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$7407407489 := \frac{(aaaaaaaaaaa + aa) \times (a + a) + (a + a + a) \times a}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$740740740749 := \frac{(aaaaaaaaaaaaaaa + aa) \times (a + a) + (a + a + a) \times a}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$750 := \frac{(aaaa - aaa) \times (a + a + a)}{(a + a) \times (a + a)}$$

$$7500 := \frac{(aaaaa - aaaa) \times (a + a + a)}{(a + a) \times (a + a)}$$

$$75000 := \frac{(aaaaaa - aaaaa) \times (a + a + a)}{(a + a) \times (a + a)}$$

$$750000 := \frac{(aaaaaaa - aaaaaa) \times (a + a + a)}{(a + a) \times (a + a)}$$

$$751 := \frac{aaaa + aaaa + aa + aa + aa - a - a}{a + a + a}$$

$$7451 := \frac{aaaaa + aaaaa + aaa + aa + aa - a - a}{a + a + a}$$

$$74451 := \frac{aaaaaaa + aaaaaa + aaaa + aa + aa - a - a}{a + a + a}$$

$$744451 := \frac{aaaaaaaa + aaaaaaa + aaaaa + aa + aa - a - a}{a + a + a}$$

$$752 := \frac{aaaa + aaaa + aa + aa + aa + a}{a + a + a}$$

$$7452 := \frac{aaaaa + aaaaa + aaa + aa + aa + a}{a + a + a}$$

$$74452 := \frac{aaaaaaa + aaaaaa + aaaa + aa + aa + a}{a + a + a}$$

$$744452 := \frac{aaaaaaaa + aaaaaaa + aaaaa + aa + aa + a}{a + a + a}$$

$$753 := \frac{aaaa \times (aa + a) + aaa \times (a + a)}{(aa - a - a) \times (a + a)}$$

$$740753 := \frac{aaaaaaa \times (aa + a) + aaa \times (a + a)}{(aa - a - a) \times (a + a)}$$

$$740740753 := \frac{aaaaaaaaaaa \times (aa + a) + aaa \times (a + a)}{(aa - a - a) \times (a + a)}$$

$$740740740753 := \frac{aaaaaaaaaaaaaaa \times (aa + a) + aaa \times (a + a)}{(aa - a - a) \times (a + a)}$$

$$754 := \frac{(aaaa + aa + aa - a - a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$7554 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaa + aaa - a - a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$75554 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aaaa + aaaa - a - a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$755554 := \frac{(aaaaaaa + aaaaa + aaaaa - a - a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$755 := \frac{(aa + aa - a) \times (aa + a) \times (a + a + a) - a \times a \times a}{a \times a \times a}$$

$$7955 := \frac{(aaa + aaa - a) \times (aa + a) \times (a + a + a) - a \times a \times a}{a \times a \times a}$$

$$79955 := \frac{(aaaa + aaaa - a) \times (aa + a) \times (a + a + a) - a \times a \times a}{a \times a \times a}$$

$$799955 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaaaa - a) \times (aa + a) \times (a + a + a) - a \times a \times a}{a \times a \times a}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 756 &:= \frac{(aa + aa - a) \times (aa + a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a \times a} \\
 7956 &:= \frac{(aaa + aaa - a) \times (aa + a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a \times a} \\
 79956 &:= \frac{(aaaa + aaaa - a) \times (aa + a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a \times a} \\
 799956 &:= \frac{(aaaaa + aaaaa - a) \times (aa + a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a \times a} \\
 757 &:= \frac{(aa - a - a) \times aaa - (aa + aa) \times aa}{a \times a} \\
 9757 &:= \frac{(aa - a - a) \times aaaa - (aa + aa) \times aa}{a \times a} \\
 99757 &:= \frac{(aa - a - a) \times aaaaa - (aa + aa) \times aa}{a \times a} \\
 999757 &:= \frac{(aa - a - a) \times aaaaaa - (aa + aa) \times aa}{a \times a} \\
 758 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + aa) \times (aa + aa + a) - a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 7658 &:= \frac{(aaa + aaa + aaa) \times (aa + aa + a) - a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 76658 &:= \frac{(aaaa + aaaa + aaaa) \times (aa + aa + a) - a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 766658 &:= \frac{(aaaaa + aaaaa + aaaaa) \times (aa + aa + a) - a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 759 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + aa) \times (aa + aa + a)}{a \times a} \\
 7659 &:= \frac{(aaa + aaa + aaa) \times (aa + aa + a)}{a \times a} \\
 76659 &:= \frac{(aaaa + aaaa + aaaa) \times (aa + aa + a)}{a \times a} \\
 766659 &:= \frac{(aaaaa + aaaaa + aaaaa) \times (aa + aa + a)}{a \times a} \\
 760 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + aa) \times (aa + aa + a) + a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 7660 &:= \frac{(aaa + aaa + aaa) \times (aa + aa + a) + a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 76660 &:= \frac{(aaaa + aaaa + aaaa) \times (aa + aa + a) + a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 766660 &:= \frac{(aaaaa + aaaaa + aaaaa) \times (aa + aa + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 761 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + aa) \times (aa + aa + a) + a \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 7661 &:= \frac{(aaa + aaa + aaa) \times (aa + aa + a) + a \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 76661 &:= \frac{(aaaa + aaaa + aaaa) \times (aa + aa + a) + a \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 766661 &:= \frac{(aaaaa + aaaaa + aaaaa) \times (aa + aa + a) + a \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 762 &:= \frac{(aaa - a - a) \times (aa - a - a - a - a) - a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 7762 &:= \frac{(aaaa - a - a) \times (aa - a - a - a - a) - a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 77762 &:= \frac{(aaaaa - a - a) \times (aa - a - a - a - a) - a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 777762 &:= \frac{(aaaaaa - a - a) \times (aa - a - a - a - a) - a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 763 &:= \frac{(aaa - a - a) \times (aa + a + a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 7763 &:= \frac{(aaaa - a - a) \times (aa + a + a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 77763 &:= \frac{(aaaaa - a - a) \times (aa + a + a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 777763 &:= \frac{(aaaaaa - a - a) \times (aa + a + a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 764 &:= \frac{(aaa - a - a) \times (aa - a - a - a - a) + a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 7764 &:= \frac{(aaaa - a - a) \times (aa - a - a - a - a) + a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 77764 &:= \frac{(aaaaa - a - a) \times (aa - a - a - a - a) + a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 777764 &:= \frac{(aaaaaa - a - a) \times (aa - a - a - a - a) + a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 765 &:= \frac{(aa - a - a - a - a) \times aaa - (aa + a) \times a}{a \times a} \\
 7765 &:= \frac{(aa - a - a - a - a) \times aaaa - (aa + a) \times a}{a \times a} \\
 77765 &:= \frac{(aa - a - a - a - a) \times aaaaa - (aa + a) \times a}{a \times a} \\
 777765 &:= \frac{(aa - a - a - a - a) \times aaaaaa - (aa + a) \times a}{a \times a}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$766 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - aaa - aa - a}{a}$$

$$9766 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - aaa - aaa - aa - a}{a}$$

$$99766 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaaa - aaa - aaa - aa - a}{a}$$

$$999766 := \frac{aaaaaaaa - aaaaaa - aaa - aaa - aa - a}{a}$$

$$767 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaa - aa \times aa}{a \times a}$$

$$7667 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaa - aaa \times aa}{a \times a}$$

$$76667 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaaa - aaaa \times aa}{a \times a}$$

$$766667 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaaaa - aaaaa \times aa}{a \times a}$$

$$768 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - aaa - aa + a}{a}$$

$$9768 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - aaa - aaa - aa + a}{a}$$

$$99768 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaaa - aaa - aaa - aa + a}{a}$$

$$999768 := \frac{aaaaaaaa - aaaaaa - aaa - aaa - aa + a}{a}$$

$$769 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a - a) \times (aaa - a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$7769 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a - a) \times (aaaa - a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$77769 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a - a) \times (aaaaa - a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$777769 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a - a) \times (aaaaaa - a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$770 := \frac{(aa + aa - a) \times (aaa - a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$7770 := \frac{(aa + aa - a) \times (aaaa - a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$77770 := \frac{(aa + aa - a) \times (aaaaa - a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$777770 := \frac{(aa + aa - a) \times (aaaaaa - a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$771 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a - a) \times (aaa - a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$7771 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a - a) \times (aaaa - a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$77771 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a - a) \times (aaaaa - a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$777771 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a - a) \times (aaaaaa - a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$772 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a - a) \times (aaa - a) + (a + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$7772 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a - a) \times (aaaa - a) + (a + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$77772 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a - a) \times (aaaaa - a) + (a + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$777772 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a - a) \times (aaaaaa - a) + (a + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$773 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a - a) \times (aaa + a) - aa \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$7773 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a - a) \times (aaaa + a) - aa \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$77773 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a - a) \times (aaaaa + a) - aa \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$777773 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a - a) \times (aaaaaa + a) - aa \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$774 := \frac{aaaa + aaaa + aaa - aa}{a + a + a}$$

$$7774 := \frac{aaaaa + aaaaa + aaaa - aa}{a + a + a}$$

$$77774 := \frac{aaaaaaa + aaaaaa + aaaaa - aa}{a + a + a}$$

$$777774 := \frac{aaaaaaaa + aaaaaa + aaaaaa - aa}{a + a + a}$$

$$775 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - aaa - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$10775 := \frac{aaaaa - aaa - aaa - aaa - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$110775 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaa - aaa - aaa - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$1110775 := \frac{aaaaaaaa - aaa - aaa - aaa - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$776 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a - a) \times aaa - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$7776 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a - a) \times aaaa - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$77776 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a - a) \times aaaaa - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$777776 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a - a) \times aaaaaa - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$777 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a - a) \times aaa}{a \times a}$$

$$7777 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a - a) \times aaaa}{a \times a}$$

$$77777 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a - a) \times aaaaa}{a \times a}$$

$$777777 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a - a) \times aaaaaa}{a \times a}$$

$$778 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - aaa}{a}$$

$$10778 := \frac{aaaaa - aaa - aaa - aaa}{a}$$

$$110778 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaa - aaa - aaa}{a}$$

$$1110778 := \frac{aaaaaaaa - aaa - aaa - aaa}{a}$$

$$779 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - aaa + a}{a}$$

$$10779 := \frac{aaaaa - aaa - aaa - aaa + a}{a}$$

$$110779 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaa - aaa - aaa + a}{a}$$

$$1110779 := \frac{aaaaaaaa - aaa - aaa - aaa + a}{a}$$

$$780 := \frac{(aaa - aa - aa - aa) \times (aa - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$10780 := \frac{(aaaa - aa - aa - aa) \times (aa - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$110780 := \frac{(aaaaa - aa - aa - aa) \times (aa - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$1110780 := \frac{(aaaaaa - aa - aa - aa) \times (aa - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$781 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - aaa + a + a + a}{a}$$

$$10781 := \frac{aaaaa - aaa - aaa - aaa + a + a + a}{a}$$

$$110781 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaa - aaa - aaa + a + a + a}{a}$$

$$1110781 := \frac{aaaaaaaa - aaa - aaa - aaa + a + a + a}{a}$$

$$782 := \frac{(aaa + aa) \times aa + aaa \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$1782 := \frac{(aaa + aa) \times aa + aaaa \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$11782 := \frac{(aaa + aa) \times aa + aaaaa \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$111782 := \frac{(aaa + aa) \times aa + aaaaaa \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$783 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a - a) \times (aaa + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$7783 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a - a) \times (aaaa + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$77783 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a - a) \times (aaaaa + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$777783 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a - a) \times (aaaaaa + a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$784 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a - a) \times (aaa + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$7784 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a - a) \times (aaaa + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$77784 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a - a) \times (aaaaa + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$777784 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a - a) \times (aaaaaa + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$785 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a - a) \times (aaa + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$7785 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a - a) \times (aaaa + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$77785 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a - a) \times (aaaaa + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$777785 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a - a) \times (aaaaaa + a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$786 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - aaa + aa - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$9786 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - aaa - aaa + aa - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$99786 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa - aaa - aaa + aa - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$999786 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaaaa - aaa - aaa + aa - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$787 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - aaa + aa - a - a}{a}$$

$$9787 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - aaa - aaa + aa - a - a}{a}$$

$$99787 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa - aaa - aaa + aa - a - a}{a}$$

$$999787 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaaaa - aaa - aaa + aa - a - a}{a}$$

$$788 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - aaa + aa - a}{a}$$

$$9788 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - aaa - aaa + aa - a}{a}$$

$$99788 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa - aaa - aaa + aa - a}{a}$$

$$999788 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaaaa - aaa - aaa + aa - a}{a}$$

$$789 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - aaa + aa}{a}$$

$$9789 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - aaa - aaa + aa}{a}$$

$$99789 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa - aaa - aaa + aa}{a}$$

$$999789 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaaaa - aaa - aaa + aa}{a}$$

$$790 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - aaa + aa + a}{a}$$

$$9790 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - aaa - aaa + aa + a}{a}$$

$$99790 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa - aaa - aaa + aa + a}{a}$$

$$999790 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaaaa - aaa - aaa + aa + a}{a}$$

$$791 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a - a) \times (aaa + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$7791 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a - a) \times (aaaa + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$77791 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a - a) \times (aaaaa + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$777791 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a - a) \times (aaaaaa + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$792 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - aaa + aa + a + a + a}{a}$$

$$9792 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - aaa - aaa + aa + a + a + a}{a}$$

$$99792 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa - aaa - aaa + aa + a + a + a}{a}$$

$$999792 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaaaa - aaa - aaa + aa + a + a + a}{a}$$

$$793 := \frac{(aaa + aa) \times (aa + a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$7293 := \frac{(aaaa + aa) \times (aa + a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$72293 := \frac{(aaaaa + aa) \times (aa + a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$722293 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aa) \times (aa + a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$794 := \frac{(aaa + aa) \times (aa + a + a) + (a + a) \times a}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$7294 := \frac{(aaaa + aa) \times (aa + a + a) + (a + a) \times a}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$72294 := \frac{(aaaaa + aa) \times (aa + a + a) + (a + a) \times a}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$722294 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aa) \times (aa + a + a) + (a + a) \times a}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$795 := \frac{(aaa + aa) \times (aa + a + a) + (a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$7295 := \frac{(aaaa + aa) \times (aa + a + a) + (a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$72295 := \frac{(aaaaa + aa) \times (aa + a + a) + (a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$722295 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aa) \times (aa + a + a) + (a + a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$796 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaa - aa \times (aa + a)}{a \times aa}$$

$$80796 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaaaa - aa \times (aa + a)}{a \times aa}$$

$$8080796 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaaaaaaa - aa \times (aa + a)}{a \times aa}$$

$$808080796 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaaaaaaaa - aa \times (aa + a)}{a \times aa}$$

$$797 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaa - aa \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$80797 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaaaa - aa \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$8080797 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaaaaaaa - aa \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$808080797 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaaaaaaaa - aa \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$798 := \frac{(aaa + aa + aa) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$6798 := \frac{(aaaa + aa + aa) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$66798 := \frac{(aaaaa + aa + aa) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$666798 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aa + aa) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$799 := \frac{(aaa - aa) \times (aa - a - a - a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$8799 := \frac{(aaaa - aa) \times (aa - a - a - a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$88799 := \frac{(aaaaa - aa) \times (aa - a - a - a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$888799 := \frac{(aaaaaa - aa) \times (aa - a - a - a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$800 := \frac{(aaa - aa) \times (aa - a - a - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$8800 := \frac{(aaaa - aa) \times (aa - a - a - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$88800 := \frac{(aaaaa - aa) \times (aa - a - a - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$888800 := \frac{(aaaaaa - aa) \times (aa - a - a - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$801 := \frac{(aaa - aa) \times (aa - a - a - a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$8801 := \frac{(aaaa - aa) \times (aa - a - a - a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$88801 := \frac{(aaaaa - aa) \times (aa - a - a - a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$888801 := \frac{(aaaaaa - aa) \times (aa - a - a - a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$802 := \frac{(aaa - aa) \times (aa - a - a - a) + a \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$8802 := \frac{(aaaa - aa) \times (aa - a - a - a) + a \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$88802 := \frac{(aaaaa - aa) \times (aa - a - a - a) + a \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$888802 := \frac{(aaaaaa - aa) \times (aa - a - a - a) + a \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$803 := \frac{(aaa - aa) \times (aa - a - a - a) + a \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$8803 := \frac{(aaaa - aa) \times (aa - a - a - a) + a \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$88803 := \frac{(aaaaa - aa) \times (aa - a - a - a) + a \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$888803 := \frac{(aaaaaa - aa) \times (aa - a - a - a) + a \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$804 := \frac{(aaa - aa) \times (aa - a - a - a) + a \times (a + a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$8804 := \frac{(aaaa - aa) \times (aa - a - a - a) + a \times (a + a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$88804 := \frac{(aaaaa - aa) \times (aa - a - a - a) + a \times (a + a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$888804 := \frac{(aaaaaa - aa) \times (aa - a - a - a) + a \times (a + a + a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$805 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaa - (a + a + a) \times aa}{aa \times a}$$

$$80805 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaaaa - (a + a + a) \times aa}{aa \times a}$$

$$8080805 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaaaaaaa - (a + a + a) \times aa}{aa \times a}$$

$$808080805 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaaaaaaaa - (a + a + a) \times aa}{aa \times a}$$

$$806 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaa - (a + a) \times aa}{aa \times a}$$

$$80806 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaaaa - (a + a) \times aa}{aa \times a}$$

$$8080806 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaaaaaaa - (a + a) \times aa}{aa \times a}$$

$$808080806 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaaaaaaaa - (a + a) \times aa}{aa \times a}$$

$$807 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaa - a \times aa}{aa \times a}$$

$$80807 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaaaa - a \times aa}{aa \times a}$$

$$8080807 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaaaaaaa - a \times aa}{aa \times a}$$

$$808080807 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaaaaaaaa - a \times aa}{aa \times a}$$

$$808 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaa}{aa \times a}$$

$$80808 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaaaa}{aa \times a}$$

$$8080808 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaaaaaaa}{aa \times a}$$

$$808080808 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaaaaaaaa}{aa \times a}$$

$$809 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaa + a \times aa}{aa \times a}$$

$$80809 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaaaa + a \times aa}{aa \times a}$$

$$8080809 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaaaaaaa + a \times aa}{aa \times a}$$

$$808080809 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaaaaaaaa + a \times aa}{aa \times a}$$

$$810 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaa + (a + a) \times aa}{aa \times a}$$

$$80810 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaaaa + (a + a) \times aa}{aa \times a}$$

$$8080810 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaaaaaaa + (a + a) \times aa}{aa \times a}$$

$$808080810 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaaaaaaaa + (a + a) \times aa}{aa \times a}$$

$$811 := \frac{(aaa - aa) \times (aa - a - a - a) + aa \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$8811 := \frac{(aaaa - aa) \times (aa - a - a - a) + aa \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$88811 := \frac{(aaaaa - aa) \times (aa - a - a - a) + aa \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$888811 := \frac{(aaaaaa - aa) \times (aa - a - a - a) + aa \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$812 := \frac{(aaa - aa) \times (aa - a - a - a) + (aa + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$8812 := \frac{(aaaa - aa) \times (aa - a - a - a) + (aa + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$88812 := \frac{(aaaaa - aa) \times (aa - a - a - a) + (aa + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$888812 := \frac{(aaaaaa - aa) \times (aa - a - a - a) + (aa + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$813 := \frac{(aa + aa) \times aaa - (a + a + a) \times a}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$8213 := \frac{(aaa + aaa) \times aaa - (a + a + a) \times a}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$82213 := \frac{(aaaa + aaaa) \times aaa - (a + a + a) \times a}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$822213 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaaaa) \times aaa - (a + a + a) \times a}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$814 := \frac{(aa + aa) \times aaa}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$8214 := \frac{(aaa + aaa) \times aaa}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$82214 := \frac{(aaaa + aaaa) \times aaa}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$822214 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaaaa) \times aaa}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$815 := \frac{(aa + aa) \times aaa + (a + a + a) \times a}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$8215 := \frac{(aaa + aaa) \times aaa + (a + a + a) \times a}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$82215 := \frac{(aaaa + aaaa) \times aaa + (a + a + a) \times a}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$822215 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaaaa) \times aaa + (a + a + a) \times a}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$816 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times (aaaa + aa)}{aa \times a}$$

$$80816 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times (aaaaaa + aa)}{aa \times a}$$

$$8080816 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times (aaaaaaaa + aa)}{aa \times a}$$

$$808080816 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times (aaaaaaaaaa + aa)}{aa \times a}$$

$$817 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaa + (aa - a - a) \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$80817 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaaaa + (aa - a - a) \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$8080817 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaaaaaaa + (aa - a - a) \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$808080817 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaaaaaaaa + (aa - a - a) \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$818 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaa + (aa - a) \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$80818 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaaaa + (aa - a) \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$8080818 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaaaaaaa + (aa - a) \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$808080818 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaaaaaaaa + (aa - a) \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$819 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaa + aa \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$80819 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaaaa + aa \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$8080819 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaaaaaaa + aa \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$808080819 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaaaaaaaa + aa \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$820 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaa + (aa + a) \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$80820 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaaaa + (aa + a) \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$8080820 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaaaaaaa + (aa + a) \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$808080820 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaaaaaaaa + (aa + a) \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$821 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaa + (aa + a + a) \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$80821 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaaaa + (aa + a + a) \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$8080821 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaaaaaaa + (aa + a + a) \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$808080821 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaaaaaaaa + (aa + a + a) \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$822 := \frac{(aaaa + aaa + aa) \times (a + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$8222 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaaa + aaa) \times (a + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$82222 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aaaaa + aaaa) \times (a + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$822222 := \frac{(aaaaaaa + aaaaaa + aaaaa) \times (a + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$823 := \frac{(aaa - aa) \times (aa - a - a - a) + (aa + aa + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$8823 := \frac{(aaaa - aa) \times (aa - a - a - a) + (aa + aa + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$88823 := \frac{(aaaaa - aa) \times (aa - a - a - a) + (aa + aa + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$888823 := \frac{(aaaaaa - aa) \times (aa - a - a - a) + (aa + aa + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$824 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times (aaaa + aa + aa)}{aa \times a}$$

$$80824 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times (aaaaaa + aa + aa)}{aa \times a}$$

$$8080824 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times (aaaaaaaa + aa + aa)}{aa \times a}$$

$$808080824 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times (aaaaaaaaaa + aa + aa)}{aa \times a}$$

$$825 := \frac{(aaaa - aa) \times (a + a + a)}{(a + a) \times (a + a)}$$

$$8325 := \frac{(aaaaa - aa) \times (a + a + a)}{(a + a) \times (a + a)}$$

$$83325 := \frac{(aaaaaa - aa) \times (a + a + a)}{(a + a) \times (a + a)}$$

$$833325 := \frac{(aaaaaaa - aa) \times (a + a + a)}{(a + a) \times (a + a)}$$

$$826 := \frac{aaaaa + a}{aa + a} - \frac{aaaa - aa}{aa}$$

$$925826 := \frac{aaaaaaaa + a}{aa + a} - \frac{aaaa - aa}{aa}$$

$$925925826 := \frac{aaaaaaaaaaa + a}{aa + a} - \frac{aaaa - aa}{aa}$$

$$925925925826 := \frac{aaaaaaaaaaaaa + a}{aa + a} - \frac{aaaa - aa}{aa}$$

$$827 := \frac{(aa + a + a + a + a) \times aaa - aa \times a}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$8327 := \frac{(aa + a + a + a + a) \times aaaa - aa \times a}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$83327 := \frac{(aa + a + a + a + a) \times aaaaa - aa \times a}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$833327 := \frac{(aa + a + a + a + a) \times aaaaaa - aa \times a}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$828 := \frac{(aa + aa + a) \times (aa + a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a \times a}$$

$$8028 := \frac{(aaa + aaa + a) \times (aa + a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a \times a}$$

$$80028 := \frac{(aaaa + aaaa + a) \times (aa + a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a \times a}$$

$$800028 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaaaa + a) \times (aa + a) \times (a + a + a)}{a \times a \times a}$$

$$829 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaa + (aa + aa - a) \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$80829 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaaa + (aa + aa - a) \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$8080829 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaaaaa + (aa + aa - a) \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$808080829 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times aaaaaaaaa + (aa + aa - a) \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$830 := \frac{((aa + a) \times (aa + a) + aa \times (a + a)) \times (aa - a)}{a \times a \times (a + a)}$$

$$6830 := \frac{((aaa + a) \times (aa + a) + aa \times (a + a)) \times (aa - a)}{a \times a \times (a + a)}$$

$$66830 := \frac{((aaaa + a) \times (aa + a) + aa \times (a + a)) \times (aa - a)}{a \times a \times (a + a)}$$

$$666830 := \frac{((aaaaa + a) \times (aa + a) + aa \times (a + a)) \times (aa - a)}{a \times a \times (a + a)}$$

$$831 := \frac{(aaaa - a - a - a) \times (a + a + a)}{(a + a) \times (a + a)}$$

$$8331 := \frac{(aaaaa - a - a - a) \times (a + a + a)}{(a + a) \times (a + a)}$$

$$83331 := \frac{(aaaaaa - a - a - a) \times (a + a + a)}{(a + a) \times (a + a)}$$

$$833331 := \frac{(aaaaaaa - a - a - a) \times (a + a + a)}{(a + a) \times (a + a)}$$

$$832 := \frac{(aa + a + a + a + a) \times aaa - a \times a}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$8332 := \frac{(aa + a + a + a + a) \times aaaa - a \times a}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$83332 := \frac{(aa + a + a + a + a) \times aaaaa - a \times a}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$833332 := \frac{(aa + a + a + a + a) \times aaaaaa - a \times a}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$833 := \frac{(aa + a + a + a + a) \times aaa + a \times a}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$8333 := \frac{(aa + a + a + a + a) \times aaaa + a \times a}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$83333 := \frac{(aa + a + a + a + a) \times aaaaa + a \times a}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$833333 := \frac{(aa + a + a + a + a) \times aaaaaa + a \times a}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 834 &:= \frac{(aaaa + a) \times (a + a + a)}{(a + a) \times (a + a)} & 838 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a + a + a) \times aaa + aa \times a}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 8334 &:= \frac{(aaaaa + a) \times (a + a + a)}{(a + a) \times (a + a)} & 8338 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a + a + a) \times aaaa + aa \times a}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 83334 &:= \frac{(aaaaaa + a) \times (a + a + a)}{(a + a) \times (a + a)} & 83338 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a + a + a) \times aaaaa + aa \times a}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 833334 &:= \frac{(aaaaaaa + a) \times (a + a + a)}{(a + a) \times (a + a)} & 833338 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a + a + a) \times aaaaaa + aa \times a}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 \\
 835 &:= \frac{(aaaa + a) \times (aa - a - a) + a \times (aa + a)}{a \times (aa + a)} & 839 &:= \frac{(aaa + a) \times (aa + a + a) + aaa \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 8335 &:= \frac{(aaaaa + a) \times (aa - a - a) + a \times (aa + a)}{a \times (aa + a)} & 1839 &:= \frac{(aaa + a) \times (aa + a + a) + aaaa \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 83335 &:= \frac{(aaaaaa + a) \times (aa - a - a) + a \times (aa + a)}{a \times (aa + a)} & 11839 &:= \frac{(aaa + a) \times (aa + a + a) + aaaaa \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 833335 &:= \frac{(aaaaaaa + a) \times (aa - a - a) + a \times (aa + a)}{a \times (aa + a)} & 111839 &:= \frac{(aaa + a) \times (aa + a + a) + aaaaaa \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 \\
 836 &:= \frac{(aaa + a + a + a) \times (aa + aa)}{(a + a + a) \times a} & 840 &:= \frac{(aaa + aaa - aa - a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a} \\
 8436 &:= \frac{(aaa + a + a + a) \times (aaa + aaa)}{(a + a + a) \times a} & 7840 &:= \frac{(aaa + aaa - aa - a) \times (aaa + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a} \\
 84436 &:= \frac{(aaa + a + a + a) \times (aaaa + aaaa)}{(a + a + a) \times a} & 77840 &:= \frac{(aaa + aaa - aa - a) \times (aaaa + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a} \\
 844436 &:= \frac{(aaa + a + a + a) \times (aaaaa + aaaaa)}{(a + a + a) \times a} & 777840 &:= \frac{(aaa + aaa - aa - a) \times (aaaaa + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a} \\
 \\
 837 &:= \frac{(aaa - a) \times aa + (aaa + aaa + aa - a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} & 841 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a + a + a) \times (aaa + a) + a \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 2837 &:= \frac{(aaa - a) \times aa + (aaaa + aaaa + aa - a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} & 8341 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a + a + a) \times (aaaa + a) + a \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 22837 &:= \frac{(aaa - a) \times aa + (aaaaa + aaaaa + aa - a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} & 83341 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a + a + a) \times (aaaaa + a) + a \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\
 222837 &:= \frac{(aaa - a) \times aa + (aaaaaa + aaaaaa + aa - a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} & 833341 &:= \frac{(aa + a + a + a + a) \times (aaaaaa + a) + a \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$842 := \frac{(aaa + aa) \times (aa + a) + (aaa - a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$6842 := \frac{(aaaa + aa) \times (aa + a) + (aaa - a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$66842 := \frac{(aaaaa + aa) \times (aa + a) + (aaa - a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$666842 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aa) \times (aa + a) + (aaa - a) \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$843 := \frac{(aaa + aa) \times (aa + a) + aaa \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$6843 := \frac{(aaaa + aa) \times (aa + a) + aaa \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$66843 := \frac{(aaaaa + aa) \times (aa + a) + aaa \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$666843 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aa) \times (aa + a) + aaa \times (a + a)}{(a + a) \times a}$$

$$844 := \frac{(aaa + aaa - aa) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$4844 := \frac{(aaaa + aaa - aa) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$44844 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaa - aa) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$444844 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aaa - aa) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$845 := \frac{((aa + a) \times aa - a \times (a + a)) \times (aa + a + a)}{a \times a \times (a + a)}$$

$$8645 := \frac{((aa + a) \times aaa - a \times (a + a)) \times (aa + a + a)}{a \times a \times (a + a)}$$

$$86645 := \frac{((aa + a) \times aaaa - a \times (a + a)) \times (aa + a + a)}{a \times a \times (a + a)}$$

$$866645 := \frac{((aa + a) \times aaaaa - a \times (a + a)) \times (aa + a + a)}{a \times a \times (a + a)}$$

$$846 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a - a) \times aa \times aa - a \times a \times a}{a \times a \times a}$$

$$8546 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a - a) \times aaa \times aa - a \times a \times a}{a \times a \times a}$$

$$85546 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a - a) \times aaaa \times aa - a \times a \times a}{a \times a \times a}$$

$$855546 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a - a) \times aaaaa \times aa - a \times a \times a}{a \times a \times a}$$

$$847 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a - a) \times aa \times aa}{a \times a \times a}$$

$$8547 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a - a) \times aaa \times aa}{a \times a \times a}$$

$$85547 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a - a) \times aaaa \times aa}{a \times a \times a}$$

$$855547 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a - a) \times aaaaa \times aa}{a \times a \times a}$$

$$848 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a - a) \times aa \times aa + a \times a \times a}{a \times a \times a}$$

$$8548 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a - a) \times aaa \times aa + a \times a \times a}{a \times a \times a}$$

$$85548 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a - a) \times aaaa \times aa + a \times a \times a}{a \times a \times a}$$

$$855548 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a - a) \times aaaaa \times aa + a \times a \times a}{a \times a \times a}$$

$$849 := \frac{(aa + aa + a) \times aaa - (a + a) \times (a + a + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$8249 := \frac{(aaa + aaa + a) \times aaa - (a + a) \times (a + a + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$82249 := \frac{(aaaa + aaaa + a) \times aaa - (a + a) \times (a + a + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$822249 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaaaa + a) \times aaa - (a + a) \times (a + a + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$850 := \frac{(aa + aa + a) \times aaa - a \times (a + a + a)}{a \times (a + a + a)}$$

$$8250 := \frac{(aaa + aaa + a) \times aaa - a \times (a + a + a)}{a \times (a + a + a)}$$

$$82250 := \frac{(aaaa + aaaa + a) \times aaa - a \times (a + a + a)}{a \times (a + a + a)}$$

$$822250 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaaaa + a) \times aaa - a \times (a + a + a)}{a \times (a + a + a)}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 851 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + a) \times aaa}{a \times (a + a + a)} \\
 8251 &:= \frac{(aaa + aaa + a) \times aaa}{a \times (a + a + a)} \\
 82251 &:= \frac{(aaaa + aaaa + a) \times aaa}{a \times (a + a + a)} \\
 822251 &:= \frac{(aaaaa + aaaaa + a) \times aaa}{a \times (a + a + a)} \\
 \\
 852 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + a) \times aaa + a \times (a + a + a)}{a \times (a + a + a)} \\
 8252 &:= \frac{(aaa + aaa + a) \times aaa + a \times (a + a + a)}{a \times (a + a + a)} \\
 82252 &:= \frac{(aaaa + aaaa + a) \times aaa + a \times (a + a + a)}{a \times (a + a + a)} \\
 822252 &:= \frac{(aaaaa + aaaaa + a) \times aaa + a \times (a + a + a)}{a \times (a + a + a)} \\
 \\
 853 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + a) \times aaa + (a + a) \times (a + a + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a} \\
 8253 &:= \frac{(aaa + aaa + a) \times aaa + (a + a) \times (a + a + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a} \\
 82253 &:= \frac{(aaaa + aaaa + a) \times aaa + (a + a) \times (a + a + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a} \\
 822253 &:= \frac{(aaaaa + aaaaa + a) \times aaa + (a + a) \times (a + a + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a} \\
 \\
 854 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - aa - aa - aa - a - a}{a} \\
 9854 &:= \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - aaa - aa - aa - aa - a - a}{a} \\
 99854 &:= \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaaa - aaa - aa - aa - aa - a - a}{a} \\
 999854 &:= \frac{aaaaaaaa - aaaaaa - aaa - aa - aa - aa - a - a}{a} \\
 \\
 855 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - aa - aa - aa - a}{a} \\
 9855 &:= \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - aaa - aa - aa - aa - a}{a} \\
 99855 &:= \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaaa - aaa - aa - aa - aa - a}{a} \\
 999855 &:= \frac{aaaaaaaa - aaaaaa - aaa - aa - aa - aa - a}{a}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 856 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - aa - aa - aa}{a} \\
 9856 &:= \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - aaa - aa - aa - aa}{a} \\
 99856 &:= \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaaa - aaa - aa - aa - aa}{a} \\
 999856 &:= \frac{aaaaaaaa - aaaaaa - aaa - aa - aa - aa}{a} \\
 \\
 857 &:= \frac{(aaa - aa - aa - aa) \times aa - a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 9657 &:= \frac{(aaa - aa - aa - aa) \times aaa - a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 86657 &:= \frac{(aaa - aa - aa - aa) \times aaaa - a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 866657 &:= \frac{(aaa - aa - aa - aa) \times aaaaa - a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 \\
 858 &:= \frac{(aaa - aa - aa - aa) \times aa}{a \times a} \\
 9658 &:= \frac{(aaa - aa - aa - aa) \times aaa}{a \times a} \\
 86658 &:= \frac{(aaa - aa - aa - aa) \times aaaa}{a \times a} \\
 866658 &:= \frac{(aaa - aa - aa - aa) \times aaaaa}{a \times a} \\
 \\
 859 &:= \frac{(aaa - aa - aa - aa) \times aa + a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 8659 &:= \frac{(aaa - aa - aa - aa) \times aaa + a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 86659 &:= \frac{(aaa - aa - aa - aa) \times aaaa + a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 866659 &:= \frac{(aaa - aa - aa - aa) \times aaaaa + a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 \\
 860 &:= \frac{(aaa - aa - aa - a - a - a) \times (aaa - a)}{aa \times a} \\
 9860 &:= \frac{(aaaa - aaa - aa - a - a - a) \times (aaa - a)}{aa \times a} \\
 99860 &:= \frac{(aaaaa - aaaa - aa - a - a - a) \times (aaa - a)}{aa \times a} \\
 999860 &:= \frac{(aaaaaaa - aaaaa - aa - a - a - a) \times (aaa - a)}{aa \times a}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 861 &:= \frac{(aaa + aa + a) \times (aa + aa - a)}{(a + a + a) \times a} \\
 7861 &:= \frac{(aaaa + aa + a) \times (aa + aa - a)}{(a + a + a) \times a} \\
 77861 &:= \frac{(aaaaa + aa + a) \times (aa + aa - a)}{(a + a + a) \times a} \\
 777861 &:= \frac{(aaaaaa + aa + a) \times (aa + aa - a)}{(a + a + a) \times a} \\
 \\
 862 &:= \frac{(aa + aa + a) \times aaa + aa \times (a + a + a)}{a \times (a + a + a)} \\
 8262 &:= \frac{(aaa + aaa + a) \times aaa + aa \times (a + a + a)}{a \times (a + a + a)} \\
 82262 &:= \frac{(aaaa + aaaa + a) \times aaa + aa \times (a + a + a)}{a \times (a + a + a)} \\
 822262 &:= \frac{(aaaaa + aaaaa + a) \times aaa + aa \times (a + a + a)}{a \times (a + a + a)} \\
 \\
 863 &:= \frac{(aa + a) \times (aa + a) \times (aa + a) - (a + a) \times a \times a}{(a + a) \times a \times a} \\
 8063 &:= \frac{(aaa + a) \times (aa + a) \times (aa + a) - (a + a) \times a \times a}{(a + a) \times a \times a} \\
 80063 &:= \frac{(aaaa + a) \times (aa + a) \times (aa + a) - (a + a) \times a \times a}{(a + a) \times a \times a} \\
 800063 &:= \frac{(aaaaa + a) \times (aa + a) \times (aa + a) - (a + a) \times a \times a}{(a + a) \times a \times a} \\
 \\
 864 &:= \frac{(aa + a) \times (aa + a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a \times a} \\
 8064 &:= \frac{(aaa + a) \times (aa + a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a \times a} \\
 80064 &:= \frac{(aaaa + a) \times (aa + a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a \times a} \\
 800064 &:= \frac{(aaaaa + a) \times (aa + a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a \times a}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 865 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - aa - aa - a - a}{a} \\
 9865 &:= \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - aaa - aa - aa - a - a}{a} \\
 99865 &:= \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa - aaa - aa - aa - a - a}{a} \\
 999865 &:= \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaaaa - aaa - aa - aa - a - a}{a} \\
 \\
 866 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - aa - aa - a}{a} \\
 9866 &:= \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - aaa - aa - aa - a}{a} \\
 99866 &:= \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa - aaa - aa - aa - a}{a} \\
 999866 &:= \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaaaa - aaa - aa - aa - a}{a} \\
 \\
 867 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - aa - aa}{a} \\
 9867 &:= \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - aaa - aa - aa}{a} \\
 99867 &:= \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa - aaa - aa - aa}{a} \\
 999867 &:= \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaaaa - aaa - aa - aa}{a} \\
 \\
 868 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - aa - aa + a}{a} \\
 9868 &:= \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - aaa - aa - aa + a}{a} \\
 99868 &:= \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa - aaa - aa - aa + a}{a} \\
 999868 &:= \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaaaa - aaa - aa - aa + a}{a} \\
 \\
 869 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - aa - aa + a + a}{a} \\
 9869 &:= \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - aaa - aa - aa + a + a}{a} \\
 99869 &:= \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa - aaa - aa - aa + a + a}{a} \\
 999869 &:= \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaaaa - aaa - aa - aa + a + a}{a}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$870 := \frac{(aaa - a - a) \times (aa - a - a - a) - a \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$8870 := \frac{(aaaa - a - a) \times (aa - a - a - a) - a \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$88870 := \frac{(aaaaa - a - a) \times (aa - a - a - a) - a \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$888870 := \frac{(aaaaaa - a - a) \times (aa - a - a - a) - a \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

$$871 := \frac{(aaa - a - a) \times (aa - a - a - a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$8871 := \frac{(aaaa - a - a) \times (aa - a - a - a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$88871 := \frac{(aaaaa - a - a) \times (aa - a - a - a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$888871 := \frac{(aaaaaa - a - a) \times (aa - a - a - a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$872 := \frac{(aaa - a - a) \times (aa - a - a - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$8872 := \frac{(aaaa - a - a) \times (aa - a - a - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$88872 := \frac{(aaaaa - a - a) \times (aa - a - a - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$888872 := \frac{(aaaaaa - a - a) \times (aa - a - a - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$873 := \frac{(aaa - a - a) \times (aa - a - a - a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$8873 := \frac{(aaaa - a - a) \times (aa - a - a - a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$88873 := \frac{(aaaaa - a - a) \times (aa - a - a - a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$888873 := \frac{(aaaaaa - a - a) \times (aa - a - a - a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$874 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - aa - a - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$9874 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - aaa - aa - a - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$99874 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa - aaaa - aa - a - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$999874 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaaaa - aaaa - aa - a - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$875 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - aa - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$9875 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - aaa - aa - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$99875 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa - aaaa - aa - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$999875 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaaaa - aaaa - aa - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$876 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - aa - a - a}{a}$$

$$9876 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - aaa - aa - a - a}{a}$$

$$99876 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa - aaaa - aa - a - a}{a}$$

$$999876 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaaaa - aaaa - aa - a - a}{a}$$

$$877 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - aa - a}{a}$$

$$9877 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - aaa - aa - a}{a}$$

$$99877 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa - aaaa - aa - a}{a}$$

$$999877 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaaaa - aaaa - aa - a}{a}$$

$$878 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - aa}{a}$$

$$9878 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - aaa - aa}{a}$$

$$99878 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa - aaaa - aa}{a}$$

$$999878 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaaaa - aaaa - aa}{a}$$

$$879 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - aa + a}{a}$$

$$9879 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - aaa - aa + a}{a}$$

$$99879 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa - aaaa - aa + a}{a}$$

$$999879 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaaaa - aaaa - aa + a}{a}$$

$$880 := \frac{(aaa - a) \times (aa - a - a - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$8880 := \frac{(aaaa - a) \times (aa - a - a - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$88880 := \frac{(aaaaa - a) \times (aa - a - a - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$888880 := \frac{(aaaaaa - a) \times (aa - a - a - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$881 := \frac{(aaa - a) \times (aa - a - a - a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$8881 := \frac{(aaaa - a) \times (aa - a - a - a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$88881 := \frac{(aaaaa - a) \times (aa - a - a - a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$888881 := \frac{(aaaaaa - a) \times (aa - a - a - a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$882 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - aa + a + a + a + a}{a}$$

$$9882 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - aaa - aa + a + a + a + a}{a}$$

$$99882 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa - aaaa - aa + a + a + a + a}{a}$$

$$999882 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaaaa - aaaa - aa + a + a + a + a}{a}$$

$$883 := \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times (aaa - a) + (a + a + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$8583 := \frac{(aaa - aa - aa - aa) \times (aaa - a) + (a + a + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$85583 := \frac{(aaaa - aaa - aaa - aaa) \times (aaa - a) + (a + a + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$855583 := \frac{(aaaaa - aaaa - aaaa - aaaa) \times (aaa - a) + (a + a + a) \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$884 := \frac{(aaa + aaa - a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$4884 := \frac{(aaaa + aaa - a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$44884 := \frac{(aaaaa + aaa - a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$444884 := \frac{(aaaaaa + aaa - a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

$$885 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - a - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$9885 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - aaa - a - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$99885 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa - aaaa - a - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$999885 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaaaa - aaaa - a - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$886 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$9886 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - aaa - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$99886 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa - aaaa - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$999886 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaaaa - aaaa - a - a - a}{a}$$

$$887 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - a - a}{a}$$

$$9887 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - aaa - a - a}{a}$$

$$99887 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa - aaaa - a - a}{a}$$

$$999887 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaaaa - aaaa - a - a}{a}$$

$$888 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa - a}{a}$$

$$9888 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - aaa - a}{a}$$

$$99888 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa - aaaa - a}{a}$$

$$999888 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaaaa - aaaa - a}{a}$$

$$889 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa}{a}$$

$$9889 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - aaa}{a}$$

$$99889 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa - aaa}{a}$$

$$999889 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaaaa - aaa}{a}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 890 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa + a}{a} \\
 9890 &:= \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - aaa + a}{a} \\
 99890 &:= \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa - aaa + a}{a} \\
 999890 &:= \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaaaa - aaa + a}{a} \\
 \\
 891 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa + a + a}{a} \\
 9891 &:= \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - aaa + a + a}{a} \\
 99891 &:= \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa - aaa + a + a}{a} \\
 999891 &:= \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaaaa - aaa + a + a}{a} \\
 \\
 892 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa + a + a + a}{a} \\
 9892 &:= \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - aaa + a + a + a}{a} \\
 99892 &:= \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa - aaa + a + a + a}{a} \\
 999892 &:= \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaaaa - aaa + a + a + a}{a} \\
 \\
 893 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa + a + a + a + a}{a} \\
 9893 &:= \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - aaa + a + a + a + a}{a} \\
 99893 &:= \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa - aaa + a + a + a + a}{a} \\
 999893 &:= \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaaaa - aaa + a + a + a + a}{a} \\
 \\
 894 &:= \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times (aaa + a) - a \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 8894 &:= \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times (aaaa + a) - a \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 88894 &:= \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times (aaaaa + a) - a \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 888894 &:= \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times (aaaaaa + a) - a \times (a + a)}{a \times a}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 895 &:= \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times (aaa + a) - a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 8895 &:= \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times (aaaa + a) - a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 88895 &:= \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times (aaaaa + a) - a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 888895 &:= \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times (aaaaaa + a) - a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 \\
 896 &:= \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times (aaa + a)}{a \times a} \\
 8896 &:= \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times (aaaa + a)}{a \times a} \\
 88896 &:= \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times (aaaaa + a)}{a \times a} \\
 888896 &:= \frac{(aa - a - a - a) \times (aaaaaa + a)}{a \times a} \\
 \\
 897 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa + aa - a - a - a}{a} \\
 9897 &:= \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - aaa + aa - a - a - a}{a} \\
 99897 &:= \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa - aaa + aa - a - a - a}{a} \\
 999897 &:= \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaaaa - aaa + aa - a - a - a}{a} \\
 \\
 898 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa + aa - a - a}{a} \\
 9898 &:= \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - aaa + aa - a - a}{a} \\
 99898 &:= \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa - aaa + aa - a - a}{a} \\
 999898 &:= \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaaaa - aaa + aa - a - a}{a} \\
 \\
 899 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa + aa - a}{a} \\
 9899 &:= \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - aaa + aa - a}{a} \\
 99899 &:= \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa - aaa + aa - a}{a} \\
 999899 &:= \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaaaa - aaa + aa - a}{a}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$900 := \frac{(aaa - aa) \times (aa - a - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$9900 := \frac{(aaaa - aa) \times (aa - a - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$99900 := \frac{(aaaaa - aa) \times (aa - a - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$999900 := \frac{(aaaaaa - aa) \times (aa - a - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$901 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa + aa + a}{a}$$

$$9901 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - aaa + aa + a}{a}$$

$$99901 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa - aaa + aa + a}{a}$$

$$999901 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaaaa - aaa + aa + a}{a}$$

$$902 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa + aa + a + a}{a}$$

$$9902 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - aaa + aa + a + a}{a}$$

$$99902 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa - aaa + aa + a + a}{a}$$

$$999902 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaaaa - aaa + aa + a + a}{a}$$

$$903 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa + aa + a + a + a}{a}$$

$$9903 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - aaa + aa + a + a + a}{a}$$

$$99903 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa - aaa + aa + a + a + a}{a}$$

$$999903 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaaaa - aaa + aa + a + a + a}{a}$$

$$904 := \frac{(aaa + a + a) \times (aa - a - a - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$8904 := \frac{(aaaa + a + a) \times (aa - a - a - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$88904 := \frac{(aaaaa + a + a) \times (aa - a - a - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$888904 := \frac{(aaaaaa + a + a) \times (aa - a - a - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$905 := \frac{(aaa + a + a) \times (aa - a - a - a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$8905 := \frac{(aaaa + a + a) \times (aa - a - a - a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$88905 := \frac{(aaaaa + a + a) \times (aa - a - a - a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$888905 := \frac{(aaaaaa + a + a) \times (aa - a - a - a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$906 := \frac{aaaa \times (aa - a - a) - (a + a + a) \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$90906 := \frac{aaaaaa \times (aa - a - a) - (a + a + a) \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$9090906 := \frac{aaaaaaaa \times (aa - a - a) - (a + a + a) \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$909090906 := \frac{aaaaaaaaaa \times (aa - a - a) - (a + a + a) \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$907 := \frac{aaaa \times (aa - a - a) - (a + a) \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$90907 := \frac{aaaaaa \times (aa - a - a) - (a + a) \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$9090907 := \frac{aaaaaaaa \times (aa - a - a) - (a + a) \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$909090907 := \frac{aaaaaaaaaa \times (aa - a - a) - (a + a) \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$908 := \frac{aaaa \times (aa - a - a) - a \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$90908 := \frac{aaaaaa \times (aa - a - a) - a \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$9090908 := \frac{aaaaaaaa \times (aa - a - a) - a \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$909090908 := \frac{aaaaaaaaaa \times (aa - a - a) - a \times aa}{a \times aa}$$

$$909 := \frac{aaaa \times (aa - a - a)}{a \times aa}$$

$$90909 := \frac{aaaaaa \times (aa - a - a)}{a \times aa}$$

$$9090909 := \frac{aaaaaaaa \times (aa - a - a)}{a \times aa}$$

$$909090909 := \frac{aaaaaaaaaa \times (aa - a - a)}{a \times aa}$$

$$910 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa + aa + aa - a}{a}$$

$$9910 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - aaa + aa + aa - a}{a}$$

$$99910 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa - aaa + aa + aa - a}{a}$$

$$999910 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaaaa - aaa + aa + aa - a}{a}$$

$$911 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa + aa + aa}{a}$$

$$9911 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - aaa + aa + aa}{a}$$

$$99911 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa - aaa + aa + aa}{a}$$

$$999911 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaaaa - aaa + aa + aa}{a}$$

$$912 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa + aa + aa + a}{a}$$

$$9912 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - aaa + aa + aa + a}{a}$$

$$99912 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa - aaa + aa + aa + a}{a}$$

$$999912 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaaaa - aaa + aa + aa + a}{a}$$

$$913 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa + aa + aa + a + a}{a}$$

$$9913 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - aaa + aa + aa + a + a}{a}$$

$$99913 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa - aaa + aa + aa + a + a}{a}$$

$$999913 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaaaa - aaa + aa + aa + a + a}{a}$$

$$914 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aaa + aa + aa + a + a + a}{a}$$

$$9914 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - aaa + aa + aa + a + a + a}{a}$$

$$99914 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa - aaa + aa + aa + a + a + a}{a}$$

$$999914 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaaaa - aaa + aa + aa + a + a + a}{a}$$

$$915 := \frac{aaaaa + a}{aa + a} - \frac{aa}{a}$$

$$925915 := \frac{aaaaaaaa + a}{aa + a} - \frac{aa}{a}$$

$$925925915 := \frac{aaaaaaaaaaaa + a}{aa + a} - \frac{aa}{a}$$

$$925925925915 := \frac{aaaaaaaaaaaaaaaa + a}{aa + a} - \frac{aa}{a}$$

$$916 := \frac{aaaaa + a}{aa + a} - \frac{aa - a}{a}$$

$$925916 := \frac{aaaaaaaa + a}{aa + a} - \frac{aa - a}{a}$$

$$925925916 := \frac{aaaaaaaaaaaa + a}{aa + a} - \frac{aa - a}{a}$$

$$925925925916 := \frac{aaaaaaaaaaaaaaaa + a}{aa + a} - \frac{aa - a}{a}$$

$$917 := \frac{(aaa - aa + a + a) \times (aa - a - a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$9917 := \frac{(aaaa - aa + a + a) \times (aa - a - a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$99917 := \frac{(aaaaa - aa + a + a) \times (aa - a - a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$999917 := \frac{(aaaaaa - aa + a + a) \times (aa - a - a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$918 := \frac{(aaa - aa + a + a) \times (aa - a - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$9918 := \frac{(aaaa - aa + a + a) \times (aa - a - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$99918 := \frac{(aaaaa - aa + a + a) \times (aa - a - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$999918 := \frac{(aaaaaa - aa + a + a) \times (aa - a - a)}{a \times a}$$

$$919 := \frac{(aaa - aa + a + a) \times (aa - a - a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$9919 := \frac{(aaaa - aa + a + a) \times (aa - a - a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$99919 := \frac{(aaaaa - aa + a + a) \times (aa - a - a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$999919 := \frac{(aaaaaa - aa + a + a) \times (aa - a - a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 920 &:= \frac{aaaa \times (aa - a - a) + aa \times aa}{a \times aa} \\
 90920 &:= \frac{aaaaaa \times (aa - a - a) + aa \times aa}{a \times aa} \\
 9090920 &:= \frac{aaaaaaaa \times (aa - a - a) + aa \times aa}{a \times aa} \\
 909090920 &:= \frac{aaaaaaaaaa \times (aa - a - a) + aa \times aa}{a \times aa} \\
 \\
 921 &:= \frac{aaaa \times (aa - a - a) + aa \times (aa + a)}{a \times aa} \\
 90921 &:= \frac{aaaaaa \times (aa - a - a) + aa \times (aa + a)}{a \times aa} \\
 9090921 &:= \frac{aaaaaaaa \times (aa - a - a) + aa \times (aa + a)}{a \times aa} \\
 909090921 &:= \frac{aaaaaaaaaa \times (aa - a - a) + aa \times (aa + a)}{a \times aa} \\
 \\
 922 &:= \frac{aaaa \times (aa - a - a) + aa \times (aa + a + a)}{a \times aa} \\
 90922 &:= \frac{aaaaaa \times (aa - a - a) + aa \times (aa + a + a)}{a \times aa} \\
 9090922 &:= \frac{aaaaaaaa \times (aa - a - a) + aa \times (aa + a + a)}{a \times aa} \\
 909090922 &:= \frac{aaaaaaaaaa \times (aa - a - a) + aa \times (aa + a + a)}{a \times aa} \\
 \\
 923 &:= \frac{aaaaa - aa - aa - aa - a - a}{aa + a} \\
 925923 &:= \frac{aaaaaaaa - aa - aa - aa - a - a}{aa + a} \\
 925925923 &:= \frac{aaaaaaaaaaaa - aa - aa - aa - a - a}{aa + a} \\
 925925925923 &:= \frac{aaaaaaaaaaaaaaaa - aa - aa - aa - a - a}{aa + a} \\
 \\
 924 &:= \frac{aaaaa - aa - aa - a}{aa + a} \\
 925924 &:= \frac{aaaaaaaa - aa - aa - a}{aa + a} \\
 925925924 &:= \frac{aaaaaaaaaaaa - aa - aa - a}{aa + a} \\
 925925925924 &:= \frac{aaaaaaaaaaaaaaaa - aa - aa - a}{aa + a}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 925 &:= \frac{aaaaa - aa}{aa + a} \\
 925925 &:= \frac{aaaaaaaa - aa}{aa + a} \\
 925925925 &:= \frac{aaaaaaaaaaaa - aa}{aa + a} \\
 925925925925 &:= \frac{aaaaaaaaaaaaaaaa - aa}{aa + a} \\
 \\
 926 &:= \frac{aaaaa + a}{aa + a} \\
 925926 &:= \frac{aaaaaaaa + a}{aa + a} \\
 925925926 &:= \frac{aaaaaaaaaaaa + a}{aa + a} \\
 925925925926 &:= \frac{aaaaaaaaaaaaaaaa + a}{aa + a} \\
 \\
 927 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aa + a + a}{aa + a} \\
 925927 &:= \frac{aaaaaaaa + aa + a + a}{aa + a} \\
 925925927 &:= \frac{aaaaaaaaaaaa + aa + a + a}{aa + a} \\
 925925925927 &:= \frac{aaaaaaaaaaaaaaaa + aa + a + a}{aa + a} \\
 \\
 928 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aa + aa + a + a + a}{aa + a} \\
 9278 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aaa + aaa + a + a + a}{aa + a} \\
 92778 &:= \frac{aaaaaaa + aaaa + aaaa + a + a + a}{aa + a} \\
 927778 &:= \frac{aaaaaaaa + aaaaa + aaaaa + a + a + a}{aa + a} \\
 \\
 929 &:= \frac{(aaaa + aa) \times (aa - a - a) + aa \times aa}{a \times aa} \\
 90929 &:= \frac{(aaaaaa + aa) \times (aa - a - a) + aa \times aa}{a \times aa} \\
 9090929 &:= \frac{(aaaaaaaa + aa) \times (aa - a - a) + aa \times aa}{a \times aa} \\
 909090929 &:= \frac{(aaaaaaaaaaaa + aa) \times (aa - a - a) + aa \times aa}{a \times aa}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 930 &:= \frac{aaaaa - aa}{aa + a} + \frac{aa - a}{a + a} \\ 925930 &:= \frac{aaaaaaaa - aa}{aa + a} + \frac{aa - a}{a + a} \\ 925925930 &:= \frac{aaaaaaaaaaaa - aa}{aa + a} + \frac{aa - a}{a + a} \\ 925925925930 &:= \frac{aaaaaaaaaaaaaaaa - aa}{aa + a} + \frac{aa - a}{a + a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 931 &:= \frac{(aaa + aa + aa) \times (aa + a + a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\ 7931 &:= \frac{(aaaa + aa + aa) \times (aa + a + a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\ 77931 &:= \frac{(aaaaa + aa + aa) \times (aa + a + a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \\ 777931 &:= \frac{(aaaaaa + aa + aa) \times (aa + a + a + a)}{(a + a) \times a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 932 &:= \frac{(aaa \times (a + a) + aa \times a) \times (a + a + a + a)}{a \times a \times a} \\ 8932 &:= \frac{(aaaa \times (a + a) + aa \times a) \times (a + a + a + a)}{a \times a \times a} \\ 88932 &:= \frac{(aaaaa \times (a + a) + aa \times a) \times (a + a + a + a)}{a \times a \times a} \\ 888932 &:= \frac{(aaaaaa \times (a + a) + aa \times a) \times (a + a + a + a)}{a \times a \times a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 933 &:= \frac{(aaaa + aa) \times (aa - a) - (aa + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times (aa + a)} \\ 925933 &:= \frac{(aaaaaaaa + aa) \times (aa - a) - (aa + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times (aa + a)} \\ 925925933 &:= \frac{(aaaaaaaaaaaa + aa) \times (aa - a) - (aa + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times (aa + a)} \\ 925925925933 &:= \frac{(aaaaaaaaaaaaaaaa + aa) \times (aa - a) - (aa + a) \times (a + a)}{a \times (aa + a)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 934 &:= \frac{(aaaa + aa) \times (aa - a) - (aa + a) \times a}{a \times (aa + a)} \\ 925934 &:= \frac{(aaaaaaaa + aa) \times (aa - a) - (aa + a) \times a}{a \times (aa + a)} \\ 925925934 &:= \frac{(aaaaaaaaaaaa + aa) \times (aa - a) - (aa + a) \times a}{a \times (aa + a)} \\ 925925925934 &:= \frac{(aaaaaaaaaaaaaaaa + aa) \times (aa - a) - (aa + a) \times a}{a \times (aa + a)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 935 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aaa - a - a}{aa + a} \\ 925935 &:= \frac{aaaaaaaa + aaa - a - a}{aa + a} \\ 925925935 &:= \frac{aaaaaaaaaaaa + aaa - a - a}{aa + a} \\ 925925925935 &:= \frac{aaaaaaaaaaaaaaaa + aaa - a - a}{aa + a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 936 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aaa + aa - a}{aa + a} \\ 9361 &:= \frac{aaaaaa + aaaa + aaa - a}{aa + a} \\ 93611 &:= \frac{aaaaaaa + aaaaa + aaaa - a}{aa + a} \\ 936111 &:= \frac{aaaaaaaa + aaaaaa + aaaaa - a}{aa + a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 937 &:= \frac{aaaaa + aaa + aa + aa}{aa + a} \\ 925937 &:= \frac{aaaaaaaa + aaa + aa + aa}{aa + a} \\ 925925937 &:= \frac{aaaaaaaaaaaa + aaa + aa + aa}{aa + a} \\ 925925925937 &:= \frac{aaaaaaaaaaaaaaaa + aaa + aa + aa}{aa + a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 938 &:= \frac{(aaa + aa + aa + a) \times (aa + aa - a)}{(a + a + a) \times a} \\ 7938 &:= \frac{(aaaa + aa + aa + a) \times (aa + aa - a)}{(a + a + a) \times a} \\ 77938 &:= \frac{(aaaaa + aa + aa + a) \times (aa + aa - a)}{(a + a + a) \times a} \\ 777938 &:= \frac{(aaaaaa + aa + aa + a) \times (aa + aa - a)}{(a + a + a) \times a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 939 &:= \frac{(aaa - aa - a - a - a - a - a) \times (aa - a) - aa \times a}{a \times a} \\ 9939 &:= \frac{(aaaa - aaa - a - a - a - a - a) \times (aa - a) - aa \times a}{a \times a} \\ 99939 &:= \frac{(aaaaa - aaaa - a - a - a - a - a) \times (aa - a) - aa \times a}{a \times a} \\ 999939 &:= \frac{(aaaaaa - aaaaa - a - a - a - a - a) \times (aa - a) - aa \times a}{a \times a} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 940 &:= \frac{(aaaa + aaa) \times (aa - a)}{a \times (aa + a + a)} \\
 9400 &:= \frac{(aaaa + aaa) \times (aaa - aa)}{a \times (aa + a + a)} \\
 94000 &:= \frac{(aaaa + aaa) \times (aaaa - aaa)}{a \times (aa + a + a)} \\
 940000 &:= \frac{(aaaa + aaa) \times (aaaaa - aaaa)}{a \times (aa + a + a)} \\
 \\
 941 &:= \frac{(aaaa + a) \times aa + a \times a}{(aa + a + a) \times a} \\
 94111 &:= \frac{(aaaaaa + aaa) \times aa + a \times a}{(aa + a + a) \times a} \\
 9411111 &:= \frac{(aaaaaaaa + aaaaa) \times aa + a \times a}{(aa + a + a) \times a} \\
 941111111 &:= \frac{(aaaaaaaaaaa + aaaaaaa) \times aa + a \times a}{(aa + a + a) \times a} \\
 \\
 942 &:= \frac{(aaaa - a) \times (aaa + a) + (a + a) \times (aa + a)}{aa \times (aa + a)} \\
 94182 &:= \frac{(aaaaaa - aaa) \times (aaa + a) + (a + a) \times (aa + a)}{aa \times (aa + a)} \\
 9418182 &:= \frac{(aaaaaaaa - aaaaa) \times (aaa + a) + (a + a) \times (aa + a)}{aa \times (aa + a)} \\
 941818182 &:= \frac{(aaaaaaaaaaa - aaaaaaa) \times (aaa + a) + (a + a) \times (aa + a)}{aa \times (aa + a)} \\
 \\
 943 &:= \frac{(aaa + aa + a) \times (aa + aa + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a} \\
 9453 &:= \frac{(aaaa + aaa + aa) \times (aa + aa + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a} \\
 94553 &:= \frac{(aaaaa + aaaa + aaa) \times (aa + aa + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a} \\
 945553 &:= \frac{(aaaaaa + aaaaa + aaaa) \times (aa + aa + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a} \\
 \\
 944 &:= \frac{(aaaaa - aaa) \times (a + a) - (aaa + a) \times aa}{(a + a) \times aa} \\
 9944 &:= \frac{(aaaaaa - aaaa) \times (a + a) - (aaa + a) \times aa}{(a + a) \times aa} \\
 99944 &:= \frac{(aaaaaaa - aaaaa) \times (a + a) - (aaa + a) \times aa}{(a + a) \times aa} \\
 999944 &:= \frac{(aaaaaaaa - aaaaaa) \times (a + a) - (aaa + a) \times aa}{(a + a) \times aa} \\
 \\
 945 &:= \frac{(aaa - aa - aa - a - a - a) \times aa - a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 9745 &:= \frac{(aaaa - aaa - aaa - a - a - a) \times aa - a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 97745 &:= \frac{(aaaaa - aaaa - aaaa - a - a - a) \times aa - a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 977745 &:= \frac{(aaaaaa - aaaaa - aaaaa - a - a - a) \times aa - a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 \\
 946 &:= \frac{(aaa - aa - aa - a - a - a) \times aa}{a \times a} \\
 9746 &:= \frac{(aaaa - aaa - aaa - a - a - a) \times aa}{a \times a} \\
 97746 &:= \frac{(aaaaa - aaaa - aaaa - a - a - a) \times aa}{a \times a} \\
 977746 &:= \frac{(aaaaaa - aaaaa - aaaaa - a - a - a) \times aa}{a \times a} \\
 \\
 947 &:= \frac{(aaa - aa - aa - a - a - a) \times aa + a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 9747 &:= \frac{(aaaa - aaa - aaa - a - a - a) \times aa + a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 97747 &:= \frac{(aaaaa - aaaa - aaaa - a - a - a) \times aa + a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 977747 &:= \frac{(aaaaaa - aaaaa - aaaaa - a - a - a) \times aa + a \times a}{a \times a} \\
 \\
 948 &:= \frac{(aaa - aa - aa - a - a - a) \times aa + a \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 9748 &:= \frac{(aaaa - aaa - aaa - a - a - a) \times aa + a \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 97748 &:= \frac{(aaaaa - aaaa - aaaa - a - a - a) \times aa + a \times (a + a)}{a \times a} \\
 977748 &:= \frac{(aaaaaa - aaaaa - aaaaa - a - a - a) \times aa + a \times (a + a)}{a \times a}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$949 := \frac{(aaa - aa - a - a - a - a - a) \times (aa - a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$9949 := \frac{(aaaa - aaa - a - a - a - a - a) \times (aa - a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

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$$952 := \frac{(aa + aa + aa + a) \times (aaa + a)}{(a + a) \times (a + a)}$$

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$$999955 := \frac{(aaaaaa - a - a - a - a - a) \times (aa - a - a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

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$$962 := \frac{(aaa + aaa) \times (aa + a + a)}{(a + a + a) \times a}$$

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$$964 := \frac{(aaa - a - a - a - a) \times (aa - a - a) + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

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$$9967 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - aa - aa - aa}{a}$$

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$$968 := \frac{(aaa - aa - aa - a) \times aa}{a \times a}$$

$$9768 := \frac{(aaaa - aaa - aaa - a) \times aa}{a \times a}$$

$$97768 := \frac{(aaaaa - aaaa - aaaa - a) \times aa}{a \times a}$$

$$977768 := \frac{(aaaaaa - aaaaa - aaaaa - a) \times aa}{a \times a}$$

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$$9769 := \frac{(aaaa - aaa - aaa - a) \times aa + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$97769 := \frac{(aaaaa - aaaa - aaaa - a) \times aa + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$977769 := \frac{(aaaaaa - aaaaa - aaaaa - a) \times aa + a \times a}{a \times a}$$

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$$9971 := \frac{(aaaa - a - a - a) \times (aa - a - a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

$$99971 := \frac{(aaaaa - a - a - a) \times (aa - a - a) - a \times a}{a \times a}$$

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$$999972 := \frac{(aaaaaa - a - a - a) \times (aa - a - a)}{a \times a}$$

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$$974 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aa - aa - a - a - a - a}{a}$$

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$$99978 := \frac{aaaaaa - aaaaa - aa - aa}{a}$$

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$$9779 := \frac{(aaaa - aaa - aaa) \times aa}{a \times a}$$

$$97779 := \frac{(aaaaa - aaaa - aaaa) \times aa}{a \times a}$$

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$$980 := \frac{aaaa - aaa - aa - aa + a + a}{a}$$

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$$9983 := \frac{(aaaa - a - a) \times (aa - a - a) + a \times (a + a)}{a \times a}$$

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$$999991 := \frac{aaaaaaaa - aaaaaa - aa + a + a}{a}$$

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$$9992 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - aa + a + a + a}{a}$$

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$$999992 := \frac{aaaaaaaa - aaaaaa - aa + a + a + a}{a}$$

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$$9993 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - aa + a + a + a + a}{a}$$

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$$9998 := \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - a - a}{a}$$

$$99998 := \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaaa - a - a}{a}$$

$$999998 := \frac{aaaaaaaa - aaaaaa - a - a}{a}$$

$$\begin{aligned}999 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa - a}{a} \\9999 &:= \frac{aaaaa - aaaa - a}{a} \\99999 &:= \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaaa - a}{a} \\999999 &:= \frac{aaaaaaaa - aaaaaa - a}{a}\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}1000 &:= \frac{aaaa - aaa}{a} \\10000 &:= \frac{aaaaa - aaaa}{a} \\100000 &:= \frac{aaaaaaa - aaaaa}{a} \\1000000 &:= \frac{aaaaaaaa - aaaaaa}{a}\end{aligned}$$

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